

T3.2 Translate the preliminary research questions identified in WP2 to concrete study designs

115966 – PREFER Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle

WP3 – Case Studies

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Abstract

WP2 sought to understand stakeholder concerns, needs and insights regarding the use of patient preference studies, aiming to recommend the use of specific methodologies for the case studies in WP3. WP3 designed, executed and evaluated the case studies of this project. Three disease areas were initially selected by PREFER for the case studies: rheumatoid arthritis (RA), neuromuscular diseases (NMD), and lung cancer. These three disease areas were selected as they span the PREFER criteria matrix for the inclusion of case studies (e.g., involve patients in different age groups, with diseases with different disease severity, treated by drugs that are relatively cheap or expensive). Besides the three case studies mentioned, PREFER aimed to add other case studies to its' portfolio. Such studies could be led by academic or industry partners. In this task the translation of work conducted in WP2 to actual case study plans is described. Based on a developed PREFER strategy documents, GAP analysis and specified selection and review criteria, in total 11 prospective case studies were conducted and included as part of the PREFER project. This report contains synopses of these 11 PREFER case studies.

Information within this report that may influence other PREFER tasks

Linked task	Points from this report that are of particular relevance to the linked task
3.4-3.8	Information from this task automatically will be taken forward in the ongoing phases of all included case studies
4.2	Synopsis documents provide input for operational guidance

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1. Introduction

The European public-private partnership PREFER ('Patient Preferences in Benefit and Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle') was launched in 2016¹. PREFER is a 5-year project, funded jointly by Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 (IMI; Europe's largest public-private initiative which aims to aid the development of better and safer medicines) and the European pharmaceutical industry (represented by EFPIA, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations). PREFER aims to strengthen patient-centric decision-making throughout the Medical Product Lifecycle (MPLC) by developing evidence-based recommendations to advise the different stakeholders (i.e., pharmaceutical industry, regulatory authorities, Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies, reimbursement agencies, academics, health care professionals, patients and patient organizations) on how and when patient preference studies should be performed, as well as how the results of these patient preference studies can be used to inform the decision-making process along the MPLC.

The PREFER project consists of four work packages (WPs), that are divided into several tasks. WP1 covers overall project management, dissemination, and communication activities as well as data management. WP2 sought to understand stakeholder concerns, needs and insights regarding the use of patient preference studies, aiming to recommend the use of specific methodologies for the case studies in WP3. WP3 designed, executed and evaluated the case studies of this project. Three disease areas were initially selected by PREFER for the case studies: rheumatoid arthritis (RA), neuromuscular diseases (NMD), and lung cancer. These three disease areas were selected as they span the PREFER criteria matrix for the inclusion of case studies (e.g., involve patients in different age groups, with diseases with different disease severity, treated by drugs that are relatively cheap or expensive). Besides the three case studies mentioned, PREFER aimed to add other case studies to its' portfolio. Such studies could be led by academic or industry partners. In this task the translation of work conducted in WP2 to actual case study plans is described.

2. Methods

2.1 PREFER strategy

Before the set-up and design of any of the case studies the PREFER steering committee wrote a strategy document to amongst others determine the focus of the PREFER project. This document (see full copy of the strategy document in Appendix 1) describes that the first phase of PREFER has been focused on the elicitation of stakeholders concerns and priorities, the identification of medical decision points and information needs across the medical product life cycle, the examination and prioritization of patient preference methods and methodological research questions. This resulted in report 2.8 which compiled information generated from Task 2.1-2.7 to identify unanswered methodological and non-methodological questions for consideration in the case studies. 28 research questions were considered as of highest priority. More information on the prioritization of research questions from Task 2.8 can be found in Smith et al². In accordance with the objectives of PREFER the high priority questions were grouped in three categories depending on if the questions aimed to: 1) address the **reliability** of preference methods; 2) assess the impact of different **educational materials**; or 3) relate to factors that could explain certain preferences and implications for **generalizability**.

The strategy document further states that the following specific items should be addressed with each empirical case study:

- What is the preference-sensitive decision underlying the patient preference study?
- Related to the objective of the case study – what type of preferences are needed?
- Discrete Choice Experiment will be the first preference method choice in empirical and simulation case studies. If DCE is not feasible in an empirical case study then a justification needs to be provided. Feasibility will be determined, but not exclusively on the following criteria: cognitive capacity of the proposed sample, sample size of the proposed case study, applicability and information needs.
- Methodological research questions should reflect the grouping of methods in Task 2.8 and be aligned with the objectives of PREFER as described in the DoW. Therefore, every case study relevant for PREFER should cover as many as possible and reasonable out of the following questions:

1. Reliability

- How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (ex: threshold technique of a few attributes vs. DCE; ex: swing weighting vs. DCE or AHP)

- How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?
- To what degree do small changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes impact results for a given method?

II. Impact of educational materials

- Does application of guidelines indicating that an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features result in a more accurate elicitation of patient preferences, compared with the traditional educational approach?
- Does the incremental value of applying an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features justify the additional investments needed (budget, other resources) required to create this component?

III. Generalizability of results

- How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases?
- What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?
- Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, patient activation, and health locus of control) and Class II constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding *an individual's preferences (covariates); i.e., can certain constructs(?) serve as covariates that are predictive of preference for particular diseases? Across different diseases and states of those diseases, is there consistent covariation of preference with certain psychological constructs?)*

2.2 Gap analysis and call for academic-led studies

After completion of the PREFER strategy, the inventory of historical case studies in WP3 task 3.3, and the synopses of the three PREFER core case studies and two already approved additional industry-led case studies, a GAP analysis was conducted to provide insights on priority areas that were not covered yet by any of the case studies conducted or planned at the time. See Appendix 2 for a full overview of the GAP analysis. In summary clear gaps were identified for studies addressing medical products in 'pre-discovery' or 'pre-submission to regulator or HTA'. Studies were lacking that provide answers to research questions (RQ) related to 'impact of attribute changes' and 'impact of educational material'. Finally, methods that were identified as promising in WP2 but underrepresented in the case studies were: Probabilistic threshold technique, Best-Worst scaling case 2, Q-method, Standard gamble, Time-trade-off, Analytical hierarchy process, Swing weighting and Visual analogue scale.

2.3 Selection procedure of academic-led studies

Based on the GAP analysis a call for additional case studies was formulated and disseminated to the full PREFER consortium. All PREFER partners were encouraged to submit proposals for new case studies. These studies should:

- Ensure alignment with PREFER strategy document
- Ensure alignment with PREFER timelines
- Ensure contributions to additional studies does not compete with manpower already allocated to core case studies

Study proposals that were submitted by academic partners were reviewed by the full SC since those studies required budget reallocation. PREFER management board made €100.000 euro available for additional academic case studies. Case studies were discussed during a SC meeting and graded as (A) approval for submission to decision board, (AC) approval for submission to decision board with conditions, or (R) rejected for further consideration at this stage. This decision was based on the study complying with the assessment criteria listed in table 1.

2.4 Selection procedure of industry-led studies

This procedure is described in detail in the report of task 3.4.

Table 1. Table used by the SC for review of submitted academic-led case studies.

	Complete this column (v=approval x=no approval)	Comments (further conditions mentioned for the granted approval)
Study has appropriate preference sensitive situation (appropriate = clearly described & clinically relevant)		
Study addresses appropriate methodological RQ (appropriate = RQ originate from prioritized list and ideally are highlighted in gap analysis)		
Study applies appropriate methods (appropriate = DCE or valid argumentation to use other method from list of 2.7 report)		
Study will finish in appropriate timelines (appropriate = draft report in June 2020)		
Conduct of study by research team will not compete with contributions to and conduct of PREFER core case studies		

2.5 Review of case studies

All case studies in PREFER were asked to first provide a synopsis of the study proposal. This synopsis followed a standardized template and should at least describe:

- Clinical context
- Methodological context
- Research questions
- Methods used
- What priority PREFER research questions are addressed
- How study supports or informs the MPLC
- How study might contribute to final recommendations
- Study population (inclusion & exclusion criteria, sample size)
- Accompanying psychological instruments and educational tools
- Endpoints to be reported
- Deliverables
- Estimated time to completion of the study

The synopsis of all case studies was reviewed by members of the SC and the scientific advisory board members (scientific advisory board was only involved in review of the core and additional academic case studies to avoid any conflict of interest) before formal approval of the case study as a prospective PREFER case study. See Appendix 3 for the review checklist that was used for these reviews.

3. Results

The three core case studies in PREFER were designed and approved for inclusion. The full synopses of the case studies are shown in Appendix 4. In summary (Table 2), the case studies describe three different disease areas, and all have a qualitative research part preceding a DCE in combination with another preference elicitation method.

Four additional academic-led case studies were submitted and approved. The full synopses of the case studies are shown in Appendix 5. In summary (Table 3), the case studies describe four different disease areas, and all have a qualitative research part. Two studies combined DCE and Swing weighting, one study only used DCE, and one study only applied PTT.

Four additional industry-led case studies were submitted and approved. The full synopses of the case studies are shown described in Appendix 6. In summary (Table 4), the case studies describe four different disease areas, and all have a qualitative research part. Two studies combined DCE and BWS case 1 and two only used DCE.

Related to the PREFER strategy priority research questions (see paragraph 2.1), the **number of case studies addressing the questions is listed:**

- How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods? **Addressed in 7 case studies**
- How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population? **Addressed in 7 case studies**
- To what degree do small changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes impact results for a given method? **Not addressed**
- Does application of guidelines indicating that an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features result in a more accurate elicitation of patient preferences, compared with the traditional educational approach? **Addressed in 2 case studies**
- Does the incremental value of applying an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features justify the additional investments needed (budget, other resources) required to create this component? **Addressed in 5 case studies**
- How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases? **Addressed in 5 case studies**
- What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks? **Addressed in 6 case studies**
- Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, patient activation, and health locus of control) and Class II

constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding *an individual's preferences (covariates); i.e., can certain constructs(?) serve as covariates that are predictive of preference for particular diseases? Across different diseases and states of those diseases, is there consistent covariation of preference with certain psychological constructs?)* **Addressed in 10 case studies**

Table 2. Summary overview of core case studies

Therapeutic area	Team leads	Primary stakeholder	MPLC point of interest	Methods used – Quantitative only
Rheumatoid arthritis	Karim Raza, University of Birmingham Larissa Valor-Mendez, University of Erlangen Jorien Veldwijk, Erasmus University Rotterdam Rachael DiSantostefano, J&J	Industry	Post approval	DCE Probabilistic Threshold Technique
Neuromuscular diseases	Grainne Gorman, University of Newcastle Ardine de Wit, UMC Utrecht Cathy Anne Pinto, MSD	Industry	Pre-discovery	DCE Q-method Best-Worst Scaling case 2
Lung Cancer	Gabriella Pravettoni, IEO Isabelle Huys, University of Leuven Serena Oliveri, IEO Meredith Smith, Alexion	Industry	Clinical drug development	DCE Swing Weighting plus point allocation

Table 3. Summary overview of additional academic-led case studies

Therapeutic area	Team Leads	Primary stakeholder	MPLC point of interest	Methods used – Quantitative only
Diabetes	Chiara Whichello, Erasmus University Rotterdam Ian Smith, UMC Utrecht Ardine de Wit, UMC Utrecht Esther de Bekker-Grob, Erasmus University Rotterdam	Industry	Post-approval	DCE Swing Weighting plus point allocation
Multiple Myeloma	Rosanne Janssens, University of Leuven Isabelle Huys, University of Leuven	Regulators	Marketing Authorization	DCE Swing Weighting

Hemophilia (PAVING)	Eline van Overbeeke, University of Leuven Isabelle Huys, University of Leuven	HTA	Reimbursement	Probabilistic Threshold Technique
Rheumatoid Arthritis	Karin Schölin-Bywall, Uppsala University Ulrik Kihlbom, Uppsala University Jorien Veldwijk, Erasmus University Rotterdam	Regulators	Marketing Authorization	DCE

Table 4. Summary overview of additional industry-led case studies

Therapeutic area	Team Leads	Primary stakeholder	MPLC point of interest	Methods used – Quantitative only
Myocardial infarction	Cathy Anne Pinto, MSD Tommi Tervonen, Evidera	Industry	Clinical drug development	DCE Best-Worst Scaling case 1
Chronic pain	Leo Russo, Pfizer	Regulators	Marketing Authorization	DCE Best-Worst Scaling case 1
COPD	Nigel Cook, Novartis	HTA	Reimbursement	DCE
Hemophilia	Leo Russo, Pfizer	HTA	Reimbursement	DCE

4. Discussion and conclusion

The translation of WP2 work into 11 prospective case studies was described as part of this task. All these case studies were conducted as part of the PREFER consortium work. All case studies address a critical decision point in the MPLC as described in T2.3, provide results relevant to key stakeholders, address prioritized methodological research questions, will contribute to the evidence base for DCE and the comparison between DCE and other promising methods, and provide insights on generalizability of results across (sub-)populations. With the conduct of these studies PREFER will add to the current existing evidence base for the use of preference elicitation methods in decision-making along the MPLC.

References

1. de Bekker-Grob, E. W., et al., . (2017). Giving Patients' Preferences a Voice in Medical Treatment Life Cycle: The PREFER Public-Private Project. *Patient*, 10(3), 263-266.
2. Smith, I. P., DiSantostefano, R. L., de Bekker-Grob, E. W., Levitan, B., Berlin, C., Veldwijk, J., & de Wit, G. A. (2021). Methodological Priorities for Patient Preferences Research: Stakeholder Input to the PREFER Public-Private Project. *Patient*, 14(5), 449-453.

Appendix 1: PREFER strategy document

30 September 2018

1. Executive summary

As of today, there is no generally accepted set of guidelines or recommendations on when and how to elicit patient preference information that is ready for decision making in Europe. As one of the most highly ranked requirements that was shared by decision makers in the IMI PREFER interviews was that preference studies should have a strong evidentiary standard so that they could be trusted to reflect preferences of the intended population. Patient preferences are currently not systematically considered for decision making to the full extent in drug development / patient access. By developing expert and evidence-based recommendations, PREFER aims to guide industry, regulatory authorities, HTA bodies and reimbursement agencies on how patient preferences can be assessed and used to inform medical product decision making. This will ultimately strengthen patients' voices and input into drug development throughout the entire medical product lifecycle (MPLC).

The first phase of PREFER has been focused on the elicitation of stakeholders concerns and priorities, the identification of medical decision points across the medical products life cycle, the examination and prioritization of patient preference methods and methodological research questions.

There is unanimous agreement and strong recommendation of the PREFER advisory groups to focus on a clear set of topics for future research and activities of PREFER. In line with the overall aim of PREFER '... to strengthen patient-centric decision making throughout the life cycle of medicinal products ... by developing evidence-based recommendations...', these topics need to be prioritized and selected in order to maximize the impact of PREFER. In essence this requires to identify and to address the biggest hurdles that currently stop decision makers to more often consider patient preference information for decision making throughout the MPLC. Therefore, scientific and non-scientific questions relevant to the entire MPLC need to be addressed.

EMA representatives strongly recommended to consider an EMA Methods Qualification that is conducted in the framework of scientific advice as a means to further focus and to maximize the impact of PREFER. Other stakeholders such as HTA bodies can be included through joint scientific advice. The HTA advisory group has also supported this approach. The steering committee agreed that Discrete Choice Experiments (DCE) will be used as the method of choice for the qualification process and for the empirical and simulation case studies based on the rich set of evidence and experience that is readily available for this method. It is expected that several of the identified high priority scientific and non-scientific questions need to be addressed for a successful application for qualification. Of note, this does not mean that PREFER considers DCE to be superior to other methods.

If successful, this approach has a number of tangible outcomes that will ultimately benefit patients, namely by,

- Providing clear guidance as to how DCE can be used in any appropriate development program
- Providing the proof of concept that patient preference methods can be qualified
- Providing a blueprint for the qualification of further methods by other applicants.

While the EMA qualification process requires a large set of scientific and non-scientific questions to be addressed, there is in particular a need to understand the role of patient preferences in early decision making to foster a more systematic involvement of patients in early phases of development. This is considered to be a prerequisite for successful use of preference information for decision making at later stages.

While PREFER is focussed on scientific questions, operational aspects are equally important for the credibility of patient preference studies. To that end, PREFER will develop an operational best

practice document that will be informed by stakeholder needs and learnings from case studies.

Some topics might be more effectively addressed by other projects and may even not be in scope of PREFER in a strict sense. Therefore, PREFER will seek for opportunities to collaborate and to create synergies with other initiatives such as IMI PARADIGM.

Finally, PREFER acknowledges that the field of preference research is rapidly developing. PREFER, therefore, will systematically monitor the preference research environment and adjust its strategy as appropriate.

2. Background

The general objective of PREFER is:

“By developing expert and evidence-based recommendations, PREFER aims to guide industry, regulatory authorities and HTA bodies and reimbursement agencies on how patient preferences can be assessed and used to inform medical product decision making. (ref: PREFER_clarified_objective-final-27Apr2017)”. This general objective supports the overall aim of PREFER ‘... to strengthen patient-centric decision making throughout the life cycle of medicinal products ... by developing evidence-based recommendations...’. Ultimately, patients will benefit through accepted pathways to ensure their preferences can systematically inform decision making.

Two central sub-objectives according to the Description of Work (DoW) PREFER are:

- to evaluate methodologies that measure preferences for their capacity to capture heterogeneity of preferences and variability among individual patient perspectives, having regard to how well-informed the preferences are as well as being representative of a wider population of patients.
- to define when and how to include patient preferences to support assessment and decision making by Regulatory Authorities, HTA bodies, and reimbursement agencies.

The first phase of PREFER has been focused on the elicitation of stakeholders concerns and priorities, the identification of medical decision points and information needs across the medical products life cycle, the examination and prioritization of patient preference methods and methodological research questions.

This science based approach resulted in report 2.8 which compiled information generated from Task 2.1-2.7 to identify unanswered methodological and non-methodological questions for consideration in the case studies. Generally, irrespective of the MPLC, the most important requirements of a preference study as revealed in the literature, methods assessments (WP 2.5, 2.6, 2.7), and interviews and focus groups (2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5) were that

- preference studies have a strong evidentiary standard and could be trusted to reflect preferences of the intended population;
- preference heterogeneity could be assessed;
- patient burden was minimized and patient understanding of surveys was maximized

(ref: PREFER report 2.8, section 3.1)

28 research questions were considered as highest priority and 39 were considered second priority, to be used to formulate the final methodological and non-methodological questions to be evaluated in the empirical case studies and simulation case studies. In accordance with the objectives of PREFER the high priority questions were grouped in three categories depending on if the questions aimed to: address the **reliability** of preference methods; assess the impact of different **educational materials**; or relate to factors that could explain certain preferences and implications for **generalizability**. (Ref. 2.8, Final report)

The high-quality scientific approach of WP 2, the comprehensive list of research questions and candidate preference methodologies have been acknowledged by all stakeholders. However, the Scientific Advisory Board, the Regulatory Stakeholder Advisory Group and the Stakeholder Advisory Group of HTA bodies & reimbursement agencies unanimously encouraged PREFER to take a stronger focus to maximize the impact on PREFER's overall goal. This includes a clear outline which methods and which research questions will be investigated in case studies and how this will turn into meaningful recommendations.

EMA representatives strongly suggested PREFER to consider the EMA Qualification Procedure as new opportunity for PREFER. This proposal has been strongly endorsed by other stakeholders like FDA and HTA bodies.

A successful EMA Qualification Procedure takes PREFER beyond pure recommendations, i.e., maximizes the impact of this IMI project. It will provide reassurance and thereby increase certainty for stakeholders that patient preferences are in general acceptable in the Regulatory environment of drug development and can support decision making.

3. Further PREFER strategy and tactics

Following the recommendations of all stakeholders and after intense discussions within the PREFER SC the EMA Qualification Procedure has been accepted as an approach that provides PREFER a strong focus

- maximizing the impact on the overall project goal
- removing of the biggest hurdles that currently stop decision makers to more often consider patient preference information for decision making throughout the MPLC
- providing the best opportunity to involve HTA bodies through joint scientific advice, if feasible
- avoiding duplication with other initiatives and striving for synergies (example, FDA, IMI PARADIGM, new ISPOR taskforce)

It is acknowledged that this will not hinder IMI PREFER to provide recommendations on more simple methodologies as alternatives in particular in the rare disease environment and compare those with DCE in this setting.

While focusing within the EMA Qualification Procedure on one or two methods, the procedure will require to address a number of high priority research questions which will be evaluated in empirical case studies as well as in simulation studies based on their capacity to enable trade-offs between different attributes.

The documentation will serve as a blueprint to qualify further methods with a much lower burden as many general aspects are already addressed. Ideally, the outcome of this procedure will be a CHMP endorsement of the selected method(s). Ultimately, the qualification needs to address the requirement that preference studies have a strong evidentiary standard and could be trusted to reflect preferences of the intended population. This is expected to require substantial work on the high priority research questions as well as development of processes and consensus on required documentation.

The PREFER SC has selected DCE as first method of choice because of its strength of evidence that is already available, existing experience of decision makers with the method and because it measures trade-offs and is thus suitable for decisions as taken by industry, regulators and HTA bodies & reimbursement agencies.

Successful applications that build on patient preferences information require a systematic approach throughout the entire MPLC. This, in particular, requires a strong focus on early decision making.

PREFER to the most part will focus on scientific and operational aspects of patient preference studies to be used for decision making throughout MPLC. Some operational aspects, e.g., a reasonable compensation of patients participating in preference studies are out of scope of PREFER and, yet,

may influence the assessment of the trustworthiness of a study. IMI PARADIGM may provide general guidance in the field of compensation of patients. Thus, both projects may benefit from a collaboration in this area.

While PREFER focussed on scientific questions, operational aspects are equally important for the credibility of patient preference studies. To that end, PREFER will develop an operational best practice document that will be informed by stakeholder needs and learnings from case studies.

4. Required contributions from case studies

Above strategy requires from PREFER contributing case studies

- that the study objectives are aligned with the PREFER goals and strategy
- that the study plays an integral role in addressing scientific and operational questions to ultimately inform PREFER recommendations and the EMA Qualification Procedure

The following specific items should be addressed with each empirical case study:

a. What is the preference-sensitive decision underlying the patient preference study?

Example 1: The available treatments for a specific disease provide very different benefit-risk profiles. A treatment in development has shown benefits but also serious risks for the patient. The development of the drug has been put on hold due to the safety risks. A PP study seems to be of value for further strategic decisions about the treatment. A tabular overview of all benefits and risks as known for the treatment landscape (ideally together with their effects in the clinical trials) will help showing the preference sensitive situation and already give an outlook to the use of the preference data in the benefit-risk decision process when the preference study is available. (For more examples see report from task 2.3 as well as the excel overview of preference sensitive situations prepared in task 2.2)

Example 2: patient preferences to show the unmet need of patients (PREFER NMD study)

b. Related to the objective of the case study – what type of preferences are needed? (preference for one treatment, preference for several attributes, preference for one attribute, is preference exploration or elicitation needed. If elicitation: ranking, rating, threshold or trade-off results?)

c. As outlined above *Discrete Choice Experiment* will be the first preference method choice in empirical and simulation case studies. If DCE is not feasible in an empirical case study then a justification needs to be provided. Feasibility will be determined, but not exclusively on the following criteria: cognitive capacity of the proposed sample, sample size of the proposed case study, applicability and information needs.

d. Methodological research questions should reflect the grouping of methods in Task 2.8 and be aligned with the objectives of PREFER as described in the DoW. Therefore, every case study relevant for PREFER should cover as many as possible and reasonable out of the following questions:

1. Reliability

- How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (ex: threshold technique of a few attributes vs. DCE; ex: swing weighting vs. DCE or AHP)

- How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?
- To what degree do small changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes impact results for a given method?

II. Impact of educational materials

- Does application of guidelines indicating that an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features result in a more accurate elicitation of patient preferences, compared with the traditional educational approach?
- Does the incremental value of applying an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features justify the additional investments needed (budget, other resources) required to create this component?

III. Generalizability of results

- How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases?
- What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?
- Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, patient activation, and health locus of control) and Class II constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding *an individual's preferences (covariates); i.e., can certain constructs(?) serve as covariates that are predictive of preference for particular diseases? Across different diseases and states of those diseases, is there consistent covariation of preference with certain psychological constructs?*

Appendix 2. GAP analysis presentation

PREFER case study portfolio - GAP analysis –

Jorien Veldwijk on behalf of WP3 leads
03-12-2018

Disclaimer: This presentation and its contents reflects the view of the presenter and not the view of PREFER, IMI, the European Union or EFPIA.

prefer.

2

Content of portfolio document

- Case study leads / managers / contact persons
- Start / end dates

- Disease area
- Primary clinical research question
- Stakeholder(s) for which study is relevant
- MPLC placement
- Study population
- Sample size

- Methodological research questions
- Methods applied
- Countries included

prefer.

3

Recap - Overview of studies

- 3 core case studies (T3.5-3.7)
- 20 historical case studies (T3.3)
- 2 additional industry-led case studies (T3.4)

prefer.

4

Overview 1 – Stakeholder and MPLC

	Core case studies (n=3)	Historical studies (n=20)	Additional industry studies (n=2)
Stakeholders			
Industry	3	6	2
HTA	3	7	2
Regulator	3	6	2
MPLC placement			
Pre-discovery	1	-	-
Development	1	7	1
Regulatory submission	-	6	-
HTA submission	-	2	-
Post-marketing	2	9	1

5

Overview 2 – Methodological RQ

	Core case studies (n=3)	Historical studies (n=20)	Additional industry studies (n=2)
Methodological RQ			
priority questions 1.2 & 1.3 Comparing methods	3	-	2
priority question 1.4 & 1.5 & 1.6 Impact of changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes	-	2	-
priority question 1.14 Generalizability of preferences across populations?	3	10	1
priority question 1.16 Impact of educational material on understanding and preferences	1	1	-
priority question 1.19 Can psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs and Class II constructs provide insight regarding an individual's preferences	3	4	2
priority question 1.10 What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?	3	2	1

6

Overview 3 – Methods

	Core case studies (n=3)	Historical studies (n=20)	Additional industry studies (n=2)
Discrete choice experiment / Best- Worst scaling case 3	3	16	2
Standard gamble			
Probabilistic Threshold Technique	1		
Time-Trade-Off			
Best-Worst scaling case 1		1	2
Best-Worst scaling case 2	1	1	
Analytical hierarchy process			
Swing weighting			
Visual analogue scale			
Q-method	1		
Survey-methods – Likert		3	
Interviews / Focus group	3	14	2

7

Summary

- Clear gaps:
 - MPLC placement
 - Pre-discovery
 - Pre-submission to regulator or HTA
 - Methodological RQ
 - Priority question 1.4 & 1.5 & 1.6 Impact attribute changes
 - Priority question 1.16 Impact of educational material
 - Methods
 - Limited use: Probabilistic threshold technique, Best-Worst scaling case 2, Q-method
 - Not used: Standard gamble, Time-trade-off, Analytical hierarchy process, Swing weighting, Visual analogue scale

prefer.

8

How to use the gap analysis

- Additional case studies should:
 - Align with PREFER strategy
 - Align with PREFER timelines
 - Not compete with contribution to core studies
 - Ideally address gaps in portfolio
 - All RQ from strategy are prioritized from larger list
 - All methods from 2.7 are promising
 - Not addressing gaps does not mean a study is not relevant
 - Preferably we do address the gaps in at least 1 additional case study (problem: we did not specifically ask partners to address particular questions, methods, MPLC points)

prefer.

Appendix 3: Review checklist for case study synopsis

PREFER reviewer checklist

For information for reviewers: these review sheets will be made available to PREFER members and, at the end of the PREFER project, these review sheets will be made publicly available.

Case study title	Reviewer name; date of review

Reviewer overall recommendations [for review of synopsis]
<input type="checkbox"/> Case study synopsis & associated documents are approved without minor comments or <input type="checkbox"/> Case study synopsis & associated documents are approved with minor comments or <input type="checkbox"/> Case study synopsis & associated documents should be re-submitted to the review committee

Criteria for review of case study synopsis	Y / I / N [Yes/Inadequately/No]	Reviewer comments (obligatory to complete when assigning 'inadequately' or 'no' for a given criteria)
The study objectives addresses prioritized PREFER research questions		
The methods selected for the study are aligned with recommended methodology from PREFER WP2		
The methods selected for the study are suitably aligned with case study objectives (i.e., can provide valid answers to both clinical and methodological research questions)		
The study population proposed for the case study is suitable to provide valid answers to the proposed research questions		
The described outcome measures of the case study are fitting to the proposed clinical and methodological research questions		
The case study will contribute to insights for decision making for at least one of the PREFER stakeholders along the medical product life cycle (Industry, Regulatory, HTA/payer)		
The study documents clearly describe how this case study will contribute to insights for decision making for at least one of the PREFER stakeholders along the medical product life cycle		
The case study will support the PREFER final recommendations document		
Proposed timelines of the case study are aligned with PREFER timelines and needs		

Any additional comments from reviewer that are not covered by criteria above:

Appendix 4: Synopses of the PREFER core case studies

RA study

Disease / Clinical Context: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a common chronic inflammatory disease affecting approximately 1% of the general public (Silman and Pearson 2002). The typical age of onset is between 40 to 60 years old although it can begin at younger or older ages as well. Symptoms include pain, swelling, stiffness and fatigue. If untreated, RA causes joint damage and disability. It is associated with significant extra-articular manifestations including accelerated cardiovascular disease, reducing life expectancy by approximately 10 years (Dougados 2016).

It is not currently possible to cure RA so disease control is the primary goal of treatment for which long-term treatment is usually required. Currently available treatments include conventional and biological disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (cDMARDs and bDMARDs), with varying benefit/risk profiles. The mainstay of treatment is with the cDMARD methotrexate (MTX) which is relatively cheap and to which approximately one third of patients respond very well (Lopez-Olivo et al 2014). For patients who do not respond to MTX alone, remission can often (though not always) be achieved with additional strategies including the use of one or more cDMARDs and the addition of one or more (expensive) bDMARDs. However, the prolonged use of both cDMARDs and bDMARDs is associated with considerable risk, including the risk of infection and of lung, liver and haematological toxicity (Lopez-Olivo et al 2014).

Very early treatment of RA is associated with improved outcomes (Nell et al, 2004; Raza et al 2006) and there is now considerable research interest in the idea of treating 'at risk' individuals in the preclinical and earliest clinically apparent phases of RA (e.g. Raza et al 2016, van Steenberg et al 2018) to assess whether a relatively short course of therapy will prevent or delay the onset of RA. EULAR recommendations identify five such groups, that are appropriate for prospective trials: individuals **without** RA having: (i) genetic risk factors for RA; (ii) environmental risk factors for RA; (iii) systemic autoimmunity associated with RA; (iv) symptoms without clinical arthritis (arthralgia); or (v) unclassified arthritis (Gerlag, Raza et al. 2012).

Two completed (Bos et al, 2009; Gerlag et al 2016) and 5 ongoing (APPIPRA; ARIAA; TREAT EARLIER; STAPRA; SToPRA) proof-of-concept preventive trials are assessing the effectiveness of drugs that are currently used to treat RA (methotrexate; rituximab; abatacept; methylprednisolone; atorvastatin; hydroxychloroquine; dexamethasone) to prevent or delay the onset of RA in one or more of these five 'at risk' groups. In particular, the SToPRA trial (evaluating the preventive effectiveness of a 12 month course of hydroxychloroquine) is recruiting asymptomatic first degree relatives of RA patients and individuals attending health fairs who are autoantibody positive (EULAR 'at risk' stages i-iii).

While members of the general public have a 1/100 probability to develop RA, first degree relatives (EULAR 'at risk' stages i-ii) of existing patients are four times more likely to develop RA in the future. Ongoing research is identifying additional biomarkers which can identify those first degree relatives who are at particularly increased risk and data already suggest that the presence of RA related autoantibodies increases the risk significantly above 4/100. First degree relatives are therefore candidates for preventive approaches. A recent trial of a non-pharmacological preventive intervention in this group showed a positive effect of personalized RA risk education on risk-related behavioural intentions and actual behavior change (Sparks et al 2018). Individuals in this group are also currently being recruited to several large prospective cohorts to increase understanding of the etiology of RA (PREVENT-RA; SERA; Arthritis Check-up). Our case study will therefore focus on first degree relatives of RA patients as a group with an elevated risk of developing RA in the future who are currently being studied in several preventive and prospective studies.

Understanding the preferences of ‘at risk’ groups is especially important in preventive contexts, where there is uncertainty around not only the effectiveness and safety of a particular treatment strategy (as per standard patient preference studies), but also around the individual’s baseline risk of developing RA in the future. As understanding of the preventive effectiveness of existing treatments for RA continues to grow, and the development of novel treatments targeting specific pathways associated with the development of RA becomes a real possibility with increasing understanding of RA etiology, knowledge of the preferences of ‘at risk’ individuals around both existing RA treatments adapted for preventative purposes and (as yet) hypothetical new ones will be valuable to inform the development and regulation of efficient preventive strategies for RA. In addition, it is of value to understand societal views of these preventative treatments by assessing treatment preferences in the general public (who of course on average have a 1 in 100 chance of developing RA at some stage) and asking them to imagine being at an enhanced risk of developing RA (future predictive tests are likely to be able to identify which members of the general public (without a family history of RA) have a particularly high risk of RA redevelopment. This adds an interesting element to the study from a methodological point of view as well; what is the impact of endowing members of the general public with an increased risk of developing RA and how do their preferences compare to those of first degree relatives with this actual increased risk of RA? A recent (full paper not yet published) discrete choice experiment looking at the preferences for pharmacological interventions of 448 first-degree relatives, suggested that method of administration may be an important determinant of preventive treatment acceptability (Harrison et al, 2017). In contrast a related best worst scaling pilot study found that the effectiveness and risks of preventive treatments were more important than method of administration for a small sample of 34 first degree relatives taking part in a prospective cohort study (Finckh et al, 2016). Participants in the former study were however self-reported first degree relatives (as compared to relatives of confirmed RA patients) taking part in an online market research panel. There is considerable evidence (e.g. Simons et al 2016) that there are a number of widespread public misperceptions around RA, and that it is often confused with other conditions (e.g. osteoarthritis) and as a result peoples’ ability to self-identify as a first-degree relative of a person with RA (as compared to recruiting relatives of confirmed RA patients) might not be entirely reliable. This limits the validity of self-reported relationships to people with RA to some extent, and as a result limits the usability of this method of recruiting first degree relatives and the obtained results. For that reason, in our case study, first degree relatives will be recruited via existing patients with a confirmed diagnosis of RA in secondary care settings in both the UK and Germany. We also propose to assess the preferences of members of the general public via an online panel to understand degree of public demand and preferences for preventive therapies for RA and to compare them with those of individuals with an elevated risk of developing RA in the future (i.e. first degree relatives). Survey questions will be added to measure who from the general public sample self-identify as being a relative of a patient with RA (it is almost certain that a small proportion will self-identify in this way). Data from members of the general public who do self-identify will be compared with data from members of the general public who do not.

Methodological Context: This preference study is designed to answer both clinical and methodological research questions at the same time. The clinical questions have been proposed by the RA core team. The methods questions have been taken from the PREFER research questions that were generated within WP2 and prioritized as part of Task 3.2. In March of 2018, WP2 (Task 2.8) distributed a list of research questions to guide the development of the case study protocols. The document covered 106 questions reflecting the questions raised by PREFER stakeholders (Academics, Patients, Physicians, HTA/Payers, Industry, Regulators) regarding patient preference studies. These 106 questions were grouped into primary, secondary and tertiary questions based on being related to methodology, clinical insights or interpretation of patient preference results. Primary and Secondary questions can be tested in PREFER case studies and Tertiary questions cannot. To prioritize among the Primary and Secondary questions, a total of 38 methods experts were asked to complete a ranking exercise to indicate their

personal top 5 questions that were deemed most relevant to study in the prospective clinical case studies. They were also asked to indicate, given their knowledge of the existing literature on patient preferences, how many studies answering their prioritized questions are currently available in the literature. Based on the ranking by these methods experts a top 10 list of prioritized research questions was drafted. These prioritized research questions were presented to and discussed with different stakeholders (amongst other HTA/Payers and Regulators). Stakeholder confirmed that their prioritized questions were among the questions prioritized by PREFER.

This case study has selected three of the top 10 prioritized methodological research questions to be studied. Additionally, three secondary questions (clinical questions) were added to the case study as well since they were put forward by stakeholders as being relevant (see secondary clinical objective question 3 & 4).

We also propose to compare the preferences of a group of first degree relatives with those of a sample of the general public by means of generating a highly representative sample via an E-panel. This will increase analytic capacity of this case study, facilitating robust assessment of the PREFER methodological research questions, and allow investigation of the impact of having an elevated risk status due to being a first degree relative of someone with the disease in question. Adding a large sample from the general public will therefore be of interest from both a clinical and a methodological perspective.

Research Question(s)		
Primary Objectives	Clinical: What are preferences of 'at risk' individuals (first degree relatives of patients with RA (EULAR 'at risk' stages i-ii) and the general population) about preventive treatments for RA?	Methodological: How similar are the results of DCE and probabilistic threshold technique?
Secondary Objectives	What is the maximum acceptable risks/Minimum acceptable benefit (e.g., how much risk reduction is necessary for a preventive drug to be acceptable. Then how much risk reduction would be traded for a reduction in risk of serious side effect etc.)? Is there heterogeneity in preferences and how can that be explained? Are there cross country (i.e., cultural and regional) differences between UK and Germany regarding the aforementioned elements? Are there differences regarding the aforementioned elements between first degree relatives (EULAR 'at risk' stages i-ii) and the general population?	To what degree do small changes in the definitions of attributes impact results? To what extent does health literacy, numeracy and health locus of control, and illness perception explain variation in preferences?
Method/design		
Methods	Focus groups to identify attributes of preventive treatment that impact on preferences to be incorporated in design of quantitative methods below. Comparison between DCE and Probabilistic threshold technique in terms of their ability to elicit preferences for preventive treatments, and to assess relative importance of treatment attributes, quantify trade-offs between attributes, assess	

	<p>preference heterogeneity, determine imposed cognitive burden, compare logistical aspects of both methods.</p> <p>Explain variation in preferences identified above on the basis of differences in health literacy, numeracy, health locus of control and illness perception as well as ,attitude towards medication, perceived risk of developing RA and attitudes towards and understanding of RA</p>
Background and Rationale	
<p>PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>1.3/2d1 How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods? (ex: threshold technique of a few attributes vs. DCE; ex: swing weighting vs. DCE or AHP)</p> <p>1.4/2e To what degree do small changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes impact results for a given method?</p> <p>1.2/2d How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?</p> <p>1.6/2e2 To what degree do preferences for a given set of attributes change with different wording of the same attributes? (This is a very real-world problem for regulators and payers. Can they trust that the results of a preference study done by one stakeholder or academic group are essentially the same as those of a study done for the same disease/treatment by another stakeholder or group?)</p> <p>1.10/4b1 What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?</p> <p>2.33/11f To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Region?</p> <p>2.34/1g To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Culture?</p> <p>1.14/9b How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases?</p> <p>2.30/11c To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Information level of patients</p> <p>2.31/11d To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Disease experience or severity</p>
<p>How the research questions support or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>The current case study is of high interest to all stakeholders involved in the medical product lifecycle (industry, regulators and HTA/payers). Options for prevention range from repurposing existing drugs with known risks but unknown benefits in this phase of disease, to the development of novel drugs that target new pathways relevant to RA development.</p> <p>Strategic decision-making for companies about whether to invest in such clinical preventive RA drug development programs, as well as decision-making about approval or reimbursement of these therapies, require weighing benefits and risks attributed to these therapies.</p> <p>In some situations, information about individuals' preferences is important in addition to the available clinical evidence, since decision-makers might have different views about risk tolerance compared to those in the target population. This applies especially to decisions that concern a chronic disease, quality of life, or when it is unclear whether the benefits exceed the risks.</p> <p>In this case study, medical community, industry, regulators and HTA/payers have no clear views about what treatment attributes matter most to 'at risk' individuals who are likely candidates for preventive RA treatment and what trade-offs these individuals would make. The proposed case study will shed light on this question,</p>

	<p>and will provide information that will be useful to support decision-making at these three levels along the medicinal product development cycle.</p> <p>Therefore, this project will have relevance to preclinical phases, all clinical phases as well as market approval and reimbursement. Preferences of the anticipated users of the drug could be highly insightful for regulators when making their decision for approval (given the side-effects the drug has and the absence of disease in the treated individuals). Also, HTA representatives and payers might be highly interested in preference information when deciding on reimbursement of this drug for the new target population in which costs of the drug and effectiveness of the drug in a currently healthy population where there is considerable uncertainty about the future development of disease will need to be carefully weighted.</p>
How the study might contribute to the final recommendations	<p>Since this case study will compare different methods of two different countries (UK and Germany) and apply several psychological constructs to explain differences in preference (formulation), this case study will contribute to final recommendations in several ways. This case study will help by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing evidence on the use of particular preference elicitation/exploration methods adopted in preventive RA therapy Providing insight regarding the similarity and applicability of DCE and PTT for decision making by all stakeholder groups along the MPLC regarding similar preventative/treatment situations as tested within this study Formulating recommendations on the utility of health literacy, numeracy, health locus of control and illness perception to explain preference heterogeneity across individuals within the same sample Providing insight regarding the extent to which attitude towards medication, perceived risk of developing RA, as well as attitudes towards and understanding of RA explain preference heterogeneity across individuals within the same sample Informing our understanding regarding cross-national (i.e., cultural and regional) variations in preferences within the same 'at risk' population Informing our understanding regarding the influence of disease experience, and level of information on preferences Providing insight regarding the influence of attribute framing on measured preferences.
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>Two recruitment strategies:</p> <p>In secondary care settings: Eligible participants will be ≥ 18 years old, without a diagnosis of RA, and first degree relatives of patients with RA. They will be identified and approached indirectly through patients with a confirmed diagnosis of RA in secondary care settings in Birmingham (UK) and Erlangen (Germany).</p> <p>Online Panel: Eligible participants will be ≥ 18 years old, without a diagnosis of RA.</p>
Setting	<p>Qualitative part: Focus groups with first degree relatives of patients with RA and members of the public without a diagnosis of RA will be conducted in the UK and Germany to inform attribute identification and attribute level selection of the quantitative preference study. NOTE: The qualitative part of this case study will not be considered as a separate preference study but is considered essential preparation for the quantitative part which is described next.</p>

	Quantitative part: Online survey of maximum 40 minutes. The questionnaire will consist of both the DCE and PTT (people are randomly assigned to start with either DCE or PTT). Two separate questionnaires will be developed in which all questions and choice tasks are equal, but in which the framing of one or more particular attributes differs (people are randomly assigned to either of the two surveys).
Key exclusion criteria	<p>Previous diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis</p> <p>Inability to complete a survey in English or German</p> <p>Under 18 years of age</p>
Sample Size requirement (total and by country)	<p>Qualitative part: Given the available literature related to the topic of this study, focus groups with approximately 40 respondents (10 first degree relatives and 10 members of the general public in both UK and Germany). Two focus groups with five participants will be held for both first degree relatives and members of the public in both countries. These numbers are expected to be sufficient to generate relevant attributes, rank order them and inform attribute level selection, since focus groups on a complete new topic generally already report data saturation after 3/4 group discussions (Krueger & Casey, 2014).</p> <p>Quantitative part: Total sample of maximum 400 is anticipated for first degree relatives in both UK and Germany. A total sample of 1000 respondents from the general public is anticipated to be recruited via e-panels in both Germany and UK. In order to test for the influence of attribute presentation on preferences, a split sample design is proposed. This entails that within both the FDR and the general population in both countries, half receives the survey framed in one way while the other half receives the exact same survey but attributes are framed in a different way.</p> <p>Sample-size calculations represent a challenge in DCE experiments. Most published choice experiments have a sample size of 100 to 300 respondents (Marshall et al., 2010). However, minimum sample size depends on several criteria, including the question format, the complexity of the choice task, the desired precision of the results, and the need to conduct subgroup analyses (Louviere et al., 2000; Johnson et al., 2013). A method for computing sample size was proposed by de Bekker-Grob (2015), however, as the article points out there is no analytic solution or power calculation that can be used to determine the appropriate sample size for a DCE unless the researcher has enough information to inform the selection of priors.</p> <p>There is no specific power calculation to determine sample size in PTT studies without knowing the expected threshold value a priori. Most PTT studies are conducted with 100 or fewer respondents, and substantially smaller samples (between 20 and 42 respondents) have been used successfully in previous studies (Gupta et al., 2016; Steures et al., 2005; Sung et al., 2004; Dales et al., 1999). Given the lack of clear guidance on sample size estimation for this type of study and the relatively small population of potential respondents, the Central Limit Theorem was used as a guide, assuming that a minimum sample size of 50 per PTT choice set would be needed to estimate a threshold value in each threshold exercise. This would be sufficient if all respondents answer all 3 sets of 3 threshold questions and the preferences demonstrate limited heterogeneity. To account for potential heterogeneity, a minimum total sample size of 100 will be considered sufficient to answer the primary objective. A target sample size of 200 is selected for the purposes of conducting subgroup analyses</p> <p>A sample size of 400 respondents 'at risk' of RA and 1000 from a panel in each country should be sufficient to answer the selected clinical and methodological</p>

	questions and provide enough information to identify preferences in these groups and comparisons across these groups. For the choice task, this assumes up to six attributes, with two to four levels each, with acceptable precision.
Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	A selection of class I constructs to explain preference heterogeneity and differences in preference formation will be selected for this study: Health literacy, Numeracy, Health Locus of Control, Attitudes towards medicine and illness perception.
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Clinical endpoints, description of how clinical research questions will be addressed.</p> <p>NOTE: Attributes need to be determined through the qualitative focus groups but potentially include risk of side effects, efficacy, duration, frequency of administration and mode of administration. A summary of insights from pre-testing/survey design qualitative focus groups will be provided to demonstrate the exact procedure used to select the final attributes and levels.</p> <p><u>Participant characteristics</u> that will be reported to describe the study samples include demographic characteristics, presence of family history of RA, current symptoms e.g. joint pain / fatigue, as well as perceived 5 year and lifetime risk of developing RA. A brief measure of attitudes towards and understanding of RA will be included as well as measures of the following psychological constructs: Attitudes towards medication in general, Health literacy, Numeracy, Health Locus of Control, and illness perception</p> <p><u>Answering clinical research questions</u></p> <p>To determine preferences of first degree relatives of patients with RA regarding preventive treatments for RA attribute (level) estimates and the relative importance of attributes will be reported. The Maximum acceptable risks/Minimum acceptable benefit will be determined thereafter to answer the second clinical research question. Heterogeneity of preferences will be investigated by applying appropriate statistical models thereby answering the third clinical research question. All results described above will be compared between the UK and German sample in order to answer the fourth clinical research question. Similarly those results will be compared between first degree relatives and the general population to answer the fifth clinical research question.</p> <p>Description of how methodological research questions will be addressed.</p> <p>The relative importance of attributes, the Maximum acceptable risks/Minimum acceptable benefit as well as heterogeneity of preferences will be compared between the DCE and PTT. The level of information gathered with both methods will be compared as well as the accuracy with which conclusions can be drawn from both method. Additionally comparisons will be made regarding logistics of both methods with respect to budget, time, perceived cognitive load etc. These comparisons will answer the first methodological research question of this case study.</p> <p>In order to answer the second methodological research question we will compare the relative importance of attributes, the Maximum acceptable risks/Minimum acceptable</p>

	<p>benefit as well as heterogeneity of preferences across the samples that have answered the survey that used different frames for attributes presentation (in other words: do outcomes change based on attribute presentation?). We will also address attribute interpretation, scale and reported complexity regarding the different frames for attribute presentation.</p> <p>Finally, the extent to which outcomes of the studies differ with respect to cognitive ability (in terms of health literacy, numeracy, health locus of control) of participants (third methodological research question) will be addressed by comparing attribute interpretation, choice consistency, response time, scale, reported complexity of the tasks across respondents with different levels of health literacy, numeracy, health locus of control and illness perception.</p>
Deliverable(s) related to this case study	<p>Templates to complete: Study protocol, Statistical Analysis Plan</p> <p>Deliverable: Study report</p>
Anticipated start of study	<p>Depending on IRB procedures, which takes at least 6 months in UK. Anticipation protocols to be ready for submission in October, IRB approval is expected in April 2019.</p> <p>In Germany IRB procedures will be faster. However, all materials for the case study need to be translated from English into German.</p> <p>Anticipated start of the focus groups phase of the case study in both countries is therefore estimated around Mid-April 2019.</p>
Estimated time to completion of the case study	18 months after start of the full study in both countries.
Key references	<p>APPIPRA: ISRCTN registry. <i>ISRCTN46017566 Arthritis prevention in the pre-clinical phase of rheumatoid arthritis with abatacept</i>. BioMed Central http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/ISRCTN46017566</p> <p>ARIAA: US National Library of Medicine. ClinicalTrials.gov http://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT02778906</p> <p>Arthritis-Checkup: Study of an early detection of the disease. 2017 http://www.arthritis-checkup.ch/index_gb.html.</p> <p>Bos WH, Dijkmans BAC, Boers M, <i>et al</i>. Effect of dexamethasone on autoantibody levels and arthritis development in patients with arthralgia: a randomised trial. <i>Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases</i> 2010;69:571-574.</p> <p>Dales RE, O'Connor A, Hebert P, Sullivan K, McKim D, Llewellyn-Thomas H. Intubation and mechanical ventilation for COPD: development of an instrument to elicit patient preferences. <i>Chest</i>. 1999 Sep;116(3):792-800.</p> <p>de Bekker-Grob EW, Donkers B, Jonker MF, Stolk EA. Sample size requirements for discrete-choice experiments in healthcare: a practical guide. <i>Patient</i>. 2015;8:373–84.</p> <p>Dougados, M. Comorbidities in rheumatoid arthritis. <i>Curr Opin Rheumatol</i> 2016, 28:282–288.</p> <p>Finckh A, Escher M, Liang MH, Bansback N. Preventative treatments for rheumatoid arthritis: Issues regarding patient preferences. <i>Curr Rheumatol Rep</i>. 2016;18:51.</p> <p>Gerlag DM, Raza K, van Baarsen LGM, <i>et al</i>. EULAR recommendations for terminology and research in individuals at risk of rheumatoid arthritis: report from the</p>

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NMD study

Disease / Clinical Context:

Neuromuscular disorders (NMD) represent uncommon (incidence 0.05 to 9 per 100,000 per year [1]), serious and debilitating (i.e. muscle weakness) conditions; all progressive with poor prognosis and with limited or no treatment options available. For the PREFER NMD case study, we have selected two neuromuscular diseases (i.e. myotonic dystrophy type 1 [DM1] and mitochondrial disorders [MD]) that despite having different physio-pathological pathways both manifest in a clinically similar manner. There is no specific cure for either disease but first in human trials for potential treatments to ameliorate these diseases are emerging. Both DM1 and MD present as multi-systemic and heterogeneous diseases, which can affect more than one family member or generation due to their pattern of inheritance and onset of symptoms can occur at different stages of life (i.e. from early childhood to late adulthood). In addition to muscle weakness, both DM1 and MD commonly affect the central nervous system (CNS), with symptoms such as: impaired or reduced cognitive function (i.e. attention, visual-spatial function, logical memory, processing speed) [2-5], learning difficulties, daytime sleepiness and fatigue, and mobility limitations. General cognitive deficits have been described in over 60 to 70% of patients and the prevalence and severity depends on the age at onset of the disease. With earlier onset of disease, the cognitive limitations are generally more severe than observed for adult phenotypes, which are classified as those with symptoms ≥ 20 years of age [5]. People affected by NMD diseases may have limited functional capacity to perform certain daily activities and often require caregiver assistance. This adds to the complexity of studying the NMD population given that patients may rely significantly on caregivers for relevant care-decisions. There are a number of challenges in delivering treatment in the context of rare diseases such as NMD and consequently there is a paucity of treatments available for this patient population. An important first step for the development and evaluation of new medical products is to understand the unmet healthcare need of patients and the reflection of patients on important benefits and risks associated with treatment. Patient preference information can better inform decision-makers (e.g. industry, regulators and HTA/payers) regarding the general unmet need of the patient population and potential value of new treatment developments, relevant clinical trial endpoints, and benefit-risk decision-making processes across the product development lifecycle. Patient preference information is also uniquely important for the development of new treatments for rare diseases such as NMD, as clinical trial evidence is often considerably uncertain or variable given the rare nature of the disease and challenges affecting trial enrolment [6-8]. Patient perspective can complement existing trial evidence used for decision-making processes. Although recent research has been conducted to better understand patient preferences for NMD treatments (pharmacological and non-pharmacological) [8-13], it has consisted mainly of qualitative research and little has been done to more fully characterize what is important to DM1 and MD patients (e.g. define attributes) and objectively quantify preferences for pharmacologic interventions. Identifying patient unmet health priorities and treatment preferences including benefit to risk trade-offs may inform decision-makers in the NMD drug development process. Additionally, for purposes of assessing these topics in this particular population, caregivers may be considered relevant sources of additional information and insights into what the patients believe, given they are sometimes incapable of recognizing certain benefits or risks depending on their cognitive abilities.

Methodological Context:

This preference study is designed to answer both clinical and methodological research questions. The clinical questions have been proposed by the NMD core team. The

methodological questions have been taken from the PREFER research questions that were generated within WP2 (Task 2.8) and prioritized as part of Task 3.2. This NMD study design has taken into consideration the rare nature of DM1 and MD and common CNS symptoms associated with this disease. Also, given the important role of caregivers in this disease area, they also play a central role in this study and allow us to capture important priorities and treatment attributes for patients, which may otherwise go unrecognized, and compare preferences obtained directly by patients and judgments of the relative importance of these attributes by caregivers.

Given this methodological and clinical context, the study design described herein focusses on eliciting preferences from DM1 and MD patients, combined, and the following three important patient and caregiver subgroups:

Subgroup 1: patients (DM1 and MD) with early onset of disease (established diagnosis or first reported symptoms before 20 years of age)

Subgroup 2: patients (DM1 and MD) with late onset (established diagnosis or first reported symptoms on or after 20 years of age).

Subgroup 3: caregivers of at least one DM1 or MD patient.

It is important to recognize that for Group 3, the intent is not to elicit preference for caregivers, but rather to elicit caregiver judgments for patients.

Research Question(s)

	Methodological Questions	Clinical Questions
Primary Objectives	For each subgroup of DM1 and MD patients (combined) and caregivers, we aim to describe and compare the results obtained using a relatively simpler versus more complex preference elicitation method. With complexity of the selected methods defined by the expertise necessary to develop the survey instrument and experiment, analyse the results, and the expected level of understanding from the respondents to assure a reliable response. (Q2d/2d1) Across patient subgroups (i.e. defined by age of disease onset as a surrogate marker of disease severity as defined in next section), we aim to describe and compare results obtained using the same preference elicitation method (Q9b) (Group 2 and 3 for Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) and Group 1, 2 and 3 for Best Worst Scaling Type 2 (BWS2)).	Identify and quantify patient unmet health priorities and preferences including benefit to risk trade-offs (e.g. minimum acceptable benefit (MAB), maximum acceptable risk (MAR)) for potential treatment options as provided by patients.
Secondary Objectives	To describe and compare responses from a preference	Assess how generalizable preferences are from one specific

	<p>elicitation method between two related diseases with similar clinical characteristics (i.e. DM1 and MD patients) (Q9b).</p> <p>To describe and compare responses from a preference elicitation method based on the respondent (i.e. comparing patient preferences with caregivers judgments regarding patient preferences) (Q11b).</p> <p>To describe heterogeneity of responses from a DCE, BWS2 or Q-methodology for patients and caregivers based on demographics and medical history (e.g., patients disease severity; prior treatment history; and, genetic status of caregivers) (Q11a, Q11b).</p> <p>To describe associations between responses from a DCE, BWS2 or Q-methodology and results obtained from psychosocial constructs assessments (health literacy, numeracy, and health locus of control) (Q10b1/Q10b2).</p>	<p>disease to a different disease but with similar characteristics (i.e. DM1 and MD)</p> <p>Understand the degree to which patient preferences and caregiver judgments for patients align with each other.</p> <p>Demonstrate the feasibility, strengths, and limitations of assessing preferences in a population that may present with cognitive limitations.</p>
Method/design		
Methods	<p>The study is designed to collect preferences from three subgroups: two patient groups defined by degree of cognitive limitation, and caregivers judging the relative importance of attributes for patients.</p> <p>This study will be conducted in two phases: [1st] qualitative study, including face to face interviews followed by focus-group based discussions and [2nd] quantitative study, including a DCE and/or BWS2 and/or Q-methodology (online surveys). The first phase of qualitative study will be used to determine and define the attributes and attribute levels to include in the DCE, BWS2 and Q-methodology of the second phase.</p> <p>The study will include both patients (DM1 and MD) and caregivers. As categorized below, patients will be allocated to a subgroup defined by age at disease onset which is considered a surrogate marker of disease severity and cognitive limitations:</p> <p><u>Group 1:</u> patients (DM1 and MD) with early onset of disease (established diagnosis or first reported symptoms before 20 years of age)</p> <p><u>Group 2:</u> patients (DM1 and MD) with late onset (established diagnosis or first reported symptoms on or after 20 years of age).</p>	

Additionally, the study will include a subgroup of caregivers (Group 3) of at least one DM1 or MD patient. All three groups will be represented in both phases of the study.

[Stage 1] Qualitative study:

The primary objective of this stage is to elicit input from patients and caregivers regarding current healthcare unmet needs, unmet health priorities and treatment attributes. This objective includes learning how to define or express these domains in a manner that is clear and consistently interpreted by subjects. An initial list of attributes selected from previous preference studies in similar populations [6-10] and currently emerging treatment trials of medications with Phase II clinical trial evidence (e.g., mexiletine, metformin, bezafibrate, modafinil and GSK3B inhibitors) can be considered as input for the development of interview guides for the qualitative study.

Face to face semi-structured interviews will first be conducted with a sample of patients with early disease onset phenotype (Group 1). Ten patients, both with DM1 and mitochondrial disease (i.e. five of each), will be interviewed, or more if data saturation is not achieved. In parallel, focus group discussions will be performed with patients with late onset phenotype (Group 2) and, separately, caregivers (Group 3). For the patient (Group 2) and caregiver (Group 3) focus groups, we will target up to 8 participants (including DM1 and mitochondrial disease participants) for each focus group and two to four focus groups in total are anticipated, depending of signs of data saturation [14].

Participants in the qualitative study will be approached as candidates for the quantitative study afterwards.

[Stage 2] Quantitative study:

Prior to the main survey, pilot testing will be performed to ensure comprehension and acceptability of the surveys and other study materials. Results of the pilot testing will be used to finalize the research materials for the main survey and to obtain preliminary preference data to further inform the experimental design and sample size calculation.

During the quantitative study, patients and caregivers will complete an online survey. The first online survey will include demographic and clinical history questions; and each online survey will include: psychosocial construct measures (health literacy and numeracy, and health locus of control), a cognition-task test, and one preference survey.

The quantitative study will include a cross-over design, with assessments (i.e. preference surveys) at two different time points (T1 and T2) two weeks (maximum of 4) apart. At each time point, 50% of the questionnaires delivered will include the method designated as being simpler (i.e. BWS2 or Q-methodology for group 1), while the other half of the patients will be given a questionnaire based on a more complex methodology (i.e. DCE or BWS2 for group 1*). A cross-over design will also allow patients and caregivers to act as their own control allowing comparison of results from one assessment time point (T1) to the other time point (T2), thereby reducing the cognitive burden

associated with testing the two methods of interest at the same time point. The washout period between T1 and T2 (i.e. two weeks) will reduce the potential bias of a learning effect and no major changes in disease status are expected in such a short period of time.

Data Collection Methods:

Qualitative study:

In-person semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions using an interview guide.

Quantitative study:

Online cross-over survey using two different preference elicitation methods:

Group 2 (Patients with late onset)

BWS2 and DCE

Group 3 (Caregivers)

BWS2 and DCE

Group 1 (Patients with early onset):

BWS2, and Q-methodology

*a higher prevalence of cognitive limitations is expected with Group 1 so a less cognitively complex tool than DCE will be explored as the complex preference elicitation method (i.e. BWS2).

Comparisons:

Within group and between group comparison of preferences obtained using different preference elicitation methods will be evaluated, as illustrated in Figure 1, below:

Figure 1: Illustration of different preference elicitation methods and planned within and between group comparisons

<p>PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>Based on the literature and interviews with stakeholders, an important but unanswered question regarding patient preference research is the level of confidence that stakeholders have in the results of different preference methods within the same population.</p> <p>Based on the research questions proposed in the PREFER task 2.8 report, this case study seeks to address a number of issues relevant to the implementation of preference studies, specifically:</p> <p><u>Question 2d:</u> How similar are the results from different preference elicitation methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?</p> <p><u>Question 2d1:</u> How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods</p> <p><u>Question 9b:</u> How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases?</p> <p><u>Question 10b1:</u> Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (e.g. health literacy and numeracy, health locus of control) provide insight regarding an individual's preferences (covariates); i.e., can certain constructs serve as covariates that are predictive of preference for particular diseases? Across different diseases and states of those diseases, is there consistent covariation of preference with certain psychological constructs?</p> <p><u>Question 10b2:</u> Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (e.g. health literacy and numeracy, health locus of control) provide insight regarding the patients' ability to form preferences?</p> <p><u>Question 11a:</u> To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with characteristics of patients?</p> <p><u>Question 11b:</u> To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with stakeholder: patient vs caregiver?</p>
<p>How the research questions support or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>Patient preference information can better inform decision-makers (e.g. industry, regulators) regarding the general unmet need of the patient population and potential value of new developments, relevant endpoints for future clinical trials, and benefit risk decision-making processes across the product development lifecycle. Patient preference information is also uniquely important for the development of new treatments for rare diseases such as neuromuscular disease (NMD), as clinical trial evidence is often considerably uncertain or variable given the rare nature of the disease and limitations with trial enrolment. Patient perspectives can complement existing trial evidence used for decision-making processes.</p>

<p>How the study might contribute to the final recommendations</p>	<p>This case study contributes to the Final PREFER Recommendations by providing evidence and experience related to pre-identified sections of the report:</p> <p><u>Rationale for performing a preference study:</u> Reasons behind this preference study will contribute to this section. This study in particular will highlight potential opportunities supporting performing preference studies in rare diseases with limited access to treatment options.</p> <p><u>Overview of methods suitable for particular contexts:</u> the methods in this case study (more simple and more complex methods) and its particular context (patients with DM1 and MD, rare diseases) will inform this section. Unique characteristics of this sample will allow the identification of suitable preference tools for populations that may present with cognitive limitations.</p> <p><u>Considerations for when and how to design patient preference studies:</u> This case study will build up experience on how to design and implement a preference study in this particular context, which will contribute to this section. More specifically, with plans to evaluate the case study results against specific criteria that are seen as important for earlier and latter stages of product development, this case study will further inform recommendations on elicitation of patient preferences via exploration (qualitative) and elicitation (quantitative) preference methods. This case study will provide a model to elicit preferences from patients/caregivers in the context of rare diseases and suitable for orphan designation, and will also provide a model to elicit preferences in diseases that may affect cognitive functioning of patients. Additionally, with the use of psychological instruments, the study results will also allow us to further explore why patient preferences may differ (preference heterogeneity), and differences in the patient's ability to form preferences.</p> <p><u>Presentation and communication of results of patient preference studies:</u> This case study will generate results that need to be tailored and presented to different stakeholders. In collaboration with the communication team of WP1, experience from these presentations will contribute to this section.</p> <p><u>Patient engagement in preference studies:</u> Experience from working together with DM1 and MD patients for the design of this case study will contribute to this section.</p> <p><u>Use of patient preference information in decision-making:</u> The case study will enable further consideration of how the results (patient preference information) will inform decision-making by industry and regulators and will also allow guidance for stakeholders interested in performing patient preference studies in populations where final care decisions do not rely on patients themselves. This study will also highlight unmet needs as reported by patients themselves that may defer from the current established priorities leading to new research investments.</p>
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	<p><u>Impact of patient preference studies:</u> This study will provide evidence of the impact of patient preference studies at early stages of the drug development cycle.</p>
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>Participants must be 18 years old or over</p> <p>Patient groups:</p> <p><u>Group 1:</u> diagnosed (genetic or biochemical) DM1 or MD patients with early onset of disease (established diagnosis or first reported symptoms before 20 years of age).</p> <p><u>Group 2:</u> diagnosed (genetic or biochemical) DM1 or MD patients with late onset (established diagnosis or first reported symptoms on or after 20 years of age)</p> <p>Caregivers group</p> <p><u>Group 3:</u> caregiver defined as a spouse, partner, parent(s), legal guardian or other adult family member living in the same house or in contact with a DM1 or MD patient in a caregiver relationship at least 4 times/week for at least one hour or more.</p> <p>Close relatives can be carriers of the genetic mutation or non-carriers, but are not considered as patients (i.e. disease not established at the time of interviewing).</p>
Key exclusion criteria	<p>Participants without capacity to provide informed consent</p> <p>Inability to verbally communicate by themselves</p> <p>In the investigators opinion, perceived lack of compliance to participate in the qualitative or quantitative study</p> <p>Participants with reported history of stroke like episodes, encephalopathy or dementia (as these may indiscriminately have a significant impact on cognitive skills and ability to complete the survey)</p> <p>For the quantitative study (phase 2), participants without access to a computer with internet connection to access and complete the survey.</p>
Sample Size requirement (total and by country)	<p>The main source for patient recruitment will be the UK Myotonic Dystrophy Patient Registry (>600 DM1 patients) and the MRC MitoCohort (>1500 mitochondrial disease patients) which are both established self-enrolling databases managed at Newcastle University. Both databases have a distribution of approximately 60% of patients with late onset (Group 2) disease and approximately 40% of patients with early onset disease (Group 1). Electronic and postal invitations for the study to all patients and caregivers registered in these databases will be issued. Additional caregivers will be recruited directly via the patients who consent to participate in the study and via NMD patient organisations working with Newcastle University. NMD patient organisations will support with study dissemination and promotion.</p> <p>The anticipated sample size for the qualitative study (stage 1) and quantitative study (stage 2) is summarized below:</p> <p>Qualitative study:</p> <p><u>Group 1:</u> 10 interviews, overall for DM1 and MD patients, or until data saturation</p>

	<p><u>Groups 2 and 3:</u> For each group, two to four focus groups or until data saturation; each focus group will include approximately 6 to 8 participants</p> <p>Quantitative study: Expected response rate is approximately 30% (i.e. allowing approximately 700 patients to be recruited (approximate 300 participants for Group 1 and 400 participants for Group 2) [11]. Caregivers will be recruited at a rate of 1 caregiver for each 2 patients (or approximately 350 participants).</p>
Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	Health literacy and numeracy, and health locus of control. No scenario-based interactive educational tools will be used in this case study.
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Expected results:</p> <p>A summary of insights obtained from the interviews and focus group discussions. This report will not only define the list of population-specific attributes to include in the second study stage but in itself is already an output to report considering the lack of previous studies in this disease area.</p> <p>A description of the extent to which a specific patient preference method can be utilized in different populations (related diseases) and the level of results comparability.</p> <p>A description of the comparison tests between responses from different stakeholders (patients and caregivers) when surveyed about the same attributes.</p> <p>A description of unmet priorities as established by patient caregivers in the DM1 and MD communities.</p> <p>A description of maximum acceptable risks (MARs); minimum acceptable benefits (MABs) for possible medical treatments.</p> <p>A quantification of the relative importance of the different attributes.</p> <p>An assessment of the heterogeneity in the preferences (based on respondents characteristics).</p>
Deliverable(s) related to this case study	Study protocol synopsis, full study protocols for qualitative and quantitative studies, statistical analysis plans, data management plans, and study reports. There are plans to present the study results at scientific conferences and in several scientific publications.
Estimated time to completion of the case study	18 months (+/- 2) from the point the time of IRB approval.

Relevant Literature	
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Lung cancer study

Disease / Clinical Context: Lung cancer is the most common malignancy in men and the third most common in women [1, 2]. The most frequent symptoms that patients report upon disease presentation are cough, dyspnea, chest pain, fatigue, chest infection, hemoptysis and weight loss, all of which greatly overlap with symptoms of other common chronic respiratory conditions and often only present at later stages of the disease [3]. This overlap is one cause of the delay between presentation and diagnosis, which means that lung cancer is diagnosed in late stages in half of all cases [4, 5]. The prevalence of late stage diagnosis is one of the reasons why lung cancer has such a low survival rate, with a 5-year overall survival rate of 18.1% in all lung cancer stages and 4.5% in metastatic stage [6]. Such survival rates, even though are still low, actually represent a 58% improvement over historical data. This improvement has resulted from advancements in technologies and treatment techniques for lung cancer. Among these recent novelties is the introduction of Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors (ICIs) as treatment options for advanced stage lung cancer [7, 8].

In recent years, we have witnessed a shift in the treatment paradigm of Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC). Specifically, the inclusion of ICIs in different lines of treatment for advanced NSCLC has been explored in several international clinical trials with promising results and has led to accelerated approval of these therapies by regulatory agencies. Different compounds targeting the receptors Programmed Death 1 (PD-1) and PD-Ligand 1 (PD-L1), involved in the regulation of anti-tumor immune response, have showed superior efficacy over previous standard treatment in different settings. These drugs include pembrolizumab (Keytruda), nivolumab (Opdivo) and atezolizumab (Tecentriq), which are now reimbursed with different indications in USA and in many European countries [9-13].

Focusing on the anti-PD1 drug pembrolizumab, it has been approved by both Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European Medicine Agency (EMA) in first line treatment of advanced unresectable or metastatic NSCLC with high ($\geq 50\%$) expression of PD-L1 [14]. This approval followed the positive results of the trial MK3475-024, which randomized patients to standard chemotherapy (CT) according to investigators' choice or pembrolizumab in first line. As compared to CT, pembrolizumab showed superior Progression Free Survival (PFS), with a median value of 10.3 vs 6.0 months ($p < 0.001$), and also superior Overall Survival (OS), with a median value of 30.0 vs 14.2 months ($p < 0.002$). Objective Response Rate (ORR) was higher in Immunotherapy (IO) arm (45% vs 28%), which also obtained a longer duration of response (median value not reached vs 6.3 months). Notably, the toxicity profile of Immuno-Oncology therapy (IO) was manageable and the incidence of moderate/serious adverse events was lower as compared to CT (26.6% vs 53.3%).

Following the approval of pembrolizumab single agent for use in clinical practice for advanced NSCLC, the combination of pembrolizumab and CT was granted approval by FDA and EMA according to the results of the trial MK3475-189 [15]. This study randomized patients to a combination of pembrolizumab and CT based on platinum salt and pemetrexed, or CT alone. Study population included patients with advanced unresectable or metastatic lung adenocarcinoma in first line setting, irrespective of PD-L1 expression. The combination of chemo-immunotherapy was superior to CT alone in terms of both PFS (8.8 vs 4.9 months, $p < 0.00001$) and OS (median not reached vs 11.3 months, $p < 0.00001$). Chemo-immunotherapy obtained higher ORR (48% vs 19%) and longer duration of response (11.2 vs 7.8 months) than CT. The addition of pembrolizumab to CT did not increase the incidence of moderate/serious adverse events as compared to standard treatment (67.2% vs 65.8%). The benefit of pembrolizumab was confirmed across all the classes of PD-L1 expression, including those with Tumor Proportion Score (TPS) $< 1\%$, although the best absolute results in terms of survival were obtained in cases with PD-L1 $\geq 50\%$.

While the benefit of combined chemo-immunotherapy is clear for patients with PD-L1 low/negative NSCLC, data are less clear for those with PD-L1 positive NSCLC. Indeed, no direct comparison exists between chemo-immunotherapy and IO alone in this subgroup. Both trials assessing pembrolizumab

have found better outcomes for the experimental arm containing IO over previous standard of care. This has led to the rise of two new alternative potential treatment algorithms for NSCLC, with no data to guide clinicians and patients' decisions between them. Indirect comparison of survival curves from the two different studies showed, with the methodological limitations of such an approach, quite overlapping results (patients alive and free from progression at 12 months: 40-50%; patients alive at 12 months: 70-80%). Toxicity was higher for chemo-immunotherapy than for IO alone (severe adverse events: 67.2% vs 26.6%; adverse events leading to treatment discontinuation: 13.8% vs 7.1%; adverse events leading to death: 6.7% vs 0.6%). Nonetheless, this observation has to be weighted in relation to the fact that most of the patients treated with first line IO will receive a platinum-based CT as second line, experiencing CT toxicity anyway. Moreover, even though survival outcome seems similar, the two treatment options difference in terms of ORR, which is superior for combination (61.4% vs 44.8%). This could be relevant in case of significant burden of disease, or symptomatic lesions, or rapid progression, where not only the length of response but also its extent becomes crucial.

Based on the results of the aforementioned studies with pembrolizumab, the first line treatment paradigm for PD-L1 positive lung adenocarcinoma can be summarized as in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hypothetical first line treatment algorithm after the results of trials MK3475-024 and MK3475-189.

Due to the lack of clear best choice between the two alternative standards of care, experts recommends to discuss treatment options with patients and individualize decisions. From the physician's point of view, the option of concomitant chemo-immunotherapy could be preferred for patients with good performance status (e.g. absence of symptoms due to disease or mild symptoms),

no serious comorbidities, adequate compliance to prescriptions and evidence of rapidly progressing disease. On the contrary, IO alone could be the best option in presence of elderly patients, poor clinical conditions, systemic comorbidities contraindicating CT, evidence of low burden or slow progression of disease.

In such a context of uncertainty, patients’ preferences terms allow us to quantify acceptance of risks to obtain an uncertain benefit.

Knowing patient preferences for different treatment options’ attributes would be valuable not only for clinicians, when determining the therapeutic plan, but also for regulators and Health Technology Assessment (HTA). For marketing authorization and for reimbursement decisions, regulators and HTA or payer stakeholders need to assess, among other decisions criteria, the expected benefits and risks of the medical product under review. Since the comparison between benefits and risks of alternative treatment strategies in first line setting is only indirect, an assessment regarding the best treatment choice is difficult to perform both from a regulatory and from an HTA/payer perspective. This situation or decision could therefore be labeled as a “preference sensitive decision”, where knowledge about patient preferences on benefits, risks and other outcomes of treatment is particularly valuable. The importance of considering patients’ preferences for the treatment of metastatic NSCLC has been highlighted in the recent European Society of Medical Oncology (ESMO) Clinical Practice Guidelines, in which an individual’s preference for treatment is a relevant factor to be taken into account alongside age, performance status, comorbidities, histology and molecular pathology when deciding among different therapeutic options for treatment of NSCLC [7].

Since the reimbursement/approval of this new treatment options is not uniformly regulated across Europe, a deeper understanding of the patients’ preferences for their different aspects (e.g. PFS, OS and adverse events impacting quality of life) will be pivotal to inform stakeholders during the decision-making process leading to their implementation.

Methodological Context: This preference study is designed to answer both clinical and methodological research questions at the same time. The clinical questions have been put forward by the lung cancer core team as being very relevant to the clinical community. The methods questions have been taken from the prioritized PREFER research questions that were generated within WP2 and prioritized as part of Task 3.2.

Research Question(s)		
Objectives	<p>Clinical:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To identify and quantify patient-relevant benefit-risk attributes of LC treatments 2) To quantify the risk tolerance for experiencing adverse events (Maximum Acceptable Risk) that patients are willing to accept for an increased probability of prolonged survival 	<p>Methodological:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) How similar are results from two different preference elicitation methods? 2) Can the following factors be used to explain preference heterogeneity and differences in preference formation? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Psychosocial constructs (currently being considered with final decision depending on total length of survey): health literacy and numeracy, health locus of

		<p>control, risk propensity and illness perception (10b3)</p> <p>b) General patient characteristics and demographics such as age, sex, education, clinical characteristics (disease and treatment experience), medical history, etc. (11a)</p>
<p>Method/design</p>		
<p>Methods</p>	<p>The study will comprise of two phases (detailed below): a qualitative phase and a quantitative phase.</p> <p>1) Qualitative phase: Since there is a limited amount of published research done regarding patient preferences for immunotherapy in lung cancer treatment, an exploratory qualitative phase involving patients will be conducted to ensure that attributes for them are considered for use in the quantitative phase. In addition to patients' contribution, a panel of clinicians and experts will be involved to define levels to be included in the quantitative phase for each attribute selected by patients as relevant for them. A literature research on patient preferences in lung cancer treatment will investigate the presence of already known patient-relevant attributes to evaluate in the choice of treatment options. Informal interviews with clinicians, regulators HTA/reimbursement agency representatives will ensure an in-depth understanding of emerged attributes.</p> <p>Focus Group Discussion with patients (estimated 4, 2 in Italy and 2 in Belgium) will prompt patients to provide an extensive list of relevant attributes when evaluating treatment options. The focus group discussion guides will be developed upon the recommendations by Kruger (https://www.eiu.edu/ihec/Krueger-FocusGroupInterviews.pdf). A second set of Focus Group Discussions (estimated 2, 1 in Italy and 1 in Belgium) will adopt the Nominal Group Technique to shorten the list of attributes and rank them by their importance from the patients' perspective.</p> <p>After the ranked list of attributes is defined, the contribution of clinicians will be required to define levels for each of the selected attributes.</p> <p>The primary aim of the qualitative phase is to inform the quantitative phase by identifying lung cancer treatment attributes and attribute levels which are most relevant to patients. The focus-group guide will be developed based upon the stated research aims, a comprehensive literature review that is currently performed within the lung cancer team, and informal interviews with clinicians regulators HTA/reimbursement agency representatives. This literature review will build further on the results from two other systematic reviews that report on patient preferences for lung cancer treatments: Blinman <i>et al.</i>, 2010 and Schmidt <i>et al.</i>, 2016. Once the pool of different treatment outcomes/attributes has been generated through systematic review and informal interviews, four focus groups will</p>	

	<p>be conducted with six patients each in Belgium and in Italy. Then, two focus groups with nominal group techniques will be conducted in both countries. The aim of these focus groups is to refine and rank the list of attributes and attribute levels to those viewed as most important to patients in order to inform the development of choice instruments for use in the quantitative phase. Finally, after the definition of the ranked list of attributes, clinicians will be asked to define levels for each of attributes.</p> <p>2) Quantitative phase: The information gathered in the qualitative stage along with the results from the literature review will be used to establish the final list of attributes and levels for the preference elicitation methods used in the Quantitative phase. As one of the research goals of this study is to compare the outcomes of patient preference instruments with different instruments, two preference elicitation instruments will be completed by the participant and the differences in outcomes compared. An additional Likert scale evaluation will prompt patients to express their opinion on general themes emerged in the focus group discussion. Instruments were chosen among those selected in the PREFER consortium. The first of these tasks will be a discrete choice experiment (DCE), the second will be a Swing Weighting (SW) task, and finally, a small group (<5) of Likert scale questions will be used to assess patients' attitude towards larger themes of survival and adverse events identified in the qualitative stage (e.g. how important is survival, short-term side effects, long term side-effects, functionally limiting side effects, etc.); the final amount of Likert questions will be determined based on the number of themes identified in the thematic analysis resulting from the qualitative stage and in view of the total length of the survey.</p> <p>The two preference elicitation instruments will be used in a cross-sectional design, where patients meeting the predefined inclusion criteria (see below) will be selected to participate in the study. Using an AB/BA crossover design, half of the participants will be randomly assigned to receive either the DCE or the SW task first, followed by the other one. Both groups will then complete the Likert scale task. Patients will receive information before completing the tasks by using a newly developed educational component (containing explanations of the meaning of attributes and levels). These patients will then complete the survey on a digital platform (i.e. tablet) containing both preference elicitation methods.. Finally, participants will also complete psychological tools to assess a profile based on the selected psychological constructs (health literacy and numeracy, health locus of control, illness perception, risk propensity). The total amount of psychological tools will be determined based on the length of the survey, the patients' possible cognitive load and burden in filling in the set of psychological instruments, the time needed to complete them, and the way of administration (self vs. interviewer based).</p>
Background and Rationale	
<p>PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from</p>	<p>The chosen methodological research questions were selected from the 2.8 PREFER deliverable and feedback received from the steering committee, industry partners, methodological experts, scientific advisory</p>

<p>prioritized list)</p>	<p>board members and clinical partners. These questions were identified as being relevant for industry, HTA and regulatory decision-making and suitable for the patient population of lung cancer patients. The resulting questions can be divided into two different categories: 1) “optimization of preference studies” (related to the categories “reliability” in the PREFER strategy document) and 2) “understanding the preference outcomes and their implications” (related to the categories “reliability” and “generalizability” in the PREFER strategy document).</p> <p>The first, optimization of preference studies, relates to understanding the “best” or most efficient way to conduct a preference study. These questions involve the comparison of preference elicitation methods. The first of these questions relates to method choice. There exists a large variety of different methods which can be used to measure patient preferences (see PREFER deliverables 2.4, 2.6, 2.7). Associated with these different types of methods are varying costs for the researcher (for development and implementation), the patient (burden of completing task and risk that some patients may not understand the task) and analytical effort or burden associated with the method. The choice of whether to use: 1) one elicitation method over the other and 2) a more expensive or cheap method is of primary concern for parties interested in measuring patient preferences. This choice directly influences how complicated and costly a study needs to be in order to produce results sufficient to answer the research question. Therefore, the primary methodological objective of the lung cancer case study is to compare two methods to assess the most effective. We will also assess whether the increased cognitive burden and analytical effort of the more complex method justifies its usage (Questions: 1.3/2d1, 1.2/2d).</p> <p>The second category of methodological questions relates to understanding the preference outcomes and their implications. This category mainly focuses on which factors can best explain variation in the preferences; whether these factors result in inter-subject differences on health literacy and numeracy, health locus of control, illness perception and risk propensity (Questions: 1.19/10b1, 1.21/10b3) or other patient characteristics (Question 1.25/11a). By asking these questions we aim to understand both how patient preference studies can be generalized to the larger patient population, as well as to understand which factors influence preferences to better assess the validity of preference outcomes. To answer these questions, we will implement the study in multiple countries and multiple treatment centers with patients and assess the relevant psychosocial constructs and patient demographics that are expected to be of importance.</p>
<p>How the research questions support or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>Answering the clinical questions contributes to medical product decision making as follows:</p> <p>Patient preference information can better inform decision-makers (e.g. industry, regulators) regarding the potential value of new developments, relevant endpoints for future clinical trials, and benefit risk decision-making processes</p>

	<p>across the product development lifecycle. Patient preferences can complement existing clinical trial evidence used for decision-making processes that build upon the results from clinical trials, such as regulatory benefit-risk assessments and health technology assessment. On the individual treatment decision-making level, considering patient-relevant outcomes could lead to a more personalized indication, which could increase patient compliance with the prescribed treatment and hence, a better efficacy. On the macro-level, results from this study could support the development of clinical practice guidelines by indicating which outcomes of the treatments available in lung cancer are important and which are less important. Knowing about patient preferences (patients' risk tolerance) towards these uncertain but impactful benefits and risks would also give clinicians insights into how patients view this tradeoff and stimulate the quality of shared decision-making.</p> <p>Answering the methodological questions contributes to medical product decision making as follows:</p> <p>Research question (2d1): Several patient preference exploration and elicitation methods are available, complex and simple methods (see PREFER deliverables 2.4, 2.6, 2.7). Decision-making stakeholders (regulators, industry, HTA bodies/payers) are in need of guidance about where to direct investments for studies involving measuring preferences. Is a larger investment in complex or expensive methods justified by a more accurate evaluation of patient preferences?</p> <p>Research question (7d): Several psychological measures are available (see Task 2.5 report). Decision-making stakeholders want preferences to be elicited from well-informed patients (see 2.1/2.2 deliverable) and to have highest grade of evidence on the validity of outcomes. For this reason several psychological measures will aim to obtain information about those constructs that may help explain the preference heterogeneity and the preference development process.</p> <p>Research question (10b3) and (11a): If decision-makers have a better view on the psychological, clinical and other patient characteristics that define preference heterogeneity, then they are better able to interpret the results and assess the validity of preferences. Patients' differences in health locus of control, health literacy and numeracy, illness perception and risk propensity will be assessed to better comprehend whether these psychological aspects could influence preference heterogeneity and the formation process of patient preferences. Specifically, the influence of illness perception, health literacy and numeracy will be evaluated to assess differences in patients' preferences, expectations and evaluation of outcomes, attribute or characteristics of immunotherapy. On the other hand, the evaluation of health locus of control and risk propensity will permit to study associations of patients' perception of control in health-related outcomes and their willingness to take risk with the benefit-risk trade-off that patients would consider when treated with immunotherapy. This is specifically of relevance in the lung cancer patient population, which is known to be large and heterogeneous (psychological characteristics, demographics, clinical characteristics).</p>
How the study might contribute to the final	<p>In the Final Recommendations, the following topics will be addressed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Rationale for performing a preference study. The lung cancer preference study experience will contribute to this part of the

recommendations	<p>recommendations.</p> <p>2) Overview of methods suitable for particular contexts: the methods in this case study and its particular context (lung cancer, large heterogeneous sample) will inform this section. These methods and their context were already defined in the PREFER deliverables 2.4, 2.6, 2.7, and this case study will inform regarding the practical feasibility of these methods. This section will relate to methods for eliciting or exploring preferences.</p> <p>3) Considerations for when and how to design patient preference studies: This case study will build up experience on how to design and implement a preference study in the context of diseases in which survival is a primary consideration and in new treatments for which long-term effects may still be unknown. Additionally, this case study will help to formulate recommendations on the utility of psychological measures to explain preference heterogeneity.</p> <p>4) Supporting evidence for EMA Methods Qualification: The use of DCEs in this case study and their comparison to other methods will add evidence which can be used during the EMA Methods Qualification assessment as declared in the PREFER strategy document.</p> <p>5) Presentation and communication of results of patient preference studies. This case study will generate results that need to be tailored and presented to different stakeholders. In collaboration with the communication team of WP1, experience from these presentations will contribute to this section.</p> <p>6) Patient engagement in preference studies. Experience from working together with lung cancer patients for the design of this case study will contribute to this section.</p>
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>For the qualitative phase, we will recruit Lung cancer patients:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age ≥18 years - Stage III and stage IV, NSCLC <p>In this phase, informal interviews with lung cancer oncologists, regulators and HTA/reimbursement representatives will be performed in order to receive insight on relevant attributes and to define different levels for each attribute.</p> <p>For the quantitative phase, the following inclusion criteria will be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age ≥18 years - Histological or cytological diagnosis of NSCLC - No previous experience of immunotherapy
Setting	<p>For the qualitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patients will be recruited via their oncologist in 2 different countries: Italy and Belgium - Focus groups will be conducted in person at a location most convenient to the participants and will take approximately one hour. <p>For the quantitative phase:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patients will be recruited via their oncologists in 2 different countries: Italy, Belgium. - Quantitative part: Digital survey (of approximately 40 minutes)
Key exclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cognitive impairment or inadequate verbal skills that may render them incapable of informed consent (as evaluated by the clinician) - Inability to understand study materials (as evaluated by the clinician) - Physical or psychological impairment that prohibits their participation in an interview or focus group (as evaluated by the clinician) - In the investigators opinion, perceived lack of compliance to participate in the qualitative method appropriate for their respective group
Sample size requirement (total and by country)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qualitative part: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Informal interviews with lung cancer oncologist, regulators, and HTA/reimbursement representatives. o o Focus groups: N=4 (6 participants each, to be conducted both in Italy and in Belgium) o Focus groups with nominal group techniques: N= 2 (to be done in Italy and Belgium) - Quantitative part: Minimum N = 250, the feasibility of recruitment of patients per country is currently assessed and will be elaborated on in the quantitative protocol.
Accompanying psychological instruments and educational tools (where applicable)	<p>1) Psychological instruments: A selection of different psychological constructs to explain preference heterogeneity and differences in preference formation will be assessed; including Health Literacy and Numeracy, Health Locus of Control, Risk propensity and Illness Perception. Questionnaires used to assess these constructs will be chosen from the 2.5 deliverable/presentation on psychological constructs and methods and selected based on the time needed to complete it, the cognitive load, route of administration (self vs. interviewer based) and the languages in which they are validated. Instruments that are currently considered for inclusion are the Multidimensional Health Locus of Control Scale (Health Locus of Control), Chew's Set of Brief Screening Questions and the Newest Vital Sign (Health literacy and numeracy), the Risk propensity scale or the Balloon Analogue Risk task (risk propensity) and the Illness Perception Questionnaire-Brief (Illness Perception). The suitability of these instruments and final selection of instruments will be based on pilot testing conducted prior to the quantitative phase.</p> <p>2) Educational component: For the quantitative phase, a visual educational component to help patients to better understand the attributes discussed in the survey will be developed. This educational component will be based on the outcomes of the qualitative phase in order to ensure that all relevant outcomes and attributes are addressed. PREFER partner MindBytes will be involved in the development of this educational component.</p>

Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>1) Qualitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What treatment attributes patients find important ○ Which treatment attributes and attribute levels need to be included in the quantitative phase <p>2) Quantitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Preference study clinical “endpoints” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Attribute (level) estimates ▪ Relative importance of attributes ▪ Maximum acceptable risks / Minimum acceptable benefit (e.g., how much effectiveness (OS, PFS) is necessary for combination therapy to be acceptable and how much effectiveness would be traded for a reduction in risks of serious side effect) ○ Psychological “endpoints”: Health Literacy and Numeracy, Health Locus of Control, Risk Propensity and Illness Perception ○ Preference study methodological “endpoints”: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Heterogeneity of preferences based on patient characteristics: clinical characteristics (e.g. severity of LC, treatment experience), demographic data (e.g. age, sex), psychological characteristics (e.g. patient expectations, risk attitude), psychological characteristics of participants (e.g. health locus of control) ▪ Comparison of preference elicitation when measured by different methods ▪ Comparison of logistics of the two preference methods such as costs ▪ Evaluation of the perceived effectiveness of the educational component as a mean to convey information
Deliverable(s) related to this case study	Study synopsis; Study protocol; Interview guide; Survey; Analysis Plan; Data Management Plan; Study report
Anticipated start of study	June 1 st , 2019
Estimated time to completion of the case study	June, 2020

Appendix 5: Synopsis of additional academic-led case studies

Diabetes study

Disease / Clinical Context:

Diabetes is a chronic disease characterized by the body's inability to maintain healthy levels of blood glucose (glycemic control) which is associated with long-term health problems such as retinopathy, nephropathy, peripheral and autonomic neuropathy, cardiovascular symptoms, and sexual dysfunction (American Diabetes Association, 2012). Diabetes was found to be directly responsible for 1.5 million deaths in 2012 with an estimated global prevalence of 9% in 2014 (World Health Organization, 2014). A majority of diabetes cases fall under two categories, type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), with T1DM accounting for approximately 5-10% of cases worldwide and T2DM accounting for approximately 90-95% of cases worldwide (American Diabetes Association, 2012). Diabetes care is centered around the cornerstone of metabolic control; specifically keeping glucose levels as close to normal as possible through the self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG), medication, a careful diet, and physical activity (Evert, A.B., et al. 2014; Rubin and Peyrot, 2001). Traditionally, SMBG has been done by pricking the finger with a lancet to draw a drop of blood and directly testing the levels of glucose in the blood, sometimes multiples times per day. While highly accurate and proven to help in controlling average blood glucose levels (Benjamin, 2002), this technique represents a large burden to the patient which often results in non-compliance to medical treatment advice (Ahoa and Groop, 2013; Dalewitz, Khan, and Hershey, 2000; Peyrot, 2005). Recent technological developments related to medical devices which can (semi-)continuously monitor blood glucose levels (or proxies thereof) have resulted in a positive outlook for patients who need to monitor their glucose levels (Garg and Akturk, 2017). Many of these devices are an improvement over the finger prick method of SMBG in that they are less invasive, can give a fuller picture of daily blood glucose levels such as by showing trends, and are easier and quicker to use. However, there is large variety within this class of medical devices in regards to function, features, and price meaning that the choice of which device should be used is a matter of personal preference.

In the EU, this device is reimbursed by health insurance companies in some countries, often for particular medical circumstances such as when a patient has recurrent severe hypoglycaemia, and in other countries it is not reimbursed. The case study will focus on two countries, the Netherlands and Poland, which are examples of 'Western' and 'Eastern' European countries with partial and no reimbursement, respectively. Currently, reimbursement for continuous glucose monitors in the Netherlands is limited to adults with consistent unregulated glucose levels (HbA1c >64 mmol/mol, >8%) despite intensive efforts to lower HbA1c, pregnant women with diabetes (type 1 and type 2), and children (Heinemann et al, 2012). Continuous glucose monitors are not reimbursed in Poland (Glowinska-Olszewska et al, 2013), although in 2018, a recommendation was made by the Agency for the Assessment of Medical Technology and Tariffs to extend reimbursement for type 1 diabetes children and adolescents from 4-17 years old, and in type 1 adults up to 26 years old who have difficulty controlling their blood glucose levels (Agencja Oceny Technologii Medycznych i Taryfikacji, 2018). In 2016, 2,950 deaths in the Netherlands were attributable to high blood glucose and 12,930 in Poland (WHO, 2016)

Methodological Context:

This case study fills in important gaps in knowledge that the three core case studies (RA, NMD and LC) do not cover within the PREFER project, and increases the knowledge surrounding the prioritized questions coming from stakeholders. The research questions proposed in the PREFER Work Package 2 led to the identification of relevant concerns to be addressed within this case study. The foremost of these questions was the comparison of different methods with a focus on different levels of instrument complexity. This case study addresses that question by comparing the outcomes of Discrete Choice Experiments and — Swing Weighting tasks. Both of these were chosen based on recommendations from the PREFER scientific advisory board, EMA members and T2.7 and with this being the only case study using Swing Weighting. But the importance of this case study lies in the gaps in knowledges that it fills in order to write recommendations (WP4) with a broader impact. Specifically, this case study fills in the gaps of knowledge regarding:

1. generalizability of findings to eastern European countries,
2. whether recruitment methods result in different preferences (panel participants vs patients recruited via clinician), and
3. whether educational materials are important in the chronic disease context.

Further, this is the only case study in PREFER which is assessing preferences about **medical devices**, which was stated as a primary aim of PREFER, in a patient population highlighted as being most relevant to PREFER stakeholders in the Task 2.8 report. By answering these questions, this case study will strengthen the final recommendations coming from the PREFER project while also addressing a general need to understand device preferences in a growing population, a need which has not been properly addressed.

Research Question(s) To assess the preferences of diabetes patients for blood glucose monitoring devices

	Clinical	Methodological
Primary Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To assess which attributes of blood glucose monitoring devices patients consider when deciding on their preferred device, and ● What relative importance do these different attributes have in choosing which devices to use? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Are the preferences for devices different (overall preference and variability of preferences) when patients are educated regarding blood glucose monitoring using an interactive educational tool vs traditional textual information? ● Is the recruitment method of the patient sample related to differences in preference outcomes? (i.e. panel participants vs patients recruited via clinician (GP) and/or patient organisations (PO)) ● Do preference values vary between two different methods with varying complexity when applied to the same population sample?

Secondary Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the minimum acceptable benefits needed to justify increased costs? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can preference heterogeneity be explained based on type of diabetes, geographic, or socioeconomic factors (e.g. country of origin, age, sex)? • Can preference heterogeneity be explained based on disease experience (e.g. years with disease, current treatment regimen, experience with hypoglycemic events)? • Do preference values differ between patients presented with a different sequence of elicitation methods?
Background and Rationale		
Describe the preference sensitive situation	Recent technological developments in glucose monitoring devices have resulted in less invasive, more accurate, easier, and quicker ways for patients to monitor and gain control of their daily blood glucose levels. However, there is large variety within this class of medical devices in regards to benefit-risk tradeoffs between function, features, and price meaning that the choice of which device should be used is a matter of personal preference.	
How the case study supports or informs medical product decision making	Patient preference information can better inform decision-makers (i.e. industry, regulators and HTA) regarding the general unmet need of the patient population and potential value of new developments, reimbursement policies, and benefit risk decision-making processes across the product development lifecycle. Industry leaders can use this preference information to guide research and development of new glucose monitoring devices in order to reduce potential losses resulting from the development of unwanted technologies. This is especially important as consumer acceptance or tolerance is often not known until post-marketing. By integrating this information earlier, industry members can develop vital technologies that patients will actually use, because they are based on patient preferences. HTA agencies can also use this information to help guide reimbursement plans to ensure that only those devices that match patient preferences will be reimbursed.	
Describe which PREFER research question(s) will be addressed (from prioritized list)	In order to address the PREFER-prioritized Research Question 2d concerning the reliability of results obtained from different methods using the same attributes on the same population, a discrete choice-based technique (DCE) and a ranking related technique (swing weighting) will be examined in this study. DCE and swing weighting were selected as elicitation methods because they are fundamentally “trade-off” methods, asking participants to choose between increasing some attribute levels at the expense of decreasing other attribute levels. Both can estimate marginal rates of substitution (such as willingness-to-pay, and MAB) values for benefits. Swing weighting was identified in PREFER task 2.7 as a “highly promising method” likely to meet most decision-makers needs at many stages of the MPLC, and it was recommended by scientific advisory board members as a method to be examined for this research question. In swing weighting, respondents get a description of a glucose monitoring device	

that has the worst possible level of performance on all outcome criteria. They are asked which criterion they would select first to improve (i.e., to swing) from the worst to the best level. After the chosen criterion is removed from the entire set of criteria, they are asked which criterion they would select second. This is continued on until all criteria are ranked. The resulting rank order is then turned into weights, for example, by using the rank ordered centroid method (Byeong, 2011). In a **DCE**, participants are presented with a series of alternative scenarios containing a number of attributes and attribute levels, with each scenario consisting of a different combination of these attribute levels. Participants pick the scenario they prefer the most, and at the end of several choice tasks, weights for each attributes/levels can be statistically derived on the basis that one scenario with specific attribute levels is preferred over another. These two methods will be employed, using the same attributes on the same population, in order to examine the reliability of preference results using different methods. Additionally, conducting a DCE would align with the IMI PREFER strategy to submit for an EMA method qualification.

These two methods will also address **Research Question 2d1** concerning the differing level of evidence provided by simple versus complex methods. An instrument is considered complex for the researcher if it is difficult to develop and the results are (more) difficult to analyze. An instrument is considered complex for the participant if the choice task is cognitively or emotionally difficult to reflect on (i.e. they involve understanding complex and abstract concepts, include probabilities, require the comparing of multiple points of information concurrently, or discuss emotionally difficult topics). In this instance, a DCE is considered the more complex method for the participant due to the cognitive complexity related to concurrently assessing multiple attributes and weighing their collective utility. The analysis of DCEs is more complex for the researcher as well due to the less exact measurement of preference data, meaning that additional analyses are necessary to verify internal validity (Tervonen et al. 2017). These instruments will be compared based on feasibility, operational requirements, analysis speed, robustness (as measured in standard errors), and cost of these two methods based on the investment in development and sample sizes required to reach and acceptable power. We will also examine the acceptability of these two methods among the targeted patient population by following up with participants to see which method they thought was easiest to complete and best reflected their true preference.

In order to address **Research Question 7d** concerning different preferences and accuracy of results obtained through a survey with an educational component containing interactive, scenario-based features compared to the traditional educational approach, these two aspects will be included in the design of the study, with half of the participants receiving information about blood glucose monitor devices through each format.

In order to address **Research Question 11k** concerning how the preferences of patients in the same disease vary between patients recruited through different channels, we will be recruiting patients through panels and also GPs/patient

	<p>organizations in one country, the Netherlands, in order to make a comparison of preferences.</p> <p>Research Question 11a concerning the relationship between patient characteristics and patient preferences, subgroup analyses will be performed in order to identify any correlations of preferences with patient characteristics, including country of residence, disease type (type 1 or type 2), age, sex, recruitment technique, and other characteristics. Heterogeneity of preferences will be examined through subgroup analysis. Research Question 11d concerning the relationship between disease experience and patient preferences will also be examined in a similar way. A sub-group analysis will be performed in order to identify any correlations between preferences and the number of years the patient has had diabetes, their current method for measuring or recording their glucose levels, and diabetes self-care regimen as identified through the Diabetes Self-Management Questionnaire (DSMQ) (Schmitt et al, 2016) administered at the end of the survey.</p>																				
<p>How the study contributes to the final PREFER recommendations</p>	<p>This study will demonstrate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and when to conduct a patient preference study, building upon the results that have come out of WP2 - Examining and comparing the performance of two elicitation methods, demonstrating in practice the results of WP2, specifically tasks 2.4, 2.6, and 2.7. - Provide a specific case study examining medical devices which is not currently being examined in other PREFER case studies (see Table 1 below). - Examining other methodological research questions not currently examined in other WP3 case studies with large sample sizes appropriate for addressing these questions, as well as providing a comparison for the research questions currently being addressed in other case studies (see Table 1 below). <p>Table 1: Examined and unexamined features/variables in WP3 case studies</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="336 1496 1361 2038"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="336 1496 951 1653">Study features/variables</th> <th data-bbox="951 1496 1042 1653">NM D study</th> <th data-bbox="1042 1496 1134 1653">RA study</th> <th data-bbox="1134 1496 1228 1653">LC study</th> <th data-bbox="1228 1496 1361 1653">Diabetes study</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="336 1653 951 1771">Examines how similar the results are from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population (RQ 2d)</td> <td data-bbox="951 1653 1042 1771">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1042 1653 1134 1771">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1134 1653 1228 1771"></td> <td data-bbox="1228 1653 1361 1771">✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="336 1771 951 1928">Examines how similar the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods are vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (RQ 2d1)</td> <td data-bbox="951 1771 1042 1928">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1042 1771 1134 1928">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1134 1771 1228 1928">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1228 1771 1361 1928">✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="336 1928 951 2038">Examines educational component with interactive, scenario-based features (RQ 7d)</td> <td data-bbox="951 1928 1042 2038"></td> <td data-bbox="1042 1928 1134 2038"></td> <td data-bbox="1134 1928 1228 2038">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1228 1928 1361 2038">✓</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Study features/variables	NM D study	RA study	LC study	Diabetes study	Examines how similar the results are from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population (RQ 2d)	✓	✓		✓	Examines how similar the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods are vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (RQ 2d1)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Examines educational component with interactive , scenario-based features (RQ 7d)			✓	✓
Study features/variables	NM D study	RA study	LC study	Diabetes study																	
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Examines how similar the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods are vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (RQ 2d1)	✓	✓	✓	✓																	
Examines educational component with interactive , scenario-based features (RQ 7d)			✓	✓																	

Examines preference variation in a disease with the characteristics of patients 11a)	✓			✓
Examines preference variation in a disease with patients recruited through different channels (panels, patient organization, physician) (RQ 11k)				✓
Examines preference variation in a disease with disease experience (RQ 11d)		✓		✓
Examines medical devices				✓
Examines EU11 (or 'Eastern' European) countries				✓

- The evidence and experience related to the use of a DCE which is useful for the EMA qualification process.
- Provide a specific case study examining preferences in an EU11 country, which is currently not being examined in any other PREFER case study (see Figure 1 below)

Figure 1: Map of countries used in WP3 case studies

Method/design	
Methods (If DCE is not proposed: clearly explain why)	<p>Qualitative (Stage 1): An initial item pre-selection will be conducted based on a scoping review of published literature surrounding preferences for diabetes devices. This will be used to compose focus group interview guides. Then, either face-to-face or tele-conference focus group interviews will be conducted with both type 1 and type 2 patients recruited through professional networks or patient representative networks (N=10 from the Netherlands, and N=10 from Poland), interviews with clinicians working with diabetic patients (N=5), interviews with patient representatives (N=5), and</p>

representatives from companies developing these devices (N=5). Data saturation is expected to be achieved after these interviews, although more will be conducted if saturation is not achieved. A similar interview guide will be used for all participants, asking the same questions concerning what is most desired or undesired in these devices including any relevant concerns and unmet medical needs. The data from these interviews will be analysed for relevant and prevalent themes. Along with a scoping literature review, these data will inform relevant attributes and attribute levels of the quantitative stage.

Quantitative (Stage 2):

Patients will be recruited from two different countries (Netherlands and Poland) either for a panel study (minimum N= 500 in NL, N=500 in PL) or through their GP or Patient Organization (minimum N= 300 in NL). Patients will then be randomized (50:50) within each group (NL Panel, PL Panel, NL GP/PO) to receive education on blood glucose monitoring either through traditional means of education (written information collated from digitized pamphlets and pre-existing websites) or through an interactive education tool. They will then be asked to complete a discrete choice experiment (DCE) and Swing weighting (SW) choice task (randomized 50:50 to receive either DCE or SW task first in order to reduce the chance that order effects will introduce a confounding variable into our preference elicitation task). The study design is summarized in Table 2:

Table 2: Study design in quantitative element

Variable		Netherlands	Poland
Recruitment	GP/Patient Organization	✓	
	Panel	✓	✓
Educational Tool	Standard Educational Tool	✓	✓
	Serious Gaming Educational Tool	✓	✓
Method	DCE followed by Swing Weighting	✓	✓
	Swing Weighting followed by DCE	✓	✓

Greater description of the sample sizes can be found in the sample size section. The survey will also contain demographic and clinical history questions, as well as some health literacy and numeracy questions in order to align this case study with the core case studies in PREFER. The beginning of the survey will contain an informed consent form, in line with PREFER agreements.

For the DCE, respondents will be asked to complete several 'choice tasks'

which describe several glucose monitoring devices with different attributes (ISPOR Task Force Report: Constructing Experimental Designs for Discrete-Choice Experiments). They will be asked, for example, a number of times whether they prefer a hypothetical Device A, hypothetical Device B, traditional finger-prick method of measuring glucose (the 'status-quo'), or an opt-out. If the patient self-reports that they are not using any method to monitor their glucose, they will see a comparison of Device A vs Device B vs an opt-out (Table 3). If the patient self-reports that they are currently using a method to monitor their glucose (whether it be a device or finger-pricking), they will see a comparison of Device A vs Device B vs traditional finger-prick (Table 4). This will be a Bayesian D-efficient design with candidate sets, meaning that only two of the profiles with alternative specific constants will be visible for each choice task. This statistically efficient design enables a comparison of a new Device against the status quo of the current monitoring method used by the patient or even if they are currently not measuring their glucose at all, while at the same time keeping the cognitive burden low. Two examples of choice tasks of the DCE survey will appear as follows (although probably with different/more attributes and attribute levels):

Table 3: Example of a possible DCE choice task I: Device A vs Device B vs Opt-out

	Device A	Device B	Opt-out
Accuracy	80%	80%	0%
Skin irritation	Severe	Some	N/A
Replacement time	6 months	2 weeks	N/A
Out of Pocket Cost/month	€200	€100	€0
I prefer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Table 4: Example DCE choice task II: Device A vs Status-Quo vs Opt-out

	Device A	Traditional Finger Prick	Opt-out
Accuracy	80%	95%	0%
Skin irritation	Some	Limited	N/A

Replacement time	2 weeks	5 times daily	N/A
Cost/month	€100	€45	€0
I prefer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

For swing weighting, respondents get a description of a glucose monitoring device that has the worst possible level of performance on all outcome criteria. They are asked which criterion they would select first to improve (i.e., to swing) from the worst to the best level. After the chosen criterion is removed from the entire set of criteria, they are asked which criterion they would select second. This is continued on until all criteria are ranked. This swing-weighting will not use point allocation. The survey will appear as follows (although high probably with different/more attributes and attribute levels):

Table 4: Example swing weighting choice task

If you could improve one aspect of a glucose monitor from worst to best, which would it be?		
Worst possibility	→	Best possibility
70% accuracy	Accuracy	95% accuracy
Severe skin irritation	Skin irritation	Limited
5 times daily	Replacement time	6 months
€200	Cost/month	€45

A think aloud pre-test will be conducted with approximately 10 respondents to assess qualitatively the understandability of the survey.

Afterwards, a pilot run will be conducted with approximately 100 respondents from each country, in order to obtain “prior” values, information necessary to optimise the design and statistical efficiency for the DCE. This means that based on the outcomes of a pilot study, the DCE design will be updated using software to obtain more reliable outcomes within the same sample size.

Between the DCE and the Swing-weighting exercise (whichever is randomised to come first) patients will be asked questions regarding their

	<p>characteristics and background. This serves to provide a break to prevent cognitive fatigue. After both the DCE and Swing-weighting are complete, the patients will complete the Diabetes Self-Management Questionnaire (DSMQ) (Schmitt et al, 2016) which asks patients about their diabetes self-management across four areas (glucose management, dietary control, physical activity, and physician contact) using 20 Likert scale questions with the option of an additional 7 questions specific to insulin use.</p> <p>At the end, patients will also complete a short survey asking whether the patient preferred the DCE or swing-weighting sections, how easy or difficult they found the survey to be, the degree of complexity as experienced by the respondent, and total survey response time will be collected from log data.</p>
Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health Numeracy - Health literacy - Patient Activation <p>For the quantitative phase, a digital, interactive, educational tool to help patients to better understand blood glucose monitoring will be developed in collaboration with the PREFER partner MindBytes. MindBytes has extensive experience in developing educational materials like this and has prototypes available which could be adapted to the diabetes case study. This tool will be based on the outcomes of the qualitative phase in order to ensure that all relevant outcomes and attributes are addressed</p>
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>For both quantitative and qualitative stages, the participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be 18 years old or over - Must reside in the country of recruitment (Netherlands, Poland) - Must be diagnosed with diabetes Type 1 or Type 2 - Must be able to read and understand Dutch, Polish, or English - Must be able to provide informed consent <p>For quantitative stage only:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have access to a computer with internet connection to complete the online survey
Setting (e.g. countries included, location and approach to conducting qualitative study, online or pen/paper)	<p>Qualitative Phase: Online or face-to face focus groups with patients from the Netherlands and online focus groups with patients in Poland (organized by SurveyEngine). Interviews with clinicians, patient representatives, or industry members will be conducted face-to-face or via telephone/voice-over-internet-phone dependent on the wishes of the interviewee.</p> <p>Quantitative Phase: All surveys will be completed online</p>

<p>survey for quantitative study)</p>	
<p>Key exclusion criteria</p>	<p>For both quantitative and qualitative stages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inability to consent or assent by themselves <p>For qualitative stage only:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inability to verbally communicate by themselves <p>For quantitative stage only:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inability to complete on-line survey
<p>Sample Size requirement and recruitment strategy (total and by country)</p>	<p>Sample Size:</p> <p>Participants will be recruited in the Netherlands (minimum n=800) and Poland (minimum n=500). The larger portion of participants from the Netherlands will come from an online panel (minimum n=500) and also there will be recruitment from GPs or patient organizations (minimum n=300). All of the participants from Poland will come from an online panel (minimum n=500). Each of these groups will be split into a group that receives the DCE first, followed by the swing weighting exercise and another group that receives the swing weighting exercise first, followed by the DCE. These groups will split again, into half receiving the standard educational tool, and half receiving the interactive educational tool. At least 650 respondents will receive the DCE first, and 650 respondents will receive the swing weighting first. Additionally, at least 650 participants will receive the standard educational tool (SET), and the other half will receive the interactive educational tool (IET). This information is illustrated in the following Figure:</p> <p>Figure 2: Minimum samples required for the study design</p> <p>For swing weighting, there is no exact sample size required. The sample size does not depend on magnitudes of the utility differences (Tervonen, et al, 2017) because swing weighting captures per-patient preferences in an exact manner. Therefore, the sample sizes will be dictated by the necessities of the DCE. For</p>

	<p>DCEs, the minimum sample size will be calculated using R-code, by using the significance level (α), statistical power level ($1-\beta$), the type of statistical model to be used in the analysis, initial beliefs of the parameter values, and the DCE design (de Bekker-Grob et al, 2015). This formal sample size calculation can and will be conducted, if the final attributes and attribute levels are determined, the choice tasks are known, and a part of the DCE data has been collected. Nevertheless, the sample size mentioned above is larger than what is commonly used in DCE practice in health care (Soekhai et al, 2018). Since we are planning on pooling the data of participants to examine the impact of the variables, a Swait and Louviere test (Swait and Louviere, 1993) will be applied to test the null hypothesis that the values do not differ across the different study arms. Additionally, we will determine whether scale effects affect the direct comparison of the coefficients from the different study arms. The methodology will be completed with direct consultation with DCE and Swing-weighting expertise from the Erasmus Choice Modeling Centre to ascertain state-of-the-art designs and modelling.</p> <p>Recruitment: All patients involved in the qualitative phase of the study will be either recruited through professional networks, patient representatives, or the Julius General Practitioner network. They will be asked to contact the researchers who will explain the goals of the focus groups and see if the patient would like to take part in a focus group. Clinicians working with diabetic patients, patient representatives, and representatives from companies developing these devices will be identified in personal or professional networks and contacted directly by the researchers to inquire as to participation.</p> <p>Patients recruited during the quantitative stage will be recruited via two means. The first of these is through SurveyEngine, who have an established pool of panel participants from which to draw in the Netherlands and in Poland. The second of these recruitment methods is through general practitioners and patient organizations. The Julius Center at the UMC Utrecht has an extensive network of general practitioners in the Netherlands who assist in reaching patients for research purposes (the JHN). Additionally, the Diabetesvereniging Nederland (DVN), a diabetes patient organization in the Netherlands, has offered their help in recruiting patients from the general patient population. The JHN and DVN will be used to recruit the patients for the GP/Patient Organization arm of the study.</p>
<p>Describe how patients will be included in the design and conduct of the preference</p>	<p>Patients will be included in the design of the educational material by involving diabetes patients and diabetes patient representatives to help generate the material on which the educational material will be made. This will be done with the guidance of diabetes clinical nurses, who can give additional insight into the areas that diabetes patients have the most difficulty understanding. This team of experts will then also be consulted in reviewing the educational tool both in terms of usability and content.</p> <p>Diabetes mentors and diabetes patient representatives will also be consulted regarding the content of the final choice tasks to see if the instruments are</p>

study	<p>understandable to the general population and cover the attributes that they find to be most important. A small group of volunteer diabetes patients previously participating in the focus groups will be asked to pilot test the instruments.</p> <p>Finally, diabetes mentors, diabetes patient representatives, patients, and clinicians involved in diabetes care will be asked what the best method is to disseminate results of the studies to the general patient population. They will also be asked to potentially help in drafting these communications to ensure readability.</p>
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Potential results:</p> <p>1) Qualitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o A summary of insights obtained from the interviews and focus groups including patient characteristics o What characteristics/outcomes/attributes patients find important o Patients' expectations regarding glucose monitor devices o Which attributes need to be included in the quantitative phase o What information needs to be included in the educational tool of the quantitative phase <p>2) Quantitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preference study clinical “endpoints” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment profile desirability • Attribute (level) estimates • Relative importance of attributes • Willingness to pay, illustrating the maximum price that patients would pay out of pocket to obtain certain qualities in the product • Maximum acceptable risks / Minimum acceptable benefit (e.g., how much accuracy is necessary for a glucose monitoring device to be acceptable and how much accuracy would be traded for a reduction in risks of skin irritation or invasiveness of application) • Psychological “endpoints”: Health Numeracy, Health Literacy, Patient Activation, and the Diabetes Self-Management with the Diabetes Self-Management Questionnaire (DSMQ). • Preference study methodological “endpoints”: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Heterogeneity of preferences including cross-country differences based on patient characteristics: clinical characteristics (e.g. disease type), demographic data (e.g. age, sex), recruitment technique (e.g. paid panel participants or voluntary GP/PO recruited) psychological characteristics (e.g. patient expectations, risk attitude), cognitive ability of participants (e.g. choice consistency, response time, scale, reported complexity of the tasks), expectations of the device, current care activities o Comparison of preferences when measured by different preference methods types o Comparison of logistics of the two preference methods (DCE and swing weighting) such as costs, time completion, feasibility, etc

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Comparison of preferences when different educational materials are used
Deliverable(s) related to this case study	Study protocol, statistical analysis plan, study report
Estimated start of the case study	January 2019
Estimated completion date of the case study	March 2020
Funding sources (list the different sources of funding to pay for the study)	IMI PREFER project
Key references	<p>Ahola, A.J. and P.H. Groop, <i>Barriers to self-management of diabetes</i>. Diabetic Medicine, 2013. 30(4): p. 413-420.</p> <p>American Diabetes Association, <i>Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus</i>. Diabetes Care, 2012. 35(Supplement 1): p. S64-S71.</p> <p>Ancker JS and Kaufman D. Rethinking health numeracy: a multidisciplinary literature review. J Am Med Inform Assoc. 2007 14(6) 713-21.</p> <p>Benjamin, E.M., <i>Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose: The Basics</i>. Clinical Diabetes Jan 2002, 20 (1) 45-47; DOI: 10.2337/diaclin.20.1.45</p> <p>Byeong SA. Compatible weighting method with rank order centroid: maximum entropy ordered weighted averaging approach. Eur J Oper Res. 2011;212:552–9.</p> <p>Dalewitz, J., N. Khan, and C.O. Hershey, <i>Barriers to Control of Blood Glucose in Diabetes Mellitus</i>. American Journal of Medical Quality, 2000. 15(1): p. 16-25.</p>

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Taryfikacji Agencja Oceny Technologii Medycznych i Taryfikacji, "Opinia Rady Przejrzystości nr 78/2018 z dnia 9 kwietnia 2018 roku w sprawie oceny zasadności rozszerzenia wykazu wyrobów medycznych wydawanych na zlecenie o system

	<p>monitorowania glikemii flash (FGM)” http://bipold.aotm.gov.pl/assets/files/zlecenia_mz/2017/175/ORP/U_14_117_180409_opinia_78_FGM.pdf</p> <p>World Health Organization, <i>Global status report on noncommunicable diseases 2014</i>. 2014: Geneva.</p> <p>World Health Organization, <i>Diabetes country profiles</i>, 2016</p>
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PAVING study

Disease / Clinical Context

Gene therapy

The pharmaceutical sector is shifting from a focus on classic chemical medicines to the development of more complex therapies like gene therapy. The European Medicines Agency (EMA) defines a gene therapy medicinal product (GTMP) as: “a biological medicinal product that contains an active substance which contains or consists of a recombinant nucleic acid used in or administered to humans to regulate, repair, replace, add or delete genetic sequence and its therapeutic, prophylactic or diagnostic effect relates directly to the recombinant nucleic acid sequence it contains or to the product of genetic expression of this sequence”³. Gene therapy is achieved through 1) genome editing to adjust somatic DNA, 2) gene addition to deliver an extra episome to the nucleus of the target cells, or 3) gene knock-down/out to inactivate disease-causing genes⁴. Currently, gene therapy clinical trials are being conducted for several diseases such as cancer, monogenic disorders like primary immunodeficiencies (PID) and haemophilia, neurological diseases and ocular diseases. Monogenic disorders belong to the disease area with the second highest amount of gene therapy clinical trials, second to cancer⁵. More detail concerning the monogenic disorders and current treatments is summarized below. For more information on the (clinical trial and marketing authorization) advances of gene therapy for monogenic disorders, please refer to Appendix I.

Haemophilia

Haemophilia is an X-linked inherited bleeding disorder characterized by a deficit in coagulation factor VIII (FVIII) in haemophilia A or coagulation factor IX (FIX) in haemophilia B. Haemophilia is classified as a rare disease occurring in 1 of 10 000 births of which haemophilia A patients account for 80-85% of the haemophilia population⁶. The severity of haemophilia depends on the remaining factor concentration. The disease is classified as mild when residual factor concentration is 5-40% of normal factor levels (1UI/ml), moderate when 1-5% and severe when <1% of normal levels⁷⁻⁹. The symptoms of haemophilia are mainly characterized by bleeding in the joints or muscles. This bleeding can occur spontaneously in severe haemophilia and mainly occurs after injuries in mild and moderate haemophilia. The bleeding of the joints causes haemophilic arthropathy which leads to joint swelling, pain, stiffness and immobility of the limb^{7, 10, 11}. Patients are diagnosed and symptomatic in the first years of life. Today, haemophilia treatment is based on increasing factor concentrations to adequately maintain haemostasis and prevent spontaneous bleeds as well as bleeds after surgery or trauma. Factor replacement therapy can be prophylactic, the guideline in Western countries, or administered on-demand. Prophylaxis is administered intravenously and injection is necessary two times per week for haemophilia B and three times per week for haemophilia A. The invasiveness of intravenous injection and the high administration frequency results in a high burden of treatment^{10, 12-14}. Therefore, new treatment options are being investigated. Today, extended half-life factors are available which decreases the dosing interval 1.5-fold for haemophilia A and 2.5- to 5-fold for haemophilia B^{8, 15, 16}. Additionally, non-factor therapies, such as monoclonal antibodies or RNAi therapy administered through subcutaneous injection, are being developed^{8, 15, 16}. However, life-long injections are still necessary and adherence to therapy remains low¹⁴.

Recently, gene therapy for the treatment of haemophilia is being extensively studied as a new treatment option. Clinical trial results are promising and currently two in vivo Adeno Associated Virus (AAV)-based gene therapies for haemophilia B and one in vivo AAV-based gene therapy for haemophilia A are moving to phase 3 trials¹⁷⁻¹⁹. For an overview of all gene therapy clinical trials in haemophilia, please refer to Appendix II. Gene therapy has been able to reduce the annualized bleeding rate to zero and eliminates the need for further factor replacement therapy in several patients²⁰⁻²⁴. However, multiple challenges remain. First, the effectiveness of AAV vector serotypes is hindered by the presence of neutralizing

antibodies (NAb)²⁵, present in approximately 30-50% of the population²⁶. Second, during clinical trials all subjects developed high NAb titer which currently inhibits second administration with the same AAV vector serotype. Third, the induction of a T-cell immune response after AAV vector administration and the subsequent decrease in factor level threatens long-term efficacy. The heterogeneity reported in clinical trial results regarding the cellular immune response warrants further investigation. Fourth, thorough follow-up of treated patients is crucial to establish long-term safety and efficacy^{5, 8, 27, 28}.

For a graphical overview of all treatment options in haemophilia please refer to Appendix III.

A list of all patient preference studies conducted in haemophilia can be found in Appendix IV.

Primary Immunodeficiencies (PID)

ADA-SCID is a rare (1:375,000 to 1:660,000 live births in Europe) autosomal recessive PID. A mutation in the ADA gene on chromosome 20 is the cause of this condition. More than 70 different mutations in the ADA gene have been described. Most of these mutations result in the substitution of an amino acid causing an unstable ADA enzyme or a complete loss of the enzyme. With purine nucleoside phosphorylase, ADA forms an essential component of the purine salvage pathway, responsible for the irreversible deamination of adenosine and 2'deoxyadenosine into inosine and 2'deoxyinosine respectively. Absent or impaired function consequently results in both intracellular and extracellular accumulation of these substrates²⁹. ADA-deficiency results in a lack of T-, B- and natural killer cells, leading to the susceptibility of ADA-SCID patients to severe recurrent infections. Patients are diagnosed and symptomatic at birth. Untreated ADA-SCID patients are expected to die in their first or second life year²⁹⁻³³. Strimvelis, a retroviral gene therapy for ADA-SCID allowing for DNA integration of the human ADA cDNA sequence, received marketing authorization in Europe on May 26th, 2016 for the treatment of patients with ADA-SCID³⁴⁻³⁶. Current alternative therapies for ADA-SCID besides gene therapy are bone marrow transplantation (Haematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation; HSCT) and enzyme replacement therapy^{37, 38}.

The benefits of Strimvelis have been shown in one main study involving 18 patients from 6 months to around 6 years old with ADA-SCID. Patients in the study had no appropriate bone marrow donor and alternative treatment had not worked or was not available. All patients were treated with Strimvelis and were still alive 3 years after treatment. The rate of severe infections declined after treatment and continued to decline with longer-term follow-up beyond 3 years³⁹. While the benefits of Strimvelis have been shown, also side effects have been shown. The most common side effect with Strimvelis (which may affect up to 1 in 10 people) is pyrexia. Serious side effects with Strimvelis may include effects linked to autoimmunity such as haemolytic anaemia, aplastic anaemia, hepatitis, thrombocytopenia and Guillain-Barré syndrome. Besides side effects, also the long-term safety and efficacy of Strimvelis is unknown.

In other PIDs gene therapy is also in development, such as in X-linked severe combined immunodeficiency (SCID-X1; common gamma chain) and Wiskott–Aldrich syndrome (WAS). In SCID-X1, gene therapy using gamma retroviral vectors has been studied in clinical trials since 1999^{40, 41}. Gene therapy in SCID-X1 showed improved cellular and humoral immunity. However, patients developed T cell acute lymphoblastic leukaemia 2.5–6 years after treatment. Significant concerns for safety halted clinical trials in SCID-X1 and other conditions for several years⁴². New gene therapies with safety improvements like self-inactivating (SIN) gamma retroviral and lentiviral vectors followed and are being studied in phase 1/2 clinical trials⁴²⁻⁴⁵. In WAS, also early gamma retroviral vectors were first used (2006-2009) and multiple patients developed leukaemia⁴⁶. Subsequently, SIN lentiviral vectors have been studied in phase 1/2 studies^{33, 47-49}.

For an overview of all gene therapy clinical trials in ADA-SCID, SCID-X1 and WAS, please refer to Appendix II. For a graphical overview of all treatment options in ADA-SCID, SCID-X1 and WAS, please refer to Appendix III.

A list of all patient preference studies conducted in PIDs can be found in Appendix IV.

Methodological Context	
<p>The work done in PREFER WP2 led to the identification of relevant concerns to be addressed with this case study (see also section “Describe which PREFER research question(s) will be addressed”):</p> <p>How patient preference studies can be conducted in paediatric populations; and when preferences of caregivers are sought, how these then relate to patient preferences</p> <p>How education should be provided to participants in patient preference studies</p> <p>How patient preference studies can be conducted in small patient populations (rare diseases)</p> <p>How patient preference studies can be designed to be informative for HTA and reimbursement decisions</p>	
Background and Rationale	
Describe the preference sensitive situation	<p>Preference sensitive situation</p> <p>According to the FDA, decisions are preference sensitive when:</p> <p>multiple treatment options exist and there is no option that is clearly superior for all patients;</p> <p>the evidence supporting one option over others is considerably uncertain or variable; and/or</p> <p>patients’ views about the most important benefits and acceptable risks of a technology vary considerably within a population, or differ from those of healthcare professionals”⁵⁰.</p> <p>In addition, the FDA states that patient preferences might be useful in case the product has a direct patient interface, intends to yield significant health and appearance benefits, directly affects health-related quality of life, can be life-saving but comes with high-risks, is developed to fill an unmet medical need or treat a rare disease or condition, offers alternative benefits to those already marketed, and uses novel technology⁵⁰.</p> <p>While only one criterion needs to be met for preference sensitivity, the context in which this study will be conducted (gene therapy in rare diseases) meets multiple criteria: 1) the first FDA criterion: “multiple treatment options exist and there is no option that is clearly superior for all patients” (Appendix III and V); 2) the second FDA criterion, as the evidence supporting gene therapy is considerably uncertain regarding long-term outcomes, contributing to the perception that no option exists that is superior to all patients; 3) almost all situations in which the FDA states that these studies could be useful; 4) different criteria mentioned by stakeholders (including HTA representatives and regulators) in the interviews and focus groups of PREFER task 2.1 and 2.2: rare diseases, chronic diseases, unclear benefit-risk balance (heterogeneous drug profiles), high unmet medical need, innovative approach, invasive treatments, and paediatric populations.</p> <p>For a graphical overview of all treatment options and preference sensitive decisions in PIDs and haemophilia, please refer to Appendix III. All attributes and levels as identified in literature (clinical trials and previous preference studies) are listed in Appendix V. An overview of feedback from PREFER, WP2, WP3 and WP4 leads regarding the preference sensitivity can be found in Appendix VII.</p>
How the case study supports or informs	<p>Future decision making</p> <p>With the rise of Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMPs), including gene therapies, that might have a permanent effect in patients, decision making (on HTA, marketing authorization and patient level) will increasingly have to deal with uncertainty</p>

<p>medical product decision making</p>	<p>regarding long-term outcomes. While performing patient preference studies in this context will not take away this uncertainty (this can only be resolved by life-long follow-up of these patients), it could provide insights on the acceptability to patients of different degrees of benefit over time and maximum acceptable risk to inform decision making. In addition, drug development is increasingly focussing on precision-medicines and rare diseases. To inform the decision making of tomorrow, we have to investigate 1) how we can perform patient preference studies in small populations and 2) how we can take into account advanced attributes such as uncertainty regarding long-term outcomes that decision makers will increasingly be confronted with. With this study we mainly aim to inform HTA/reimbursement decision making, but the study could also inform marketing authorization and clinical decision making.</p> <p>HTA/reimbursement (primary decision point)</p> <p>Gene therapies are high-cost drugs and offer a 'one and done' approach where one infusion can possibly replace lifelong administration of other high-cost drugs. But even when marketing authorisation is granted, their high cost and uncertainty relating to long-term outcomes hinder market access. The current approved gene therapies for monogenic diseases in Europe show that reaching the market is a slow and difficult process. Glybera®, approved in Europe in 2012 for the treatment of lipoprotein lipase deficiency, was only used in one patient in Germany for a price of €900 000 and is now withdrawn from the market since no renewal of market authorisation was requested ⁵¹. Strimvelis®, approved by the EMA in 2016 for the treatment of adenosine deaminase deficiency–severe combined immunodeficiency (ADA-SCID), a primary immunodeficiency (PID), requires specific cell processing and is only administrable in a specialized centre in Italy. The Italian medicines agency is reimbursing the treatment at a price of €594 000 using a risk-sharing agreement and a payback if the treatment is unsuccessful. However, there is still uncertainty whether the Italian health care system can support this price ^{52, 53}.</p> <p>Hanna et al. suggest two challenges for advanced therapeutic medicinal products (ATMPs) such as gene therapies to overcome: 1) convince payers of the added value of the therapy and 2) make sure that the therapy is still affordable given the healthcare budget ⁵³. The second challenge can be addressed by innovative reimbursement schemes and systems. Regarding the first challenge, for value assessments of gene therapies but also for other cures, it has been argued that Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY) may not be appropriate for assessing the value of cures and that elements beyond health gain should be taken into account ^{54, 55}. Gutknecht et al. ⁵⁵ stated that the QALY only reflects clinical outcomes that have a direct impact on Quality of Life (QoL) and/or survival, and suggested that through measuring patient preferences also process characteristics (e.g. treatment administration or frequency) and non-health outcomes (e.g. costs) can be taken into account.</p> <p>In HTA, patient preferences can inform the identification of patient-relevant outcomes, inform the identification of subpopulations for whom the benefits outweigh the risks, help to weigh outcomes according to their relative importance to patients, and can be used as quality-of-life weights in the calculation of quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) ⁵⁶.</p> <p>In measuring patient preferences regarding gene therapy, the PAVING study has the potential to provide information on how patient preference studies can be designed to provide relevant input for the appraisal of gene therapies in an era of value-based and patient centric healthcare. Besides patient preferences also all other factors that are relevant for reimbursement decisions (including the cost of the treatment), will be</p>
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	<p>weighed and considered in these appraisals and in decision making. HTA and payer members of the study specific advisory board will provide input on how the preference study can be designed in a way that the results will be most informative for HTA and payers, their role does not imply any responsibility with respect to future HTAs and reimbursement decisions regarding gene therapies.</p> <p>Marketing authorization (secondary decision point) While this study will not aim to inform regulators, the results obtained from this study could still inform regulators on whether or not, or in what cases, patients are willing to accept gene therapies. In the FDA draft guidance on Human Gene Therapy for Haemophilia ⁵⁷, the FDA states “Patient experience data may provide important additional information about the clinical benefit of a Gene Therapy product. FDA encourages sponsors to collect patient experience data during product development, and to submit such data in the marketing application”, encouraging the submission of patient preference information regarding gene therapy. EMA has also shown interest in feedback from patients regarding gene therapy ⁵⁸. The advisory board of the study includes one representative from the Committee for Advanced Therapies of EMA to ensure the study is also relevant for regulators.</p> <p>Clinical decision making (tertiary decision point) While this study will not aim to inform physicians, the results obtained from this study could still inform physicians in showing the spectrum of preferences that patients can have regarding gene therapy and other potential therapies, and on how to educate patients on gene therapy.</p>					
<p>Describe which PREFER research question(s) will be addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>PREFER research questions Table 1 shows the different PREFER research questions that will be investigated in this study and the way in which they will be addressed.</p>					
	<p>Table 1 PREFER research questions</p>					
	<p>PREFER research question category</p>	<p>PREFER research question</p>	<p>Data used</p>	<p>Assessment type</p>	<p>Compared populations</p>	
	<p>Methodological Research Questions: Higher priority</p>	<p>4a 2 Which presentation formats respondents prefer (displays, video, descriptions, etc.)</p>	<p>Interviews</p>	<p>Qualitative/descriptive (results will be used in design of educational tool and survey)</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>Disease dependent methodological research questions</p>	<p>9b How generalizable are preferences from one disease to</p>	<p>Interviews and survey</p>	<p>Qualitative/descriptive and statistical*</p>	<p>Haemophili a caregivers vs. PID caregivers</p>	

			related diseases?																							
		11 b	How preferences vary between patients and caregivers	Survey	Statistical	Haemophili a patients vs. haemophilia caregivers																				
		11 d	How preferences vary with disease severity	Survey	Statistical	Moderate vs. severe haemophilia patients																				
	Questions unlikely to be addressed in case studies but needed for WP4	15 b	How to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/ tailored to decision making?	Meetings with advisory board	Qualitative/ descriptive	NA																				
* Depends on the selection of attributes; NA, Not applicable																										
How the study contributes to the final PREFER recommendations	<p>PREFER recommendations</p> <p>This study will be of added value to the PREFER recommendations as it 1) meets the PREFER strategy in investigating how qualitative and quantitative patient preference studies can be conducted in the context of rare diseases and how these studies can inform HTA and reimbursement decisions, 2) can provide insights on how patient preference studies should be designed to inform future decision making for very innovative (advanced) therapies and ultra-rare diseases, and 3) it investigates PREFER research questions that are not yet addressed by other case studies, including research questions that were labelled as “<i>Questions unlikely to be addressed in case studies but needed for WP4</i>”. Table 2 demonstrates the added value for the recommendations of the PAVING study compared to the other WP3 case studies.</p>																									
<p>Table 2 Features of the study compared to other WP3 case studies</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Study features</th> <th>NMD study</th> <th>RA study</th> <th>LC study</th> <th>Diabetes study</th> <th>PAVING study</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="2">PREFER strategy</td> <td>Examines a rare disease⁶</td> <td>✓</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Is primarily conducted to inform HTA/reimbursement</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>✓</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Study features		NMD study	RA study	LC study	Diabetes study	PAVING study	PREFER strategy	Examines a rare disease ⁶	✓				✓	Is primarily conducted to inform HTA/reimbursement					✓
Study features		NMD study	RA study	LC study	Diabetes study	PAVING study																				
PREFER strategy	Examines a rare disease ⁶	✓				✓																				
	Is primarily conducted to inform HTA/reimbursement					✓																				

Future decision	Examines an ultra-rare disease ⁶					✓
	Examines preferences regarding an advanced therapy					✓
PREFER research questions	Examines which presentation formats respondents prefer (4a2)					✓
	Examines how generalizable preferences are from one disease to related diseases (9b)	✓				✓
	Examines to what degree preferences vary with stakeholder perspective: patient vs caregiver (11b)	✓ ¹				✓ ^{2,3}
	Examines to what degree preferences vary with disease experience or severity (11d)		✓ ⁴		✓ ⁴	✓ ^{3,5}
	Examines how to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/tailored to decision making (15b)					✓
<p>1. Some patients have impaired or reduced cognitive function 2. Patients do not have impaired or reduced cognitive function 3. Only in haemophilia 4. The study investigates how preferences vary with disease experience, not severity 5. The study investigates how preferences vary with disease severity 6. Rare disease EU definition: less than 1 in 2,000 people 7. Ultra-rare disease EU definition: less than one in 50,000 people</p>						
<p>This study can together with the other WP3 case studies contribute to the following topics of the recommendations (topics cited from ‘Scope of Recommendations’): Rationale for conducting/using patient preference studies: This study will contribute to showing what the value of patient preferences can be in patient preference sensitive situations. Overview of evidence-based patient preference exploration and elicitation methods: This study can provide new evidence on the value of some qualitative and quantitative methods (see section below on methods). Considerations for when and how to design patient preference studies: This study will investigate how to design patient preference studies in (ultra-)rare diseases aiming to inform HTA bodies or payers. The question of how to conduct patient preference studies in rare diseases was specifically raised in the PREFER strategy document (“Chapter 4 Further PREFER strategy and tactics”) Use of results of patient preference studies in assessments and decision making: As discussed in the PREFER strategy document (Chapter 4 “Further PREFER strategy and tactics”), PREFER would like to investigate how patient preferences can be used in</p>						

	<p>decision making. This study will be designed in collaboration and discussion with HTA bodies and payers to generate a study design relevant for HTA and payer decision making. In doing this, we will be able to provide insights regarding research question 15b: how to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/tailored to decision making.</p> <p>Involvement of patients in patient preference studies: This study could be a great example of how patients can contribute to patient preference studies as we will collaborate with multiple patient organizations and EUPATI Belgium (see section in study population on collaboration with patients).</p> <p>For an overview of feedback from PREFER, WP2, WP3 and WP4 leads regarding the added value of this study, please refer to <i>Appendix VII</i>.</p>
Method/design	
<p>Methods (If DCE is not proposed: clearly explain why)</p>	<p>Qualitative method selection</p> <p>The qualitative phase will be used to identify attributes important to patients and will inform the selection of attributes (<i>Appendix V</i>) for the quantitative phase. The PREFER task 2.7 report indicates that for HTA/post-marketing decision making the following qualitative (exploration) methods score high: semi-structured interviews, in-depth interviews, nominal group technique, focus groups and dyadic interviews. Since we would like to use an individual technique (to allow participants to express themselves equally), but also a structured interview guide that allows for some open discussion with the participants, we would like to conduct semi-structured interviews till saturation (with a maximum of 30 interviews).</p> <p>Quantitative method selection</p> <p><i>We will not use DCE:</i> We think that conducting a DCE in rare diseases could add to the evidence PREFER wants to generate for the EMA methods qualification. However, we think that our population size and estimated sample sizes are too low to perform a DCE (especially in the PID population, ultra-rare, were will not be able to recruit the hundreds of patients necessary to perform a DCE)⁵⁹⁻⁶¹. Since we want to compare results between populations, we think it would be better to choose another elicitation method.</p> <p><i>Selected method:</i> We will use the (probabilistic) threshold technique in this study, one of the 10 most promising preference elicitation methods identified by PREFER task 2.7. In our selection of the method, the threshold technique was found to be the best fit for this particular study as this method is able to compare a standard of care versus a new alternative (gene therapy) and does this in a profile setting (which is not the case for swing-weighting for example). In addition, the method allows for elicitation of individual preferences (n=1), allowing use in very low sample sizes and exploration of preference heterogeneity by regressing each outcome on characteristics of the respondents. The precision of the estimates will be greater and standard deviations will be smaller when the sample size increases. The method can be performed with the limited proposed PID sample size of 20-30 participants. It is advisable that the amount of threshold question series (the number of investigated attributes) is kept between 4-6.</p> <p>For more information on how the method was selected and feedback from methods experts, please refer to <i>Appendix VI</i>. For an overview of feedback from PREFER, WP2, WP3 and WP4 leads regarding the method selection, please refer to <i>Appendix VII</i>.</p>
<p>Accompanying</p>	<p>Psychological instruments: health literacy (Chew et al. 2008)⁶²</p>

psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	Educational tools: We want to create an educational tool explaining gene therapy to patients. This will be done in collaboration with EUPATI Belgium, the involved patient organizations (BOPPI and AHVH), physicians and MindBytes.
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>Haemophilia patients: Diagnosed with haemophilia A or B Disease severity: moderate or severe, or taking prophylactic factor replacement therapy Over 18 years of age</p> <p>Haemophilia caregivers: Caregiver* of child (2-18 years old) diagnosed with haemophilia A or B Over 18 years of age</p> <p>PID caregivers: Caregiver* of child (<18 years old) diagnosed with ADA-SCID, WAS or SCID-X1 Over 18 years of age</p> <p>* Caregivers are defined as parent(s), legal guardian or other adult family member living in the same house or in contact with the patient in a caregiver relationship at least 4 times/week for at least one hour or more</p>
Setting	<p>Country: Belgium</p> <p>Qualitative approach: Interviews (the interviewer meets the interviewee at a location that is convenient for the interviewee)</p> <p>Quantitative: Online survey</p>
Key exclusion criteria	<p>Insufficient command of the Dutch, French or English language – with exception of Moroccan Arabic or other Moroccan languages (interpreter will be subcontracted)</p> <p>Not living in Belgium</p>
Sample Size requirements and recruitment strategy (total and by country)	<p>Qualitative phase: We want to conduct interviews till saturation is reached, with a maximum of 30 interviews: Haemophilia: 10 patients and 10 caregivers PID: 10 caregivers</p> <p>Recruitment: Through hospitals (UZ leuven, possibly also UZ Gent) and patient organizations (BOPPI and AHVH) in Belgium</p> <p>Quantitative phase: Haemophilia: Haemophilia is a rare disease (EU definition: 1 in 2,000 people) but relatively common compared to other rare diseases. We estimate that we will be able to include 100-300 patients and around 100 caregivers. The number of affected patients in Belgium for haemophilia A is 992 and 239 for haemophilia B according to the 2017 annual global survey of the World Federation of Haemophilia (WFH). PID: ADA-SCID, WAS and SCID-X1 are all ultra-rare diseases (EU definition: one in 50,000 people) and the exact prevalence in Belgium is difficult to measure. In discussion with the specialist at the University hospital of Leuven the physician mentioned that we should be able to find 10 ADA-SCID participants (parents). Also, the patient organization (BOPPI) is eager to collaborate. Therefore, we estimated that we could reach a PID sample size for the quantitative phase of 20-30 caregivers.</p> <p>Recruitment: Through hospitals (UZ leuven, possibly also UZ Gent) and patient organizations (BOPPI and AHVH) in Belgium</p>

	<p>Sample size requirements: The threshold technique allows for elicitation of individual preferences (n=1) and the method can thus be used in very low sample sizes. The precision of the estimates will be greater and standard deviations will be smaller when the sample size increases. A method expert confirmed that the method can be performed with the limited proposed PID sample size of 20-30 participants. The amount of threshold question series (the number of investigated attributes) was advised to be kept between 4-6.</p> <p>For an overview of feedback from PREFER, WP2, WP3 and WP4 leads regarding the patient population and recruitment, please refer to <i>Appendix VII</i>.</p>
Describe how patients will be included in the design and conduct of the preference study	<p>Patient involvement</p> <p>EUPATI Belgium will be involved in the creation of the educational tool and to ensure the study is patient relevant the protocol will be setup with, and reviewed by, patients/patient representatives from the Belgian Organisation For Patients With Primary Immunodeficiency (BOPPI), Belgian Haemophilia Society (AHVH) and European Organisation for Rare Diseases (EURORDIS).</p>
Outcome measurement	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Endpoints / attributes and potential levels: For an overview of all potential attributes and levels, please refer to Appendix V. The selection of attributes and assessment of the value of outcomes to decision-making will be made as follows (Figure 1):</p> <p>identify attributes through a literature review (clinical trials, previous patient preference studies and reimbursement criteria) have a first meeting with the advisory board to identify attributes important to decision-makers (top-down identification of attributes) - to see if they give more importance to the main clinical endpoints in clinical trials, to patient reported/relevant outcomes, or to other attributes like costs and administration frequency in the context of gene therapy for haemophilia and primary immunodeficiencies - ; and to ask what criteria they would use to assess the preference study if it was submitted to them in interviews with patients and caregivers identify attributes important to them (bottom-up identification of attributes) and subsequently ask them to indicate their top 3 and bottom 3 attributes on a list compiling the ones they identified and those of decision-makers have a follow-up meeting with the advisory board to discuss results of interviews and finalize the selection of 4-6 attributes to investigate with the threshold technique (consensus meeting) design the threshold technique using the 4-6 attributes agreed upon and taking into account the assessment criteria decision-makers would use to assess the study if it was submitted to them have a final advisory board meeting to discuss the results of the threshold technique and evaluate the value of these results to decision-making</p>

Planning	
Deliverables related to this case study	Data Management Plan, Qualitative study protocol, quantitative study protocol, statistical analysis plan, study report.
Estimated start	January 2019
Estimated completion	April 2020 For an overview of the timelines, please refer to the PAVING flowchart .
Contributions	For an overview of the contributions of Eline van Overbeeke and Isabelle Huys to this study and the main case studies of PREFER, please refer to the PAVING flowchart . Brett Hauber will be involved in the study to guide Eline through the design and analysis of the quantitative phase. Only involved PREFER KU Leuven researchers (Eline and Isabelle) will have access to the raw data.
Funding sources	We would like to seek funding from PREFER. For an overview of the requested budget, please refer to the PAVING budget overview .

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Multiple Myeloma

Disease / Clinical Context

The proposed additional case study concerns a patient preference study among Multiple Myeloma (MM) patients and aims to elicit their preferences for the treatment of MM.

Incidence, epidemiology and symptoms of MM

Accounting for 1% of all cancers and 13% of blood cancers, MM is the second most frequent haematological malignancy after non-Hodgkin lymphoma^{63, 64}. In Europe, MM has an incidence of 4.5–6.0/100000/year and the median age at diagnosis is between 65 and 70 years. The mortality of MM is 4.1/100000/year⁶⁴. MM is characterised by a proliferation of plasma cells in the bone marrow, typically accompanied by the secretion of monoclonal immunoglobulins (M-proteins)⁶⁵. This proliferation causes symptoms such as skeletal damage, hypercalcemia, renal insufficiency, anaemia and infections⁶⁶. MM is a rare disease and similarly, treatments being approved by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) for the treatment of MM receive orphan designation. Despite several treatments being available (see below), MM has been labelled an incurable disease and only half of the diagnosed patients live longer than five years under currently available treatments. Because MM disrupts the normal functioning of the bone marrow, damages the bones and causes kidney failure, MM is a debilitating and life-threatening disease¹. These facts stress the need for the development and market entry of innovative MM treatments².

Current treatment landscape

Clinical practice guidelines

The MM treatment landscape is changing drastically; both in first-line and relapse settings, the introduction of new drugs has transformed the MM treatment approach. The following classes of medical products currently exist: **immunotherapies** (such as monoclonal antibodies) **and other therapies** (such as alkylators, steroids, proteasome inhibitors and histone deacetylase inhibitors)⁶⁷. Both national and international clinical practice guidelines exist for the treatment of MM. The two main international MM clinical practice guidelines are those issued by the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN)^{64, 66}. Focusing on the European context, the text below describes the ESMO guidelines, whereas the NCCN guidelines are given in Appendix 1,2 and 3. The ESMO guidelines recommend that treatment is initiated in all patients with *active* MM, as opposed to *asymptomatic (=smoldering) myeloma*, where *immediate* treatment is not recommended. For **patients in good clinical condition** (fit or young patients), induction therapy (i.e. the initial therapy toward reducing the number of cancer cells) followed by high-dose therapy with autologous stem cell transplantation (ASCT) is the standard treatment⁶⁴ (See figure 1 for first-line treatment). As induction therapy, the ESMO guidelines recommend performing 3-4 courses of **three-drug combinations** including at least bortezomib (first-in-class proteasome inhibitor) plus dexamethasone, and as a third drug, e.g. thalidomide, doxorubicin, lenalidomide or cyclophosphamide⁶⁴. Due to a lack of clinical trial evidence, consolidation therapy (i.e. intensification or post-remission therapy, used to further

¹ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/medicines/human/orphan-designations/eu3161767>

² www.ema.europa.eu/en/news/new-treatment-patients-multiple-myeloma

diminish the number of cancer cells) is currently not recommended by ESMO⁶⁴. For patients in good clinical conditions, ESMO recommends that ASCT be followed by maintenance therapy (i.e. therapy used to help a primary treatment succeed)⁶⁷. For **elderly patients, ineligible for ASCTS**, oral combinations of melphalan and prednisone (MP) plus novel agents are considered as standards of care in Europe⁶⁴.

Figure 1. First-line treatment of MM

Patients in good clinical condition are eligible and follow the arm “yes”. Elderly patients are ineligible for ACTS and follow the arm “no”. MPT, melphalan, prednisone, thalidomide; VMP, bortezomib, melphalan, prednisone; CTD, cyclophosphamide, thalidomide, dexamethasone; MP, melphalan, prednisone; VTD, bortezomib, thalidomide, dexamethasone; VCD, bortezomib, cyclophosphamide, dexamethasone; PAD, bortezomib, doxorubicin, dexamethasone; RVD, lenalidomide, bortezomib, dexamethasone. Copied from *Multiple myeloma: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up (2013)*.

Real-world treatment practices in Europe

Although there are established standards of care in the newly diagnosed setting where patients are categorised into transplant eligible or transplant ineligible (Figure 1), the standard of care is less clear in the relapse settings (second and further treatment lines). A number of regimens are approved for the whole relapse setting (Appendix 3). Additionally, both ESMO and NCCN guidelines lack specificity as regards to which specific medical product to be selected above another in relapse settings (Appendix 3). This results in a challenge for physicians^{63, 67}. This challenge is reflected in the results by Raab *et al.*⁶³, where real-world evidence on current (2016) treatment practices was investigated and notable differences in current (2016) practices were found regarding the medical products used in second and following treatment lines across European countries (Appendix 4,5). Raab *et al.*⁶³ attribute the diversity of prescribed treatments to the fact that although current ESMO and NCCN guidelines list a number of alternative regimens, they lack precise recommendations on which of these should be preferred for relapsed or refractory MM patients and there are no standards of care and optimal treatment choices^{68, 69}.

Methodological Context

Decision-making context of the preference study: the centralized marketing authorization of medical products

This study primarily focusses on informing the regulatory benefit-risk assessment (BRA) as part of the centralized marketing authorization (MA) for novel MM treatments such as immunotherapies. Besides balancing benefits and risks, BRA is characterized by an interplay between the interpretation of hard clinical data and value judgements⁷⁰. Over the past decade, the existing BRA has been put into question, as it has been argued that regulators have a different risk tolerance than patients on whose behalf they take decisions⁷¹. Furthermore, it is doubted whether the patient perspective is sufficiently understood in regulatory BRA, as the clinical trial endpoints considered during regulatory BRA usually do not explicitly capture the patient perspective (27).

Addressing these concerns, the potential role of patient preferences in regulatory BRA has been advocated⁶⁹⁻⁸⁷. Reasons why their use in regulatory BRA is encouraged include that

patients are uniquely experienced with the disease and the treatment-associated benefits and risks and that including patient preferences will lead to a better acceptance among external stakeholders about the decision made^{69, 86, 88-91}. Patient preferences are not equally valuable for informing decision-making in all disease areas and for all medical products. The term “**preference sensitive**” has been coined to refer to decisions where patient preferences matter⁵⁰; authors argue that the value of patient preferences in BRA is higher in preference sensitive situations^{75, 81, 83, 85, 92}, e.g. when the medical product under evaluation answers a **medical need** or involves a **challenging benefit-risk tradeoff**^{75, 92}.

Methodological issues related to measuring patient preferences for regulatory BRA addressed in the proposed additional case study

The use of patient preferences in BRA as a possible tool for understanding the patients’ perspective on the relevance of outcomes, benefit-risk tradeoffs and for tailoring MA decisions based on subgroups with homogeneous preferences has been suggested several times^{73, 79, 81, 83, 93}. However, their use in regulatory benefit-risk assessment is currently hampered by an important methodological issue, namely **the neglect of preference heterogeneity and variation among subgroups**^{76, 86, 94}. Preference heterogeneity has been described as “the part of the natural variation between patients (variability) that can be attributed to characteristics of those patients”. Preference heterogeneity and variation in preferences among patient subgroups implicate that the value of medical products might be perceived differently by different groups of patients⁷⁶. The importance of measuring preference heterogeneity has also been underlined by stakeholders taking part in WP2 interviews and focus groups, and in the PREFER strategy document.

The different possible sources of preference heterogeneity can be classified into the following categories of patient characteristics: (i) **cultural variables** (e.g. geographical area, ethnicity, religion), (ii) **demographic variables** (e.g. age, sex, education, employment), (iii) **clinical variables** (e.g. time of diagnosis, disease stage, treatment experience) and (iv) **psychological variables** (e.g. health literacy, health numeracy). Although authors stress the importance of analyzing preference heterogeneity when uniform decisions are considered for heterogeneous populations, as is the case for regulatory MA⁹⁵, and underline the value of this information for BRA, in practice, preference heterogeneity is often ignored or badly understood^{73, 75, 76, 81, 83, 94}. Additionally, in order to take into account the results from a specific preference study in a certain MA decision, it is crucial that regulators know to what extent the patients included in a specific preference study resemble the patients for whom the MA decision needs to be taken, i.e. the extent to which these patients’ preferences can be **generalized** to the larger European population (the importance of which has also been highlighted in the PREFER strategy document, category “generalizability”). A lack of this information may lead to uncertainty on behalf of regulators assessing the preference study results on whether they can consider these results ‘representative’ for the patient population for whom they need to take the decision. Briefly, since BRA is primarily based upon the assessment of the scientific evidence presented in the marketing application (that may contain preference study results), the neglect of preference heterogeneity and uncertainty about the generalizability of preferences towards the larger European sample currently hampers the use of preference study results for regulatory MA.

It is therefore imperative to better understand and explain preference heterogeneity according to **patient characteristics**. To obtain an in-depth understanding of the impact of patient characteristics on the elicited preferences, a **patient preference study** will be conducted among MM patients, collecting the following information: (i) geographical area, ethnicity and religion to explain preference heterogeneity according to **cultural characteristics**, (ii) age, sex, education, employment to explain preference heterogeneity according to **demographic characteristics**, (iii) time of diagnosis, disease stage, treatment experience to explain preference heterogeneity according to **clinical characteristics** and (iv) health literacy and numeracy to explain preference heterogeneity according to **psychological characteristics**.

The proposed additional PREFER case study adds evidence for PREFER recommendations by (see also 'Describe which PREFER research question(s) will be addressed from prioritized list'):

Comparing Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) and Swing Weighting (SW). The importance of knowing how method selection affects preference study results has been highlighted in WP2 interviews, where stakeholders were concerned about a lack of guidance on method selection and research that validates and compares different preference methods. Developing an evidence-based understanding of how **preference heterogeneity can be explained by patient characteristics**. The importance of knowing about and taking into account preference heterogeneity has been highlighted in literature ^{76, 86, 94} and within PREFER WP2 interviews, where stakeholders reasoned that patient characteristics and their impact on preferences are often unknown to researchers. By administering the survey to MM patients from five European countries that are diverse in geographical location (North, East, South, West and Central Europe) and culture, the proposed study will be equipped to investigate if and how patient characteristics influence preferences.

Research Question(s)

	Clinical	Methodological
Primary Objectives	<p>To identify and quantify patient-relevant benefit-risk attributes of MM treatments including immunotherapies (<i>patient preferences on the attribute-level</i>) Identify: see 'qualitative phase'. Quantify: see 'quantitative phase'.</p> <p>To quantify trade-offs for benefit-risk attributes of MM treatment including immunotherapies (<i>patient preferences on the attribute-level</i>) See 'quantitative phase'</p>	<p>To compare preferences elicited by DCE vs SW (primary research question 2d, category "reliability" in PREFER strategy document) Research question: How do preferences elicited from the same patient population, for the same attributes and levels, compare when elicited by DCE versus SW?</p> <p>To better understand preference heterogeneity (primary research question 11a, categories "reliability" and "generalizability" in PREFER strategy document) Research question: How can preference heterogeneity be</p>

		<p>explained by the following patient characteristics?</p> <p>cultural variables: country, ethnicity, religion</p> <p>demographic variables: age, sex, education, employment,</p> <p>clinical variables: time of diagnosis, disease stage, treatment experience</p> <p>psychological variables: health literacy, health numeracy</p>
Secondary Objectives		<p>To determine and improve patient understanding of the survey questions and software, and the cognitive burden for patients of the survey (primary research question 4a)</p> <p>Research questions: What is the cognitive burden of the survey? How well do patients understand the questions? How well do patients understand the numerical data presented in the survey?</p>
Background and Rationale		
Describe the preference sensitive situation	<p>Factors influencing the value of measuring and using patient preferences for decision-making should inform the decision on whether or not to conduct a preference study for informing decision-making. The following categories of factors suggest patient preferences would be valuable in decision-making in the context of MM ⁹³:</p> <p>Factors related to the characteristics of the patient population (e.g. rarity of the disease, medical need);</p> <p>Factors related to the product characteristics (e.g. clarity of the benefit-risk balance.</p> <p>The proposed patient preference study responds to these categories:</p> <p>MM has been labelled a rare disease and novel medical products for which patient preferences would be quantified in the proposed study therefore can be labelled orphan medical products. Additionally, MM has been labelled an incurable disease and only half of the diagnosed patients live longer than five years under currently available treatments, stressing the unmet medical need for MM treatment³.</p>	

³ See: www.ema.europa.eu/en/news/new-treatment-patients-multiple-myeloma

	<p>The (regulatory) benefit-risk assessment of novel MM treatments such as immunotherapies might be challenging. Among the 18 medical products for MM assessed by the EMA and for which an EPAR is available, two immunotherapies have been “conditionally approved”⁴: ixazomib and daratumumab⁵, and eight are under “additional monitoring”⁶ (see Appendix 6). The conditional MA of daratumabab was switched later on to full MA. In the case of ixazomib, the challenge of the benefit-risk assessment undertaken by the EMA originated from the perceived uncertain benefit of ixazomib combined with its modest risk. The clinical trial data used for this conditional MA decision compared ixazomib with placebo, both of which were administered together with lenalidomide and dexamethasone. The EMA concluded that there was “uncertainty regarding the size of improvement”. The improvement of ixazomib was an increase of 6 months in progression free survival (PFS) in patients treated with ixazomib compared to placebo⁷. The most frequent side-effects (seen in more than 1 in 5 people) in the clinical trial used for conditional MA were: diarrhoea, constipation, thrombocytopenia, neutropenia, peripheral neuropathy, nausea, peripheral oedema, vomiting and nose and throat infection. Similar side effects were however seen when lenalidomide and dexamethasone were used without ixazomib. Ixazomib can also lead to peripheral neuropathy and hepatotoxicity. Within the context of decision-making undertaken by the EMA on ixazomib, data on patient preferences could potentially have assisted the CHMP in interpreting the benefit-risk profile for patients. This is something we want to explore further within the context of this study (see below ‘How the case study supports or informs medical product decision making, regulatory benefit-risk assessment’).</p>
<p>How the case study supports or informs medical product decision making</p>	<p>The proposed preference study aims to inform:</p> <p>Regulatory benefit-risk assessment and marketing authorization of novel therapies such as immunotherapies (primary decision-making context)</p> <p>The current preference study can help regulators understand: (i) what patients find relevant benefits and risks of MM treatments and (ii) patients’ acceptance of the risks of MM treatments. In this way, results from this study may support regulators during regulatory benefit-risk assessment by indicating: (i) whether the novel MM</p>

⁴ Conditional approval means that due to a lack of evidence presented in the market application, EMA decides to authorize the medical product for a year, and re-evaluate the medical product yearly and requests the market applicant to submit new data

⁵ Darzalex was originally given conditional authorisation. As the company then provided the additional information necessary, the authorisation has been switched to full approval. References:

https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/ema_group_types/ema_medicine/field_ema_web_categories%253Aname_field/Human/search_api_aggregation_ema_therapeutic_area_name/Multiple%20Myeloma?sort=field_ema_public_date&order=desc and [EPAR of daratumumab](#)

⁶ Additional monitoring means that following the marketing authorization, the medical product will be monitored even more intensively than other medical products e.g. because of high toxicities observed in the clinical trial

⁷ References: [EPAR of ixazomib](#), “Three new drugs for multiple myeloma”. *The Medical Letter* 2016; 58 (1495):e70-71 and the [BCFI](#), the Belgian annual reference work for general practitioners and pharmacists for indication and background information on medicines

	<p>treatment targets and meets patients’ preferred attributes (i.e. whether the selected clinical trial endpoints were relevant to patients), (ii) whether patients would accept the risks of the novel MM treatment in turn for the benefits it provides. Finally, results from this study may be used to tailor marketing authorization of novel treatments targeting these attributes by identifying subgroups of patients with different preferences based on patients’ characteristics (preference heterogeneity).</p> <p>Health Technology Assessment (HTA) and reimbursement of novel therapies such as immunotherapies (secondary decision-making context)</p> <p>Access to a medical product is mainly related to its coverage (reimbursement) and costs (price). Due to the fact that MM treatments are administered in multiple (e.g. three-) drug combinations, costs for MM treatment can exceed \$150,000 per person per year (in U.S. dollars) and triplet regimens that include carfuzomib or daratumumab can even exceed these costs ⁶⁷.</p> <p>As a basis for advising reimbursement decisions, HTA generally consists of performing a cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) where the costs of the treatment are divided by its effectiveness. The value of the medical product is typically quantified by calculating the quality adjusted life year (QALY) gained with the new treatment and the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER). Although no consensus exists regarding the ICER threshold, the WHO arbitrarily defines 3 times gross domestic product per capita as a reasonable ICER ⁹⁶. The ICER of all new MM treatments is far beyond this level ⁹⁷. This results in that novel MM treatments are often not reimbursement or at a minimal level, stressing the need for “value-based” pricing and reimbursement.</p> <p>The results from the proposed study may be used to inform value-based reimbursement and pricing of novel MM therapies (e.g. immunotherapies) and more specifically to: (i) indicate whether the MM treatment targets (clinical) outcomes that are relevant to patients, (ii) examine the relative benefit-risk trade-off of novel MM treatments targeting the attributes explored in the proposed study ⁸², (iii) indicate the general acceptability of a novel MM treatment to patients ^{68, 98, 99} and (iv) tailor reimbursement decisions for novel MM treatments based upon preference heterogeneity ⁷⁶.</p>
<p>Describe which PREFER research question(s) will be addressed from prioritized list (see green for how this</p>	<p>Primary research question 2d: “How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?”</p> <p>To compare preferences elicited by DCE vs SW, the proposed study will include in the survey (quantitative part) DCE questions and SW questions. Both the SW and DCE questions will be constructed using the same attributes and levels identified through</p>

<p>study will address these questions)</p>	<p>the qualitative phase. Both DCE and SW will generate quantified weights for the attributes. Since the same participants will be filling out these questions, this will allow to investigate whether and how the attribute weights as identified through DCE vs SW differ.</p> <p>Primary research question 11a: “To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with characteristics of patients (treatment experience, region, culture, time of diagnosis)?”</p> <p>The proposed study aims to develop an evidence-based understanding of how preferences may differ according to demographic, clinical, cultural and psychological patient characteristics. To this end, the proposed study will recruit patients with different disease experiences and treatment experiences and from multiple European countries. The survey will include questions asking this information from participants (see also ‘Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools’). In the analysis of the survey results, it will be investigated whether there is a correlation between these participants’ characteristics and preferences. For example, collecting information on patients’ treatment experiences will be enable investigating whether preferences differ among patients in first, second and third line treatment.</p> <p>Primary research question 4a: “Do patients understand the numerical / quantitative information shown in preference surveys?”</p> <p>To understand patient understanding of the survey, the proposed study will include a pilot phase where the survey is administered in an interview-based setting (see ‘quantitative phase’). During the interview, questions will be asked on the understandability of the questions. This information will be used to: (i) improve the survey questions and (ii) describe what was the ‘gap’ between the expert language and the patient language, useful for subsequent patient preference studies.</p>
<p>How the study contributes to the final PREFER recommendations (see Appendix 7 for graphic overview of how this study fits within PREFER)</p>	<p>In the Final Recommendations, the following topics will be addressed (see ‘Scope of Recommendations’):</p> <p>Rationale for performing a preference study</p> <p>The rationale for conducting this MM preference study described above, namely how this preference study aims to inform preference sensitive decisions from the regulatory and HTA perspective will contribute to this part of the recommendations.</p> <p>Overview of methods suitable for particular contexts</p> <p>The methods in this case study (SW, DCE) and their particular context will inform this section. Preference assessment methods and their context were already prioritized in the PREFER</p>

	<p>deliverables 2.4, 2.6, 2.7, and this case study will inform regarding the practical feasibility of DCE and SW. Besides the preference assessment method itself, this preference study will also inform recommendations about: (i) how to improve patient understanding and cognitive burden of the study and ii) how to analyse preference heterogeneity.</p> <p>Considerations for when and how to design patient preference studies</p> <p>This case study will build up experience on how to design and implement a preference study in the context of diseases in which survival and toxicities are of primary consideration. Additionally, this case study will help to formulate recommendations on the utility of measures to explain preference heterogeneity according to health numeracy and literacy. Further, this case study will help to inform recommendations in studies with multinational samples and possible cross-national variation of preferences.</p> <p>Presentation and communication of results of patient preference studies</p> <p>Since the results from this study are extremely suitable to be communicated to patients and in view of the multitude of stakeholders - including industry, regulatory and HTA stakeholders for assessing the relevance of (selected) endpoints - that might benefit from using the results from this study, it is sought to valorize the results from this preference study by engaging with these stakeholders via the organization of a workshop towards the end of the study, bringing together patients and their organizations, regulators other stakeholders to discuss the results the preference study.</p> <p>Patient engagement in preference studies Experience from involving MM patients and a patient organization in the design of this case study (see below) will contribute to this section.</p>
Method/design	
<p>Methods (If DCE is not proposed: clearly explain why)</p>	<p>Qualitative phase and selection of benefit-risk attributes</p> <p>The qualitative phase will consist out of the following sub-phases: (i) individual interviews with MM patients and (ii) a focus group discussion with MM patients using the nominal group technique (NGT).</p> <p>Interviews</p> <p>Semi-structured individual interviews will be conducted with a limited amount (until saturation, maximally 20) of MM patients from the different included countries and aim to identify patient-relevant benefit-risk attributes of MM treatment. The interview guideline will be developed based upon: (i) a literature review of preference studies conducted among MM patients, (ii) a review of clinical trial</p>

databases and endpoints used in MM clinical trials to ensure attributes of future drugs are identified and (iii) a review of the clinical trial endpoints used for MM treatments already assessed by the EMA (see excel table listing clinical evidence per assessed medical product by EMA) (*). The interview guideline will be discussed with regulatory and HTA stakeholders to ensure the interview will capture attributes relevant for their decisions. The conversation with every participant will be voice-recorded and transcribed. Completion of the interview is estimated to take maximally one hour.

Focus group discussion

The interviews will generate a list of attributes for potential inclusion in the quantitative phase. A focus group with patients will be conducted using NGT to prioritize and potentially group these attributes. Following the recommendation by Krueger *et al.*¹⁰⁰, maximally 12 patients will take part.

In order to identify levels for the prioritized list of attributes the same information sources (*) as for the interviews will be used.

Quantitative phase

The quantitative phase aims to: (i) quantify the importance of the attributes identified in the qualitative phase according to patients and (ii) quantify patients' benefit-risk trade-offs for these attributes.

To investigate methodological research question 2d, two methods were selected for the study: DCE and SW. The survey will include both DCE and SW questions that aim to elicit patients' trade-offs for the same attributes and levels. Both DCE and SW questions will generate quantified weights for the attributes. This will allow to investigate potential differences between preferences (attribute weights) elicited using DCE and SW. Both of these methods were identified as promising methods from PREFER task 2.7. Tervonen *et al.*⁵⁹ performed a qualitative comparison of DCE and SW and argue that these two methods are among the most recommended methods for eliciting benefit-risk preference trade-offs; which is one of the clinical aims of the proposed study.

Based upon the "rule of the thumb"⁸ for calculating sample sizes for DCE⁶⁰, the proposed study would need an estimated sample

⁸ Rule of the thumb used: $N > 500c/(t \times a)$. Parameters: number of choice tasks (t), the number of alternatives (a), and the number of analysis cells (c). When considering main effects, 'c' is equal to the largest number of levels for any of the attributes. When considering all two-way interactions, 'c' is equal to the largest product of levels of any two attributes⁶⁰. de Bekker-Grob, E.W., B. Donkers, M.F. Jonker, and E.A. Stolk, *Sample Size Requirements for Discrete-Choice Experiments in Healthcare: a Practical Guide*. Patient, 2015. 8(5): p. 373-84.. For the sample size estimation, the following values were used:

- $t=6$; the number of choice tasks is not yet known, therefore, the number choice tasks from the study by Postmus *et al.* (35) was used
- $a=2$; participants will be asked to choose between 2 alternatives
- $c=5$; the number of levels is not yet known, therefore, the number of levels from the study by Postmus *et al.* (35) was used

	<p>of 208 patients minimally. Although MM has been labelled a rare disease, Postmus <i>et al.</i>¹⁰¹ were able to recruit 560 MM patients in the UK only. The patient organization ‘Myeloma Patients Europe’ helped recruitment in the UK and would also assist us in recruiting patients for our study in the proposed countries. Additionally, we will contact haematologists for helping with patient recruitment. Therefore, it is foreseen that the sample size needed will be obtained.</p> <p>In view of the fact that the PREFER recommendations will contain an overview of methods suitable for particular contexts (see Scope of Recommendations), the proposed study would inform this section of the recommendations, and more specifically best practices on how to design and use DCE and SW to support regulatory BRA and MA (primary decision-making context) and HTA/reimbursement (secondary decision-making context).</p> <p>The final online survey will be translated to the native languages of the participants by a professional translation company to the native language of the participants (see ‘Study population’). Completion of the quantitative survey is estimated to take maximally half an hour. The actual quantitative phase will be preceded by a pilot in which a limited number of patients will be interviewed while filling in the survey. These pilots aim to: (i) understand how long it takes patients to fill in the survey, (ii) verify whether patients understand the questions and subsequently (iii) improve the survey. During and after filling out the survey, patients will be asked to provide oral feedback (in their native language) on the clarity and difficulty of the questions.</p>
<p>Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)</p>	<p>The survey will include numerical and medical information. Therefore, it is relevant to understand whether preferences expressed by patients during the survey, differ according their level of health literacy and numeracy (see below). During the pilot phase, it will be assessed whether the survey is not too long and should this be the case, it will be sought to shorten the survey.</p> <p>Health literacy</p> <p>To investigate whether preferences differ according to health literacy (methodological research question 11a), Chews’ set of brief screening questions (three questions) will be added¹⁰². These three questions have been found effective in detecting inadequate health literacy: "How often do you have someone help you read hospital materials?" "How confident are you filling out medical forms by yourself?" and "How often do you have problems learning</p>

	<p>about your medical condition because of difficulty understanding written information?".</p> <p>Health numeracy To investigate whether preferences differ according to health numeracy (methodological research question 11a), questions probing about patients' familiarity of probabilities and percentages will be added, e.g. the abbreviated numeracy 'Rasch-based' scale, of which its predictive validity has been established by Weller <i>et al.</i>¹⁰³.</p>
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>Inclusion criteria for patients entering both the qualitative pilot as the quantitative phase are: Diagnosed with active (=symptomatic) MM; Understanding of one of the survey languages; Resident in one of the included countries.</p>
Setting (e.g. countries included, location and approach to conducting qualitative study, online or pen/paper survey for quantitative study)	<p>Qualitative phase Interviews MM patients from the different included countries in the quantitative phase: Belgium, Finland, Romania, Spain, the United Kingdom will be interviewed.</p> <p>Focus group discussion The discussion will take place at a location most convenient for the majority of the participants. The group discussion will be conducted in Dutch (Belgium).</p> <p>Further details on the setting of the interviews and group discussion will be provided in the protocol.</p> <p>Quantitative phase An electronic online survey will be used. Patients will be recruited from the following 5 countries: Belgium, Finland, Romania, Spain, the United Kingdom.</p>
Key exclusion criteria	<p>Exclusion criteria for patients entering both the first qualitative phase as the quantitative phase are: Patients with asymptomatic (=non-active or smoldering) MM. These patients do not show symptoms of MM⁹; Patients younger than 18.</p>
Sample requirement and recruitment strategy (total and by country)	<p>Sample size requirement Interviews MM patients (maximally 20) from included countries in the quantitative phase: Belgium, Finland, Germany, Romania, Spain, the United Kingdom. The reason for including these specific countries is that they are diverse in terms of location (North, East,</p>

⁹ People who are diagnosed with asymptomatic MM have higher levels of M protein and more plasma cells in the bone marrow than people with MGUS. However, there is still no evidence of symptoms or signs of myeloma, such as significant bone disease or anaemia (<https://www.cancer.net/cancer-types/multiple-myeloma/stages>)

	<p>West, South and Central Europe) and culture. This will increase the chance that the included patient sample is heterogeneous in terms of patient characteristics, which is crucial since one of the methodological aims is to investigate preference heterogeneity according to patient characteristics.</p> <p>Focus group discussion</p> <p>MM patients (maximally 12) from included countries in the quantitative phase: Belgium, Finland, Germany, Romania, Spain, the United Kingdom.</p> <p>Quantitative phase</p> <p>Based upon the “rule of the thumb”¹⁰ for calculating sample sizes for DCE⁶⁰, the proposed study would need an estimated sample of 208 patients minimally. Postmus <i>et al.</i>¹⁰¹ were able to recruit 560 MM patients in the UK only. The patient organization ‘Myeloma Patients Europe’ (MPE) is the umbrella organisation of myeloma patient groups and associations from across Europe. MPE helped recruitment in the UK and would also assist us in recruiting patients for our study in the UK and the other proposed countries, as they are in contact with the national MM patient organizations. Additionally, we would contact haematologists for helping with patient recruitment. Therefore, it is foreseen that the sample size needed will be obtained. Besides the rule of the thumb, other approaches have been put forward to calculate DCE sample sizes. The exact estimated sample size will be elaborated on in the protocol.</p> <p>Sample size recruitment</p> <p>Myeloma Patients Europe and haematologists will be approached to help patient recruitment. It is sought to contact patients via internet (email and/or social media).</p>
Describe how patients will be included in the design and conduct of the preference study	MM patients will be involved in the choice of attributes, levels and elicitation questions. Patients will be asked for oral feedback on the questionnaire and software during the qualitative phase. Patient organization representatives will be: (i) asked to review and provide input on study materials: the information sheet, informed consent, survey (including explanatory parts) and interview questions of pilot phase, (ii) asked to review and provide input on the results

¹⁰ Rule of the thumb used: $N > 500c/(t \times a)$. Parameters: number of choice tasks (t), the number of alternatives (a), and the number of analysis cells (c). When considering main effects, ‘ c ’ is equal to the largest number of levels for any of the attributes. When considering all two-way interactions, ‘ c ’ is equal to the largest product of levels of any two attributes 60.de Bekker-Grob, E.W., B. Donkers, M.F. Jonker, and E.A. Stolk, Sample Size Requirements for Discrete-Choice Experiments in Healthcare: a Practical Guide. Patient, 2015. 8(5): p. 373-84.. For the sample size estimation, the following values were used:

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- $a=2$; participants will be asked to choose between 2 alternatives
- $c=5$; the number of levels is not yet known, therefore, we used the number of levels from the study by Postmus *et al.* (35)

	and publication coming from this study and (iii) asked to be involved in the organization and conduct of a workshop bringing forward the results of this study to stakeholders (see above).
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Endpoints / attributes and levels</p> <p>The qualitative phase will generate attributes and levels to be included in the quantitative phase. The quantitative phase will generate: (i) weights for the attributes included in the survey and (ii) benefit-risk tradeoffs for these attributes.</p> <p>Description of preference heterogeneity according to patient characteristics</p> <p>It will be sought to describe the correlation between patient characteristics and the elicited preferences.</p>
Deliverable(s) related to this case study	<p>Study protocol of the qualitative phase (including interview guideline, informed consent form)</p> <p>IRB approval of qualitative phase protocol;</p> <p>Qualitative phase results: list of attributes and levels;</p> <p>Study protocol of the quantitative phase (including sample size calculation, statistical analysis plan, survey questions, informed consent form);</p> <p>IRB approval of quantitative phase protocol;</p> <p>Pilot results: final survey</p> <p>Final survey implementation (screenshots of different language versions)</p> <p>Study report</p> <p>Workshop materials: slides and report</p> <p>Conference abstract(s)</p> <p>Peer-reviewed publication(s)</p>
Estimated start of the case study	February 2019
Estimated completion date of the case study	April 2020
Funding sources (list the different sources of funding to pay for the study)	No funding is currently available to perform the proposed study
Key references	<p>Postmus D, Richard S, Bere N, van Valkenhoef G, Galinsky J, Low E, et al. Individual Trade-Offs Between Possible Benefits and Risks of Cancer Treatments: Results from a Stated Preference Study with Patients with Multiple Myeloma. <i>Oncologist</i>. 2017;23(1):44-51.</p> <p>Tervonen T, Gelhorn H, Sri Bhashyam S, Poon JL, Gries KS, Rentz A, et al. MCDA swing weighting and discrete choice experiments for elicitation of patient benefit-risk preferences: a critical</p>

	assessment. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2017;26(12):1483-91. ⁵⁹ Additional references: see 'References'.
Proposal about data-sharing with PREFER (only applicable to industry members)	NA

RA – Uppsala

Disease / Clinical Context:

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory autoimmune disease characterised by painful inflammation of the joints and fatigue. If not successfully controlled RA can lead to joint destruction and loss of function. The disease can have extra-articular manifestations associated with increased mortality ¹⁰⁴. Early treatment is associated with better clinical outcomes (Burmester & Pope, 2017). Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) target inflammation. There are numerous DMARDs available with different modes of action and practical characteristics, such as method of administration, frequency of administration, risk of adverse events or monitoring requirements (Aletaha et al., 2010; ¹⁰⁵.

1st line and 2nd line treatment options

Newly diagnosed RA patients start their treatment with conventional synthetics (csDMARDs) as first-line standard treatment as soon as possible. When standard treatment is not effective or tolerated by patients, treatment is typically changed to biologics (bDMARDs) or JAK-inhibitors (tsDMARDs) targeting specific biological mechanisms associated with the initiation and progression of inflammation. Defining the most suitable treatment pathway for patients with RA in need of changing treatment means to choose from different medical products with different risks of side effects and practical attributes that could have an effect on the patients' quality of life (Smolen et al., 2017). In such situations information about patient preferences is important to inform regulatory decisions relating to approval and post marketing ⁽⁵⁰⁾. Changes from treatment with biologics to JAK-inhibitors or visa-versa may also occur, often due to inefficiency of the first drug or side effects. Information related to the regulatory approval status, side effects, mode of administration and efficacy for bDMARDs and tsDMARDs are summarized in Table 1, below.

Table 1. Information about mode-of-administration, side effects and efficacy of biologics and JAK-inhibitors

	Biologics (bDMARDs)	JAK-inhibitors (tsDMARDs)
Approved by the EMA:	Enbrel (1998), Remicade, MabThera (1998), (1999), Kineret (2002), Humira (2003), Orencia (2007), Cimzia (2009), Simponi (2009), RoActemra (2009), Remsima (2013) and Inflectra (2013).	Tofacitinib (2017) and Olumiant (2017)
Side effects	Undesired effects for biologics can include severe infections, such as lung infections, liver damage, reduced ability to make new blood cells, nausea, pain or swelling at the injection site (EMA, 2019).	The long-term side effects are not clearly defined since the drugs are only tested in a relatively small sample within a short period of time. The undesirable effects seen with Tofacitinib are serious infections such as pneumonia (infection of the lungs), cellulitis (infection of the deep skin tissue), herpes zoster (shingles),

		<p>urinary tract infection, diverticulitis (infection affecting the intestines) and appendicitis (infection of the appendix) as well as opportunistic infections, TB and other infections that can occur in patients with weakened immune systems. The most common reported adverse reactions in the RCTs were headache, upper respiratory tract infections, nasopharyngitis, diarrhoea, nausea and hypertension (https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/xeljanz).</p> <p>For Olumiant, the undesirable effects seen are increased blood cholesterol levels, nose and throat infections and nausea (which may affect 2 or more people in 100). Infections reported with Olumiant treatment also included herpes zoster (shingles) (https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/olumiant).</p>
Administration	Biologics require subcutaneous injection or infusion	JAK-inhibitors can be given orally.
Efficacy	Biologics are effective in reducing RA symptoms, slowing disease progression, improving physical function and quality of life in patients with moderate to severe RA.	<p>Xeljanz: Six studies in over 4,200 patients with rheumatoid arthritis have shown that Xeljanz is effective at reducing joint pain and swelling, improving joint movement and slowing down joint damage (https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/xeljanz).</p>

		<p>Olumiant: Three studies in around 2,500 patients showed that Olumiant improves symptoms, such as tenderness and joint swelling, in patients whose previous DMARDs have not worked well enough. In these studies, Olumiant (alone or with the DMARD methotrexate) resulted in more patients achieving an improvement of 20% or more in a standard symptom score (ACR 20) than comparator medicines and placebo (https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/olumiant).</p>
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Clinical question

The main clinical issue driving this study is, at the point of patients switching from 1st-line treatment (i.e. synthetics) to one of two possible 2nd-line treatments (biologics, JAK-inhibitors) and/or patients already taking one 2nd-line treatment and switching to an alternative 2nd-line treatment (i.e. going from biologic to JAK inhibitor, or going from JAK-inhibitor to biologic), what trade-offs RA patients make between risks and benefits of biologics and JAK-inhibitors and thereby support regulatory decision-making. RA patients’ preferences for changing treatment from conventional synthetics to biologics or JAK-inhibitors or between different biologics and JAK-inhibitors could provide essential information for regulators in the approval and post-authorisation stages when evaluating safety and effectiveness.

Methodological Context:

This preference study is designed to answer both clinical and methodological research questions. The methodological questions are related to the PREFER research questions that were generated within WP2 and prioritized as part of Task 3.2 and included in the PREFER strategy document. We propose to use both qualitative and quantitative research methods that were deemed promising based on the 2.7 report: Focus groups (including Nominal group technique) and a Discrete Choice Experiment.

Research Question(s)

	Clinical	Methodological
Primary Objectives	To elicit RA patients’ preferences (including risk-benefit trade-offs and relative importance of attributes) for biologics and JAK-inhibitors when changing treatment.	To what extent does the application of an educational tool (vs standard written information) influence the accuracy of patients’ preferences as well as the outcomes of a DCE?

Secondary Objectives	To estimate MAR/MAB of RA patients for changing to biologics and JAK-inhibitors To what extent do patient characteristics explain preference heterogeneity amongst RA patients in Sweden?	To what extent do psychological constructs (health literacy and numeracy) provide insight regarding the accuracy and consistency of patients' preferences?
Background and Rationale		
Describe the preference sensitive situation	<p>A decision is preference sensitive when: 1) multiple treatment options exist and there is no option that is clearly superior for all patients, 2) one option is considerably uncertain or variable, 3) and/or patients' views on the most important benefits and risks differ within the patient population or health care professionals ⁽⁵⁰⁾. This study addresses the first and third preference sensitive criteria, as described below.</p> <p>1) Finding a suitable 2nd line treatment for patients with RA is usually done by trial and error, where the patients try different medical products. The treatment needs to be changed if not effective or tolerated by patients. Treatment can be changed from conventional synthetics to biologics or JAK-inhibitors, or between biologics and JAK-inhibitors. This is a situation in which multiple treatment options exist and there is no option that is clearly superior for all patients. Patients with RA are facing several different alternatives (biologics vs. JAK inhibitors). For example, biologics and JAK-inhibitors have different administration methods that may influence the patients' choice.</p> <p>2) Moreover, the RA patient population is a diverse group of patients at different disease stages, ages, different experiences of side effects and the effectiveness of a medical product. In addition, some patients are risk averse and some patients are not. This might lead to heterogeneity in preferences, which needs to be investigated.</p>	
How the case study supports or informs medical product decision making	<p>This study will support regulatory decision making by providing information on how patients with RA value the benefits and risks of biologics and JAK-inhibitors when changing treatment. We will also assess how patient preferences differ within the patient sample (i.e. preference heterogeneity).</p> <p>Patient preference information could provide important additional information in decisions relating to a renewal of an existing JAK-inhibitor or for an approval of a new JAK-inhibitor. Regulatory authorities are becoming increasingly interested in the use of</p>	

	<p>patient preference information to inform decision making. During recent years, both the FDA and the EMA have declared an interest in patient preference information in different projects (⁵⁰; EMA/141854/2014, 2014).</p> <p>Previous studies report that patient preference information has the potential to provide additional and valuable information in regulatory decisions throughout the Medical Product Lifecycle (MPLC). Regulatory decisions that are aligned with patients' preferences would more likely be associated with greater treatment satisfaction, uptake and adherence (Ho et al., 2016). This study will provide patient preference information, that can support evaluation and decision making in the following stages of the regulatory process:</p> <p>Scientific evaluation (pre-submission): In this stage, regulators are evaluating whether the benefits of a particular drug outweigh the harms. In this situation, patients are currently being involved as representatives on decision boards and panels. Patient preference information could provide additional information from the patient perspective. Additionally, insights into Maximum Acceptable Risk levels and preference heterogeneity can be provided. This information is valuable when the benefit-risk profile is uncertain to the regulators, as is currently the case for JAK-inhibitors.</p> <p>Safety monitoring & ongoing benefit-risk assessment (post authorisation): Medical products on the market are closely monitored and there is an ongoing benefit-risk assessment to evaluate side effects not reported in the clinical trials. Patient preference information at this stage could provide information about preferences for side effects that appear when the medical product is tested in an everyday practice. Approvals usually last for five years, during this period the regulators request post-authorisation safety studies and post-authorisation efficacy studies. For a renewal of a drug license, patient preference information could support the efficacy studies by clarifying and updating patients' views on benefits and risks. Efficacy studies are important for complementing available efficacy data, to highlight scientific uncertainties of the evidence on the benefits (https://www.ema.europa.eu/documents/scientific-guideline/scientific-guidance-post-authorisation-efficacy-studies-first-version_en.pdf).</p>
<p>Describe which PREFER research question(s) will be addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>The primary methodological research question is 'to what extent does the application of educational tool (vs standard written information) influence the accuracy of patients' preferences as well as the outcomes of a DCE?' This question addressed the prioritized questions in '1.16 (7d) Does application an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features result in a</p>

	<p>more accurate elicitation of patient preferences, compared with the traditional educational approach? Does the incremental value of applying an educational component with interactive, scenario-based features justify the additional investments needed (budget, other resources) required to create this component? In this study, the educational tool does not qualify as a “full” educational component with interactive and scenario-based features. As described below, the educational tool is simpler without scenarios and choice tasks. On the other hand, it is cheaper and requires less time to develop and less time consuming for the participants. Such a tool may therefore be more feasible option for certain kinds of patient preference studies and maybe also more appropriate for a medical product approval.</p> <p>The secondary methodological research questions is ‘To what extent do psychological constructs (health literacy and numeracy) provide insight regarding the accuracy and consistency of patients’ preferences?’ This question concerns the extent to which results of measurements of psychological constructs may explain differences in preferences between DCE participants. Additionally, these constructs might increase the insights into differences in the accuracy of using either an educational tool or traditional written information among different patients’. The prioritized research questions addressed is ‘1.19, (10b1) Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, and health locus of control) and Class II constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, patient activation, risk propensity) provide insight regarding an individual’s preferences (covariates); i.e., can certain constructs(?) serve as covariates that are predictive of preference for particular diseases? and 1.20 (10b2) Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy and health locus of control) and Class II constructs (self-efficacy, patient activation, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding the patients’ ability to form preferences?’</p>
<p>How the study contributes to the final PREFER recommendations</p>	<p>This study will contribute to the final PREFER recommendations by addressing the following topics that are listed in deliverable 4.1:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Rationale for performing a preference study. This study will provide results from DCE among RA patients in Sweden during the pre- and post-marketing process. This study will inform the recommendations regarding the applicability of a DCE at these decision points in the MPLC. 2) Overview of methods suitable for particular contexts: The method in this study and its’ particular context (RA, a large heterogeneous sample) will inform this section. Specifically this study will provide evidence related to both ‘methods for eliciting or exploring preferences’ and

	<p>'methods to educate patients', since this study uses a DCE in a RA treatment context as well as that is applies different sets of educational material when conducting the DCE.</p> <p>3) Considerations for when and how to design patient preference studies: This study will provide experience on how to design and implement a preference study in the RA disease context, in which preferences of patients are still unknown. Additionally, this study will help to formulate recommendations on the utility of psychological measures (class 1) to explain preference heterogeneity as well as on educational material to accurately train respondents of a DCE.</p> <p>4) Supporting evidence for EMA Methods Qualification: The use of a DCE in this study will add evidence which can be used during the EMA Methods Qualification assessment.</p> <p>5) Presentation and communication of results of patient preference studies: This study will generate results that need to be tailored and presented to different stakeholders (regulators, patients, academics). Representatives of all thee stakeholder groups are included as research partners in this study (from the early beginning onwards), which will provide (and already has provided) valuable lessons learned. In addition, since patient research partners will be part of developing the communication of the results to patients, this study will also provide insights into the procedures and process of including patient research partners throughout the case study.</p> <p>6) Patient engagement in preference studies: Experience from working together with RA patients and RA patient research partners for the design of this study will contribute to this section.</p>
<p>Method/design</p>	
<p>Methods (If DCE is not proposed: clearly explain why)</p>	<p>For development of this study we are using a 2-step approach, 1) qualitative and 2) quantitative. The work was initiated with attribute and level identification for the development of a DCE eliciting RA patients' preferences for biologics and JAK-inhibitors. Secondly, we developed the educational tool to inform participants about the attributes and levels in the DCE.</p> <p>NOTE: the study described in this synopsis is an ongoing study. The qualitative phase is already finalized and the data of the quantitative phase are currently collected. The study was developed and started with particular care to include research questions relevant for PREFER.</p>

Qualitative phase: Attribute and level identification (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Literature overview

Filtering attributes

Validation meetings

Patient ranking

Validation meetings

Attributes and levels in previous studies measuring RA patients' preferences on DMARDs were identified by a literature review. A total of 318 titles were read and 55 abstracts were selected for further review. Finally, 22 papers were selected for a full article review. Out of the 22 articles, 12 were selected for further review. Four additional articles were added to the list after manual searching. The final number of articles included in the analysis of attributes was 16.

A total of 52 potential attributes were identified from the articles. Screening of the attributes was done in a stepwise manner: 1) listing of all attributes (duplicates crossed), 2) grouping attributes into categories by the criteria: plausible, tradable, distinctly different to other attributes and relevant to study objective (Bridges et al., 2011).

Validation meetings with a rheumatologist resulted in selecting 10 attributes to be further discussed in the group discussions. RA patients (n=7) identified the most important attributes in two focus groups using the 'nominal group technique' (NGT). The patient ranking revealed the most important attributes when changing RA treatment.

The results from the focus groups informed validation meetings with one rheumatologist, two RA patient research partners, and the research team. A total of seven attributes with three levels each were identified and refined during several meetings. The final attributes included in the DCE are: how you take the medicine, how often you take the medicine, mild short term side effects, external side effects, psychological side effects, severe side effects and effectiveness (see table in 2 Attributes and levels in section 'Endpoints to be reported' for more details).

In summary, by using a best practice state-of-the art stepwise approach, attributes and levels of this DCE were selected (see table 2) (Bridges et al., 2011). This step-wise approach consisted of: literature review, interviews with experts (rheumatologists and

scientists), NGT with patients, validation meetings with experts (rheumatologists, patient research partners and scientists). After the selection the study was carefully pre-tested (among patient research partners) and pilot-tested (among a convenience sample of the anticipated target population, N=22). Results of those tests were discussed with experts and led to small changes in the formulation of the attributes and levels.

The attributes and levels presented in the DCE is defined to reflect a clinical situation where the characteristics of the medical products is presented to a patient by a rheumatologist. The attributes and levels were cheerfully selected and phrased in collaboration with patients, rheumatologists, regulators and scientists.

The rheumatology group at the Medical Product Agency in Sweden have confirmed the accuracy of the attributes and levels included in the DCE. Regulators cannot be certain of which medical product characteristics would be most important to patients when making a decision. By including the different types of side effects in the DCE (mild short term, external, psychological and severe), regulators will be able to get an overview of how the patients weight the characteristics by the relative importance and if there are heterogeneity within the patient population. Such information could support the regulators in deciding on whether a medical product should be authorised or not.

Quantitative phase: DCE survey

All information gathered in the qualitative stage were used to establish the final list of attributes and levels for the preference elicitation study (DCE) and for the educational tool (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Development of educational tool

The educational tool was developed to inform participants of the questionnaire about the attributes and levels included in the DCE. Once the attributes and levels were identified, an overview of the literature describing DMARDs was made. A first draft was made to

describe RA and all attributes and levels. The draft was reviewed by professionals; rheumatologists and psychologists. Then a meeting with two RA patient research partners took place in order to refine the language to fit the Swedish RA population. A secondary validation meeting with professionals was also scheduled to review the changes made after comments from both patients and professionals. The educational tool was developed together with MindBytes when receiving the revised description of RA and the attributes and levels. The educational tool included two parts, firstly a brief introduction to RA. The introduction was presented with graphics, text and voiceover. The second part described the attributes and levels included in the DCE. This part had a click-on function with graphics and voiceover. The educational tool was piloted together with the DCE.

We designed the content of the educational tool in line with the PREFER EDU-GRID tool. As opposed to a full interactive gamified tool (and therefore very expensive), we opted for something more simple and often more feasible that does improve the written text by means of videos, spoken text and click functions (so respondents can redirect through the information how they see fit). We chose to use a high level of realism and a moderate interactivity level on the basis of the study population. We used facts and figures for informing respondents about RA and the attributes and levels included in the DCE. We used the decision making scenario 'think of your selves in a situation where your treatment is not working, your joints are swollen, you have pain or unbearable side effects'. For the format we used written text, audio/spoken words, photos and illustrations. We used pictographs and icon arrays to describe risks and percentage.

Pilot survey

A pilot survey was developed with a *d*-efficient (Bayesian) design in Ngene software. The pilot DCE included 15 choice tasks and demographic questions. The pilot was tested among RA research partners, RA-instructors, RA patients and general population (n=22) to test and validate the understanding of the information in the educational tool, the DCE and the demographic questions.

For the main survey, we randomised the sample in order to answer the methodological research questions. Participants in the survey will be randomly assigned to written information (currently standard in DCEs) or the educational tool. After that they are randomly allocated to either of the 4 blocks. The blocked design lowers the number of choice tasks for each participant which decreases the burden for the participants and which strengthens the validity of the results.

Figure 3. Research arms

	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px; text-align: center;">Pass in</div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 10px;">Written info</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 10px;">Educational tool</div> </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B1</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B2</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B3</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B4</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B1</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B2</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B3</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 5px;">B4</div> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px 10px; text-align: center;">Demographics</div>
<p>Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)</p>	<p>Psychological instruments: Two different psychological constructs will be measured to potentially explain preference heterogeneity and differences in preference formation; Health Literacy (Wangdahl & Martensson, 2014) and Numeracy¹⁰⁶. We included these constructs because they might explain ‘abnormalities’ in our results since the levels in the DCE involve numbers and risk information, which in general are known to be difficult to interpret and understand. Additionally, the effect of the educational tool on preferences and preference construction might be different for people with different health literacy or numeracy levels</p> <p>Educational tool: For the quantitative phase, we used an educational tool to help patients better understand the attributes and levels included in the DCE. This tool is based on the outcomes of the qualitative phase in order to ensure that all relevant outcomes and attributes are addressed. PREFER partner MindBytes was involved in the development of this educational tool.</p>
Study Population	
<p>Key inclusion criteria</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patients with an established RA diagnosis - Patients between 18-80 years of age - Patients answering to the questions themselves
<p>Setting (e.g. countries included, location and approach to conducting qualitative study, online or pen/paper survey for quantitative study)</p>	<p>For the qualitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patients were recruited via the Swedish Rheumatism association, and the University hospital in Uppsala. - The Nominal Group interviews were conducted at Uppsala University. Interviews lasted for approximately 1,5 hours. - RA patient research partners from the Swedish Rheumatism association contributed in the development of the DCE and the educational tool. <p>For the quantitative phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patients will be recruited via the Swedish Rheumatism association. - Quantitative part: Online patient survey (of approximately 40 minutes)
<p>Key exclusion criteria</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cognitive impairment or inadequate verbal skills that render patients incapable of informed consent - Inability to read study materials

<p>Sample Size requirement and recruitment strategy (total and by country)</p>	<p>- Inability to speak or read language of study materials</p> <p>Qualitative part: The Nominal Group exercise included a total of 6 RA patients.</p> <p>Quantitative part: Minimum N = 600 (300 in the ‘written information group and 300 in the educational tool group), the feasibility of recruitment of patients will be elaborated on in the protocol.</p> <p>Sample-size calculations represent a challenge in DCE experiments. Most published choice experiments have a sample size of 100 to 300 respondents (Marshall et al., 2010). However, minimum sample size depends on several criteria, including the question format, the complexity of the choice task, the desired precision of the results, and the need to conduct subgroup analyses (Louviere et al., 2000; Johnson et al., 2013). A method for computing sample size was proposed by de Bekker-Grob et al (2015), however, as the article points out there is no analytic solution or power calculation that can be used to determine the appropriate sample size for a DCE unless the researcher has enough information to inform the selection of priors.</p> <p>By using a broader generally accepted rule of thumb, sample sizes are deemed sufficient as described below.</p> $Sample\ size > \frac{500l}{TA}$ <p>Sample size depends on the number of choice tasks (T), the number of alternatives in a choice set (A), and largest number of levels in any attribute (l). Our DCE proposes to use 15 choice tasks with 2 alternatives each (excluding the opt-out since patients need to change treatment and do not have the option to opt-out) and a maximum number of levels of about 3. In such a case a DCE needs at least 50 respondents to estimate the main effects. Given the split sample design (i.e., written information and ET), the blocked design (asking people to only complete a subset of the choice tasks, thereby limiting the burden on individual participants) and proposed heterogeneity analysis, we would need a minimum of $50 \times 2 \times 4 = 400$ respondents. According to these calculations a sample size of 600 respondents should be sufficient to answer the proposed research questions and provide enough information to identify preferences in these groups and comparisons across these groups with acceptable precision.</p>
<p>Describe how patients will be included in the design and conduct of the preference study</p>	<p>RA patients, RA patient research partners and RA-instructors were part of developing the whole DCE survey and the educational tool. More specifically, RA patients ranked and discussed the most important attributes to be included in the DCE by using the NTG. RA research partners were part of developing the educational tool and the DCE by participating in validation meetings. The educational tool and the DCE were also pilot tested in ‘think aloud’ interviews with RA research partners and RA-instructors before sending out the pilot survey. The research partners will also be part</p>

	of the analysis and writing of results.										
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)											
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Endpoints / attributes and potential levels</p> <p>Questions regarding the characteristics of RA patients will be reported to describe the study sample. The questions include demographic characteristics, such as; sex, age, educational level, occupational status time since diagnosis, experience with RA treatment and side effects etc. Health literacy and Numeracy will be included as measurements of psychological constructs. Questions regarding the participants' perceived understanding of the information and difficulty of the questionnaire were also included. Table 1 describes the endpoints measured for each objective. A panel Latent Class Analysis is suggested to be conducted on the data that will be gathered.</p> <p>Table 1. Objectives and endpoints.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Objective</th> <th>Endpoint(s)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>To elicit RA patients' preferences (including risk-benefit trade-offs and relative importance of attributes) for biologics and JAK-inhibitors when changing treatment.</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attribute level estimates • Relative importance of the attributes • Trade-offs between benefits and risks • Potential uptake rates </td> </tr> <tr> <td>To estimate MAR/MAB of RA patients for changing to biologics and JAK-inhibitors.</td> <td>Maximum acceptable risk levels and minimum acceptable benefit levels.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>To what extent do patient characteristics explain preference heterogeneity amongst RA patients in Sweden.</td> <td>Heterogeneity will be assessed by class assignment in the latent class analysis.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>To what extent does the application of an educational tool (vs standard written information) influence the accuracy of patients' preferences as well as the outcomes of a DCE?</td> <td> <p>To investigate the accuracy of the preferences retrieved by using either an educational tool or standard written information we will compare:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale & choice consistency • Accuracy measures to indicate internal validity (e.g. dominant decision making)(Janssen et al., 2017). • Time of completion • Drop-out </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Objective	Endpoint(s)	To elicit RA patients' preferences (including risk-benefit trade-offs and relative importance of attributes) for biologics and JAK-inhibitors when changing treatment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attribute level estimates • Relative importance of the attributes • Trade-offs between benefits and risks • Potential uptake rates 	To estimate MAR/MAB of RA patients for changing to biologics and JAK-inhibitors.	Maximum acceptable risk levels and minimum acceptable benefit levels.	To what extent do patient characteristics explain preference heterogeneity amongst RA patients in Sweden.	Heterogeneity will be assessed by class assignment in the latent class analysis.	To what extent does the application of an educational tool (vs standard written information) influence the accuracy of patients' preferences as well as the outcomes of a DCE?	<p>To investigate the accuracy of the preferences retrieved by using either an educational tool or standard written information we will compare:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale & choice consistency • Accuracy measures to indicate internal validity (e.g. dominant decision making)(Janssen et al., 2017). • Time of completion • Drop-out
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived understanding and difficulty of the questionnaire <p>To compare the outcomes of a DCE when using either an educational tool or standard written information, we will compare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attribute levels estimates • Relative importance of the attributes • Trade-offs between benefits and risks • Potential uptake rates
	<p>To what extent do psychological constructs (health literacy and numeracy) provide insight regarding the accuracy and consistency of patients' preferences?</p>	<p>The effect of health literacy and numeracy on preferences and understanding of the survey instrument will be assessed by comparing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses to warm up questions • Scale & choice consistency Survey internal validity checks • Perceived understanding and difficulty of the questionnaire
<p>Table 2. Attributes and levels. Note: this is a highly simplified overview, a more detailed and elaborated overview and training was provided to respondents of the survey to ensure accurate interpretation of the attribute levels as is common practice in DCE studies.</p>		
<p>Attributes Levels</p>		
	<p>How you take the medicine</p>	<p>Tablet (taken orally) Injection (given under the skin, by yourself or someone else)</p>

	<p>Drip (given by a nurse in a day care department)</p> <p>How often you take the medicine</p> <p>Daily Weekly Monthly</p> <p>Mild short term side effects (for example: nausea, vomiting and headache)</p> <p>Common; 1 out of 10 (so out of every 10 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) Uncommon; 1 out of 100 (so out of every 100 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) Rare; 1 out of 1000 (so out of every 1000 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect)</p> <p>External side effects (for example: hair loss, weight gain and rash)</p> <p>Common; 1 out of 10 (so out of every 10 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) Uncommon; 1 out of 100 (so out of every 100 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) Rare; 1 out of 1000 (so out of every 1000 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect)</p> <p>Psychological side effect (for example: anxiety, mood changes, depression and sleep disturbances)</p>
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	<p>Common; 1 out of 10 (so out of every 10 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) Uncommon; 1 out of 100 (so out of every 100 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) Rare; 1 out of 1000 (so out of every 1000 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect)</p> <p>Severe side effects that requires hospitalization (for example: severe infections and allergic reactions)</p> <p>Common; 1 out of 10 (so out of every 10 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect) 1 of 100 gets the side-effect Rare; 1 out of 1000 (so out of every 1000 patients who take the drug, 1 suffers from the side effect)</p> <p>Effectiveness The effectiveness of the treatment is the ability to decrease inflammation and swelling of the joints, also pain and other symptoms.</p> <p>30% Chance of improvement 50% Chance of improvement 70% Chance of improvement</p>
<p>Deliverable(s) related to this case study</p>	<p>Study protocol, statistical analysis plan, study report</p>
<p>Estimated start of the case study</p>	<p>2018-01-01 (ongoing, qualitative study complete)</p>
<p>Estimated completion date of the case study</p>	<p>2020-06-01</p>
<p>Funding sources (list the different sources of funding to pay for the study)</p>	<p>Mind the Risk Staffing costs of participating partners and costs related to the qualitative and quantitative phases are being funded by Mind the Risk.</p> <p>PREFER Costs associated with the educational tool and advertisement is requested to be funded by PREFER because of the</p>

	methodological question 'How does the application of an educational tool (vs standard written information) influence patients understanding in a DCE? ' was added specifically for PREFER.
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Appendix 6: Synopsis of additional industry-led case studies

Chronic pain

Disease / Clinical Context: Chronic Pain
Methodological Context: Discrete Choice Experiment and Best Worst Scaling
Clinical Research Question(s)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Quantify patient preferences for pharmaceutical treatments for chronic moderate-to-severe musculoskeletal pain associated with osteoarthritis (OA) and chronic low back pain (CLBP). 2. Understand patients' preferences for, and potential trade-offs among, treatment attributes that are most relevant to them and that correspond to existing and future treatment options (e.g., nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), opioids, anti-NGF mAbs)
Methodological Research Questions
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. For a sub-group of attributes, do patient preferences differ when assessed in a discrete-choice experiment (DCE) versus a best-worst scaling (BWS) exercise? 2. Does adding a BWS exercise to a DCE provide substantial additional information? Can patients complete both? <p>(Note: Others to be added following discussion with PREFER regarding other PREFER research questions)</p>
Method/design
<p>Online discrete-choice experiment (DCE) survey administered in the United States (US) and the United Kingdom (UK) to patients with moderate-to-severe knee and/or hip OA pain or CLBP who are intolerant to or have failed prior treatment with three classes of pain medication. The online preference-elicitation survey instrument will ask patients to evaluate a series of choices between pairs of hypothetical OA or CLBP treatment alternatives. The survey instrument will be developed following recommendations for good research practices (Lancsar and Louviere, 2008; Bridges et al., 2011; Johnson et al., 2013). Patient-relevant treatment attributes were identified from four qualitative focus groups of patients that were conducted in December, 2017. The survey instrument, which includes the attributes and levels identified in the qualitative work, will be developed in consultation with external clinical consultants. Pretesting of the survey with respondents similar to those who will be taking the final online survey will be conducted to assess respondent comprehension and ensure that the survey will yield high quality data. This study will also include a best-worst scaling (BWS) exercise to capture the relative importance of attributes that were relevant to patients, but that were not included in the DCE. Three attributes from the DCE (risk of having a heart attack, risk of addiction/dependency, and risk of bone and joint problems that are severe enough that you will need a total joint replacement) will also be included in the BWS to create a link between the two preference-elicitation methods (Zhang et al., 2015).</p>
Background and Rationale
<p>Osteoarthritis and chronic low back pain are two of the most common chronic pain conditions worldwide, and both are associated with substantial humanistic and socioeconomic burdens (Bindawas et al., 2015; Farr et al., 2013; Gore et al., 2012; Gore et al., 2011; Ma et al., 2014). Patient preferences for chronic pain treatments for OA and CLBP have only been formally measured in a limited way. Posnett and colleagues (2015) used a discrete-choice experiment</p>

(DCE) to identify preferred attributes of treatments for OA of the knee in five European countries and found that injectable treatments were significantly preferred over oral treatments. Laba and colleagues (2013) used a DCE to estimate the relative importance of seven OA treatment attributes (pain efficacy, mode of action, dose frequency, treatment schedule, side effects, prescription, and out-of-pocket costs) and respondent characteristics on decisions to continue treatments. These authors found that side effects, out-of-pocket costs, mode of action, and treatment schedule had a significant effect on the choice to continue treatment, whereas the other attributes and participant characteristics did not. Hauber and colleagues (2013) used a DCE to estimate the benefit-risk trade-offs that patients in the United Kingdom (UK) were willing to make when considering OA treatments and found that patients were willing to accept significantly greater safety risk in exchange for reductions in ambulatory pain than they were for reductions in resting pain. Arden and colleagues (2013) conducted a DCE similar to that of Hauber and colleagues (2013) and found that physician preferences were similar to patient preferences for OA treatments. More recently, Mühlbacher and colleagues (2015) conducted a DCE in German patients with chronic pain (44% with neuropathic back pain) to identify the key treatment attributes for patients when evaluating and selecting potential pain treatments. These authors found the following treatment attributes relevant to patients in their study (in descending order of importance): no personality change, less nausea and vomiting, pain reduction, rapid effect, low risk of addiction, applicability with comorbidity, and improvement of quality of sleep.

Current pharmacologic therapy for OA and CLBP includes analgesics, such as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and opioids, typically in a step-up approach (McAlindon et al., 2014; Qaseem et al., 2017). Considering the risks associated with the currently available pharmaceutical therapies, the lack of response in roughly 50% of patients (Nagakura, 2017), and for the number of patients with comorbidities who are inappropriate candidates for NSAIDs and/or opioids, there is an unmet need for novel, opioid-sparing medications for the treatment of these chronic pain conditions. In addition, current and potential OA and CLBP treatments differ substantially in benefits, risks, and mode and frequency of administration. Therefore, the choice of treatment for these conditions is preference sensitive.

<p>PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>2d. How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?</p> <p>Linkage: While this study is not conducting the full study using two different methods, there is the opportunity to compare the results for a subset of attributes that appear in both the DCE and BWS exercises (heart attack, addiction/dependency, and joint replacement).</p> <p>9b How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases?</p> <p>Linkage: This study will assessing and comparing preferences for the same attributes between osteoarthritis (OA) and chronic lower back pain (CLBP) patients and compare patient populations in the US and UK.</p> <p>4b1 What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of</p>
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	<p>cognitive tasks?</p> <p>Linkage: Study will include comprehension questions related to attribute definitions, risk comprehension, task completion, literacy, and numeracy.</p> <p>10b3 Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, patient activation, and health locus of control) and Class II constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding preference heterogeneity; i.e., how much of the heterogeneity of preference studies can be explained by different results on particular psychological instruments?</p> <p>10c1 Can these psychological instruments be used to ensure matching of the survey sample to a real-world population?</p> <p>Linkage: We are interested in adding questions like this to our survey instrument to explore both preference heterogeneity and external validity.</p> <p>11a To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with characteristics of patients?</p> <p>Linkage: The study plans to test for subgroup differences in the DCE, keeping in mind limits inherent to our sample size.</p>
<p>How the research questions support or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>The clinical research questions will address whether patients consider the benefit-risk balance of new pain treatments, such as tanezumab, to be favorable to them. This will help inform regulatory decisions on product approval and product labeling. It will also provide valuable information to health care payers who want to determine if newer pain treatments are bringing real incremental value to patients. Finally, data on the preferences of the OA and CLBP patient populations will be valuable to Pfizer decision-making in regards to further development options in chronic pain.</p>
<p>How the study might contribute to the final recommendations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •This study will demonstrate whether preference results for similar, but not identical, patient populations can be assessed in the same study. •Study will also show if linking a DCE and BWS via some common attributes has added value to the final study results. •Study will inform the recommendations regarding the ability of specific psychological instruments to explain preference heterogeneity.
<p>Study Population</p>	
<p>Key inclusion criteria</p>	<p>Patients diagnosed with moderate-to-severe knee and/or hip OA or CLBP who are intolerant to or have failed prior treatment with three</p>

	classes of pain medication.
Key exclusion criteria	Diagnosis of a comorbid chronic pain conditions, such as rheumatoid arthritis or bone cancer.
Sample Size requirement	A sample of 300 respondents in each country (US and UK) is planned, for a total of 600 patients overall. The sample in each country will be evenly split between OA and CLBP patients. In addition, in each country, 150 patients must have tried or still be taking an opioid in the past 2 years and 150 patients must not be currently on or have ever taken an opioid pain medication.
Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	Locus of control is one of interest to us. We plan to decide this based upon discussion with the Task 2.5 leads and the Milan IEO team.
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Survey Variables	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Screening questions 2. Background questions on the respondent's experience with OA or CLBP treatments and, potentially, the patient's disease and treatment history 3. A patient-friendly description of each DCE attribute 4. For each attribute, a question or two designed to encourage the respondent to think about the attribute, to break up the text describing the attributes, and to assess respondents' comprehension of the attribute 5. Practice DCE questions to familiarize respondents with the DCE questions and to assess respondents' comprehension of the DCE questions 6. Discrete-choice experiment questions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attributes: Extent of Pain relief and/or Restoration of Function Cardiovascular side effects Musculoskeletal side effects Risk of Addiction/Dependency Personal Cost to you Mode and frequency of administration Frequency of administration 7. A patient-friendly description of each BWS item 8. Best-worst scaling questions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Items: Risk of moderate-to-severe constipation Risk of mild-to-moderate psychotropic or cognitive side effects Risk of mild-to-moderate nausea and vomiting Risk of having a bleeding ulcer

	<p>Risk of having a tingling or burning sensation in the fingers or toes Risk of mild-to-moderate swelling in the ankles and feet Risk of having a moderate stroke</p> <p><i>Risk of having a heart attack</i> <i>Risk of addiction/dependency</i> <i>Risk of bone and joint problems that are severe enough that you will need a total joint replacement</i></p> <p><i>Note: These attributes appear in both the DCE and BWS portions.</i></p> <p>9. Demographic questions 10. Psychological instruments to measure numeracy, literacy etc.</p>
<p>Deliverable(s) related to this case study</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative Focus Groups Report • Survey Instrument • Study Protocol • Statistical Analysis Plan • Final Study Report • Peer Reviewed Publication

Myocardial infarction

Disease / Clinical Context: Cardiovascular/ Preferences for treatment attributes associated with antithrombotic treatments	
Methodological Context: Comparing patient preferences for those with a recent acute myocardial infarction (MI) and those at a more chronic stage of disease	
Research Question(s)	
Primary Objectives	To compare preferences for antithrombotic treatment attributes of acute and chronic MI patients, with acute MI patients defined as those with their most recent MI within the year (≤ 365 days) prior to study enrollment and chronic MI patients defined as those enrolled more than one year (> 365 days) after experiencing their most recent MI.
Secondary Objectives	To assess preference heterogeneity in other relevant subgroups (e.g., those at greater probability of future events and those with family or close friends having experienced a prior atherothrombotic event).
Exploratory Objective	To assess whether there are differences in preferences when elicited with a discrete choice experiment (DCE) on probabilistic outcomes, compared to a case 1 best-worst scaling (BWS) exercise with the same but deterministic outcomes.
Method/design	
Methods	This is a three-phase preference study: (i) qualitative pilot; (ii) quantitative pilot; and (iii) main survey. The primary preference-elicitation instrument is a discrete choice experiment (DCE), which is complemented by a best-worst scaling (BWS) instrument. The survey was designed using the d_p -optimal method, which takes into account prior information on utilities of attribute-level differences. Descriptive statistics will be developed for patient demographic information and clinical characteristics. Econometric modeling will be used for discrete choice data; random parameter, latent class, multinomial logit, and heteroscedastic logit models will be fit, and model selection will be based on information measures and expert judgment. BWS results will be analyzed using the logit model.
Background and Rationale	
PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from prioritized list)	<p>How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Addressed by exploratory objective</i> <p>How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Addressed by exploratory objective</i> <p>To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with characteristics of patients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Addressed by secondary objective</i> <p>To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with longitudinal sampling: General population, treatment naïve, shortly after treatment, after chronic treatment, etc.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Although we are not longitudinally studying the same patients, we are assessing preferences at two different stages of disease within the same UK MI population and applying a common study protocol</i>
<p>How the research questions support or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>Past studies have assessed patient preferences for antithrombotic treatments in the secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease in terms of their benefit and risk characteristics, such as reduction of mortality probability and increases in the probability of non-fatal bleedings. These preferences may differ based on patient characteristics. Currently, no data exists on how patient preferences differ based on disease stage (acute or chronic), and little is known regarding other clinical and demographic factors that may cause preference heterogeneity among patients who have previously experienced a myocardial infarction (MI).</p> <p>Understanding preference heterogeneity by disease stage is of particular relevance for this therapeutic area as cardiovascular drugs are investigated and approved for initial administration at different stages of the disease process, with increased probability of future events increasing dramatically within the first several months of the acute event and plateauing in more chronic phases. Knowledge of whether acute and chronic patients have different preferences (i.e., willingness to accept higher probability of side effects in exchange for higher efficacy) could inform decision-making by regulators, payers, and at point of care; it would allow for a patient-centered assessment of which treatment options may be more suitable (i.e., have a more favorable benefit-risk profiles) in these two phases of disease. The main objective of this study is to assess whether patient preferences for clinical treatment characteristics vary between patients with acute and chronic MI, and to consider the implications of performing B-R assessments for drug development programs.</p> <p>In addition to the applied research goals described above, this study has an exploratory goal of comparing how two different elicitation instruments might produce different results. In addition to response mode, only one of the instruments (discrete choice experiment) captures the patient's attitude towards negative events, whereas the second one (case 1 best-worst scaling) will address patient valuation of clinical events under certainty. Economic theory has long distinguished decisions under certainty from those on risky outcomes; there is a body of evidence on how the subjective assessment of probabilities is prone to behavioral phenomena, such as over-emphasizing small probabilities, which causes standard utility theory to be an invalid description of preferences. However, the differences in preferences for risky and deterministic outcomes have rarely been addressed in patient-preference research. The results may inform survey design for future studies.</p>
<p>How the study might</p>	<p>The study addresses a number of the research questions for</p>

contribute to the final recommendations	PREFER and the results may further inform development of the final recommendations.
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	<p>Patients must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 18 years of age • Previously hospitalized with an MI <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Post-MI up to one year (acute MI group) ○ Post-MI for more than one year (chronic MI group) • Able to read and understand English • Willing and able to complete an online survey • Willing and able to provide (electronic) consent to participate in study • Resident of England • Qualitative pilot only: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Be willing and able to participate in a telephone interview, and to be audio-recorded
Key exclusion criteria	<p>Patients will be excluded if they:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a cognitive impairment, hearing difficulty, visual impairment, acute psychopathology, or insufficient knowledge of English that—in the opinion of the investigator/interviewer—could interfere with a patient's ability to provide written consent and complete an interview or survey. • Are pharmaceutical employees and those employed in a position where they have a direct role in treating patients with an MI
Sample Size requirement (total and by country)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative Pilot: n=5 (participants with chronic MI) • Quantitative Pilot: n=40 (participants with chronic MI) • Main Survey: n=380 (200 acute MI patients, and 180 chronic MI patients recruited from UK National Health Service (NHS) clinical sites.
Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health literacy and numeracy assessment • Traditional educational approach (printed materials)
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endpoints / attributes and potential levels: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Probability of CV death <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Levels: 1%, 5%, 10%, 16% 2. Probability of non-fatal heart attack <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Levels: 8%, 11%, 14%, 18% 3. Probability of non-fatal stroke <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Levels: 0%, 2% 4. Probability of non-fatal bleeding within the skull

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Levels: 0%, 3% <p>5. Probability of other non-fatal severe bleeding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Levels: 0%, 3% • Patient characteristics: A summary of demographic and baseline characteristics (e.g.medical history) will be provided. • Potential results: We hypothesize that disease chronicity affects a patient’s tolerance for an increased probability of adverse events (i.e., that a patient’s willingness to accept an increased probability of bleeding events in exchange for a decreased probability of stroke and MI differs between acute and chronic stages of disease), and chronic patients are likely to tolerate a lower probability for adverse events for larger treatment benefit. <p>In addition, we hypothesize that the two methods, BWS and DCE, which elicit preferences for deterministic and probabilistic events, will produce different preferences after the DCE results have been scaled to equal ranges per event (i.e. to correspond to the events occurring deterministically). Standard economic theory suggests that risk preferences are often non-linear, but we might not be able to establish non-linear shape of the preferences with the variation in attribute ranges and the sample size of this study.</p>
Deliverable(s) related to this case study	Study protocol (inclusive of statistical analysis plan), study report. The MSD study team plans share the preliminary results at the end of the study with the PREFER protocol review team (PRT) for additional input and discussion prior to finalizing the study report.
Estimated time to completion of the case study	1-2Q2019

COPD

Disease / Clinical Context: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)
Methodological Context: Discrete Choice Experiment
Clinical Research Questions
<p>Study aim: To quantify the preferences of COPD patients regarding symptoms, the impact on their QOL, and evaluate whether preferences vary with certain respondent characteristics.</p> <p>Primary objective*: The level of importance which COPD patients place on symptoms such as cough and mucus secretion and consequences thereof, versus more traditional endpoints such as breathlessness and exacerbations.</p> <p>*during the conduct of the study the overall strategy changed and therefore the analysis plan was adapted to analyze preference for improvement of excess mucus production, (chronic) cough and shortness of breath in addition to downstream impacts on sleep, physical activity, and as urinary leakage compared to improvement of exacerbations alone.</p> <p>Secondary objective: To provide predicted choice probabilities on trade-offs COPD patients are willing to make to achieve desired COPD disease states.</p> <p>Exploratory objectives: To assess how stated preferences may vary according to patient symptomatic burden and disease severity; socio-demographic characteristics and the level of patient 'activation'.</p>
Methodological Research Questions
<p>PREFER methodological research questions addressed through this case study are listed in a subsequent section below</p> <p>Additional methodological questions which were addressed through this COPD case study included:</p> <p>Timing in the medical product lifecycle: conduct of a study during phase 1 of the product development, with a focus on disease features only, to help inform the future clinical development program</p> <p>The value of insights from online qualitative studies (social media, online bulletin boards) to inform the design, attributes and levels of the patient preference study</p> <p>The value of scientific advice from an HTA body during the design phase of the quantitative project (the first time this had been done for a patient preference study)</p> <p>The attributes of the discrete choice experiment focused only on disease symptoms (i.e. a drug-agnostic DCE design) as a means to inform patient-relevant clinical endpoints</p> <p>The use of supplementary disease-specific Patient Reported Outcome instruments in the online survey to allow a broader clinical profiling of study participants and enable us to explore subgroup response heterogeneity</p> <p>Use of an instrument to measure patient activation, to see if this had an impact upon preferences expressed by the patients</p> <p>The derivation of health state utilities from the (disease-specific) preference data, allowing us to compare these disease-specific utility values with those obtained through the generic instrument, EQ-5D</p> <p>The engagement and collaboration between industry and patient groups in 5 countries to design and conduct a multi-country patient preference study</p>
Method / Study Design
<p>The study design is illustrated by the graphic below. Key steps were</p> <p>Literature review, social media listening and online bulletin board with COPD patients, to understand COPD symptoms that mattered most to them, allowing the construction of a draft attribute & levels grid for the DCE</p>

Input from the steering committee consisting of medical experts and COPD patient groups in the countries where the study was to be conducted

Analysis of PRO instruments (both COPD-specific and generic) to be used as part of the online survey alongside the DCE to enable further clinical profiling of the respondents and explore subgroup heterogeneity of results

Input in the form of scientific advice from the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE), England, to the study design, instruments to be used and analysis plan

Following IRB review, refinement of the wording, survey design, conceptual relevance and attribute & levels grid through qualitative telephone interviews with patients in each country

Finalisation of the survey design and programming for online administration of survey; soft launch to check everything working as anticipated

Full survey launch in all countries, data collection and analysis

Development of a simulation model based upon the preference data, to allow modelling of different patient health states and understand the impact on predicted preference share

Background and Rationale

Clinical background and context:

The measurement of lung function (FEV1) and exacerbations are traditional measures in clinical trial of COPD. With the exception of shortness of breath, the measurement of daily symptoms is much less established. However, previous research evaluating patient perspectives in COPD has shown that besides breathlessness and exacerbations, persistent cough and mucus production (frequently occurring together), as well as downstream consequences of these, sleep disturbance, physical activity and urinary incontinence (as a consequence of the cough) are also of great concern for patients, imposing a substantial burden on their lives.

Chronic cough and mucus production are associated with disease progression and exacerbation, and hence the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD)

	<p>has recently included symptomatic assessment into its COPD classification system, with COPD treatment management to include symptom assessment beyond dyspnoea and exacerbation. Understanding patient needs and expectations related to disease and treatments are essential to ensure that drug development is addressing what matters to the patient. Therefore, the development and selection of endpoints in COPD clinical trials should be informed and driven by findings from methodologically robust and rigorous qualitative and quantitative patient research exploring what is important to them.</p> <p>With the present patient preference study, we sought to quantify the relative importance that patients place on alleviation of excess mucus production, (chronic) cough and shortness of breath in addition to downstream impacts on sleep disturbance and urinary incontinence, as well as reducing exacerbations</p>
<p>PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>4b1-What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?</p> <p>10b1-Can psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs and Class II constructs provide insight regarding an individual's preferences?</p> <p>10c2 - Help to show external validity, particularly in conjunction with PRO or related instruments specific to the disease area?</p> <p>11-To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Characteristics of patients, Stakeholder, (11d) Disease experience or severity, Treatment experience, (11f) Region, (11g) Culture, Healthy vs heaving disease, Time of diagnosis, Longitudinal sampling, Patients recruited through different channels?</p> <p>15b1 - Should the attributes in preference studies aiming to inform MA/payer/industry decisions relate to benefits/risks or also to broader aspects related to quality of life/disease/...?</p> <p>15b2 - What is the impact of including attributes related to the disease/quality of life/price/... on the preferences elicited?</p> <p>15b3 - When in the drug development process should preferences be measured for informing MA/payer/industry decisions?</p> <p>15c2 - When along the MPLC should a patient preference study be conducted to inform regulators or HTA?</p> <p>17a - What is the optimal approach towards recruitment of participants? What incentives are needed to recruit patients into preference studies?</p>
<p>How the research questions support or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>The study showed the importance of starting early in the product lifecycle (phase 1), so that the results are available in time to inform the design of phase III clinical trials.</p> <p>A product-agnostic DCE design with focus exclusively on different symptoms of the disease that matter most to patients, proved very amenable to identify the patient-relevant clinical endpoints and quantify their relative importance.</p> <p>The results inform both our own phase III program in COPD and have also been input to a separate, multi-stakeholder project to develop a Core Outcome Set for COPD (CoreCOPD).</p> <p>The preference study results, showing importance patients place upon the six COPD symptoms studied, can be used by regulatory</p>

	and HTA/reimbursement agencies to weight the results of future clinical trials in COPD, to better understand the value afforded the patient by new therapeutic offerings.
How the study might contribute to the final recommendations	<p>The COPD study contributes to final PREFER recommendations in regard to:</p> <p>When in the product lifecycle to conduct a preference study</p> <p>Use of a symptom-based design to inform clinical endpoint selection</p> <p>The value of external stakeholder scientific advice during the design of the study</p> <p>Exploring and understanding preference heterogeneity (including across different disease severities and by country)</p> <p>How to derive disease-specific utility estimates from the preference data</p>
Study Population	
Key inclusion criteria	For the full quantitative survey, patients were included in the study if they were aged ≥ 40 years at the time of survey with diagnosis of COPD by a healthcare practitioner, had self-reported moderate-to-severe COPD defined as having had ≥ 1 COPD flare-up/exacerbation in the last year (requiring additional treatment with oral corticosteroids and/or antibiotics to manage their chest symptoms, or had to visit the hospital/emergency room due to COPD) along with daily symptoms of cough and excess mucus production. Patients were excluded if they had participated in a COPD patient survey in the past 3 months.
Key exclusion criteria	Patients were excluded if they had participated in a COPD patient survey in the past 3 months.
Sample Size requirement (total and by country)	<p>Primary recruitment for the full survey was conducted via patient support groups and participation was voluntary. Patient groups in the UK, USA, France, and Australia leveraged their patient's network for the patient recruitment. Supplementary recruitment via patient panels was introduced once patient group recruitment was saturated, with participation compensated at fair market value to encourage patient involvement. In Japan, patients were recruited only through patient panels.</p> <p>A specified minimum of 120 patients from each country was required for the design, meeting statistical properties of balance and orthogonality of the DCE. This proposed sample size is based on simulations of the design efficiencies within the lighthouse studio software. The target sample counts for each country had a minimum of 150, however, since recruitment in Japan was considered to be potentially challenging, a lower estimate of 120 was used to inform the DCE design. With 11 tasks, an N of 120 allows for a balanced design, with all countries using the same design parameters for consistency, despite the differing sizes.</p> <p>In total, 1050 patients (USA [n=400], UK [n=200], France [n=150], Australia [n=150] and Japan [n=150]) completed the final survey,</p>

<p>Accompanying psychological instruments, and other PRO instruments in the online survey</p>	<p>Patient Activation Measure Questionnaire (PAM-Q®, from Insignia Health) COPD assessment test (CAT) Cough And Sputum Assessment Questionnaire (CASA-Q) EuroQOL EQ-5D (3L) general quality of life questionnaire and Visual Analog Scale (VAS)</p>																							
<p>Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)</p>																								
<p>Study Variables and Endpoints to be reported</p>	<p>Demographics and clinical characteristics collected: Age Gender Country Educational level Employment status Smoking status Height, weight (= BMI) COPD diagnosis Comorbidities Allergies, asthma status Daily cough & mucus symptoms Exacerbations and flare-ups in last 12 months Self-reported COPD status Incontinence status</p> <p>Final attributes and levels grid:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="480 1234 1366 1977"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="480 1234 647 1294">Attribute</th> <th data-bbox="647 1234 818 1294">Level 1</th> <th data-bbox="818 1234 1023 1294">Level 2</th> <th data-bbox="1023 1234 1203 1294">Level 3</th> <th data-bbox="1203 1234 1366 1294">Level 4</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="480 1294 647 1563"> Shortness of breath "During a typical day..." </td> <td data-bbox="647 1294 818 1563"> Shortness of breath experienced during strenuous activity (e.g., walking uphill/upstairs) </td> <td data-bbox="818 1294 1023 1563"> Shortness of breath experienced during light activity (e.g., a short walk on level ground) </td> <td data-bbox="1023 1294 1203 1563"> Shortness of breath experienced when washing or dressing (e.g., taking a shower) or dressing </td> <td data-bbox="1203 1294 1366 1563"> Shortness of breath experienced at rest (e.g., when sitting or lying down) </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="480 1563 647 1760"> Cough "During a typical day..." </td> <td data-bbox="647 1563 818 1760"> Cough does not interrupt/disturb any usual activities </td> <td data-bbox="818 1563 1023 1760"> Cough interrupts/disturbs some usual activities </td> <td data-bbox="1023 1563 1203 1760"> Cough interrupts/disturbs most usual activities </td> <td data-bbox="1203 1563 1366 1760"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="480 1760 647 1977"> Urine leakage "During a typical day..." </td> <td data-bbox="647 1760 818 1977"> COPD symptoms do not cause any urine leakage </td> <td data-bbox="818 1760 1023 1977"> COPD symptoms are causing a few drops of urine leakage </td> <td data-bbox="1023 1760 1203 1977"> COPD symptoms are causing urine leakage which makes underwear wet </td> <td data-bbox="1203 1760 1366 1977"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Attribute	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Shortness of breath "During a typical day..."	Shortness of breath experienced during strenuous activity (e.g., walking uphill/upstairs)	Shortness of breath experienced during light activity (e.g., a short walk on level ground)	Shortness of breath experienced when washing or dressing (e.g., taking a shower) or dressing	Shortness of breath experienced at rest (e.g., when sitting or lying down)	Cough "During a typical day..."	Cough does not interrupt/disturb any usual activities	Cough interrupts/disturbs some usual activities	Cough interrupts/disturbs most usual activities		Urine leakage "During a typical day..."	COPD symptoms do not cause any urine leakage	COPD symptoms are causing a few drops of urine leakage	COPD symptoms are causing urine leakage which makes underwear wet	
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	<p>Mucus production “When waking up on a typical morning...”</p>	<p>It is not at all difficult to bring up mucus</p>	<p>It is a little difficult to bring up mucus</p>	<p>It is very difficult to bring up mucus</p>	
	<p>Feeling rested “When waking up on a typical morning...”</p>	<p>Feel rested</p>	<p>Feel somewhat rested</p>	<p>Do not feel rested at all</p>	
	<p>COPD flare-ups/exacerbations “During a typical year...”</p>	<p>Never experience any COPD flare-ups/exacerbations</p>	<p>Experience one or more COPD flare-ups/exacerbations that require antibiotics or steroids</p>	<p>Experience one or more COPD flare-ups/exacerbations that require a hospital stay or visit</p>	
<p>COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease</p>					
<p>Further clinical profiling using the CAT and CASA-Q PRO instruments Attitudinal profiling using PAM-Q instrument General health related quality of life profiling with EQ 5D and VAS Completion of Patient Survey Experience questions</p>					
<p>Deliverable(s) and manuscripts related to this case study</p>	<p>Study protocol, including screener and final questionnaire Statistical analysis plan Study report Published manuscripts: Cook NS, Kostikas K, Gruenberger J-B, Shah B, Pathak P, Kaur VP, Mudumby A, Sharma R, Gutzwiller FS. Patients' perspectives on COPD: findings from a social media listening study. 2019: 5(1): 00128-02018 Cook N, Gey J, Oezel B, J Mackay A, Kumari C, Preet Kaur V, Larkin N, Harte J, Vergara-Muro S, Gutzwiller F. Impact of cough and mucus on COPD patients: primary insights from an exploratory study with an Online Patient Community. International Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease 2019: Volume 14: 1365-1376. Patalano F, Gutzwiller FS, Shah B, Kumari C, Cook NS. Gathering Structured Patient Insight to Drive the PRO Strategy in COPD: Patient-Centric Drug Development from Theory to Practice. Advances in Therapy 2020: 37(1): 17-26. Cook NS, Cave J, Holtorf A-P. Patient Preference Studies During Early Drug Development: Aligning Stakeholders to Ensure Development Plans Meet Patient Needs. Frontiers in Medicine 2019: 6(82).</p>				

	<p>Manuscripts in preparation:</p> <p>Cook NS, Criner GJ, Burgel P-R, Mycock K, Gardner T, Mellor P, Hallworth P, Sully K, Tatlock S, Klein B, Jones B, Le Rouzic O, Adams K, O'Brien M, Phillips K, McKeivitt M, Toyama K, Gutzwiller FS. People living with Moderate-to-Severe COPD Prefer Improvement of Daily Symptoms Over the Improvement of Exacerbations: A Multi-Country Patient Preference Study, ERJ Open Research (submitted).</p> <p>Jones B, Ryan M, Cook N, Gutzwiler F. What do patients value? Developing a preference based utility score for Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. In preparation for Value in Health.</p>
<p>Estimated time to completion of the case study</p>	<p>Case study was completed (including analysis by June 2020), with further analysis and manuscripts being finalised in 4Q 2021</p>

Haemophilia

Disease / Clinical Context

People with haemophilia (PWH) experience various degrees of bleeding, depending on residual coagulation factor levels.¹ Bleeding occurs most commonly in joints, soft tissue, and muscles, causing short-term symptoms (acute bleeding, acute pain) and long-term complications (chronic pain, haemophilia arthropathy, or disability).² Acute and chronic complications may dramatically reduce health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of PWH.³⁻⁵

Haemophilia is managed either by maintaining a routine of prophylactic infusions of the missing clotting factor (Factor VIII or Factor IX), or treatment with on-demand infusions at the time of a bleed. The goal of disease management is to control the frequency and severity of bleeds and prevent joint damage and other complications associated with bleeding episodes. Recent gene therapy trials in both haemophilia A and B have reported promising results which demonstrate that gene therapy could yield a long-term functional “cure” by changing or replacing the missing/abnormal genes.

A “cure” may be derived from a permanent correction of the underlying genetic defect or through prevention of all complications of living with the disorder; a functional cure eliminates the day-to-day burden, though the underlying genetic disease remains.⁶ This would enable the body to produce the previously-missing clotting factor without/with a much-reduced need for, factor replacement therapy. Gene therapy could be life-changing for PWH, relieving them of daily burden and limitations they currently experience.⁷ Currently, phase 3 trials of gene therapy are beginning with a product in haemophilia A recently being submitted to the marketing authorization application to the European Medicines Agency (EMA), however more research is needed to understand the preferences of PWH.⁸ These novel therapies have the potential to change the landscape of haemophilia management.

There are several studies which have explored preferences of PWH for different haemophilia treatments through conjoint analysis, for physician preferences,⁹⁻¹² pharmacist preferences,^{11,12} and patient preferences.¹¹⁻¹⁵ However, these studies have not examined preferences as gene therapy becomes available. Therefore, this study aims to assess how people with moderate or severe haemophilia (A and B) value different features of treatment when considering whether to undergo gene therapy.

Methodological Context

HCD Economics response:

HCD Economics independently developed a proposal to conduct this study. This study has been funded by Pfizer UK. HCD Economics were asked by Pfizer UK if they would be willing to contribute to the PREFER IMI project as part of this project and HCD Economics have agreed. HCD Economics recognise that this research may offer a useful case study as there is a paucity of research which have examined preferences for gene therapies using a preference study design (discrete choice experiment).

HCD Economics are collaborating with the research team from KUL-PREFER who are also undertaking the PAVING study in Belgium. As with the PAVING study, relevant concerns to be addressed from PREFER WP2 with this case study (see also section “Describe which PREFER research question(s)”) include:

*How patient preference studies can be conducted in small patient populations (rare diseases)
How patient preference studies can be designed to be informative for HTA and reimbursement decisions*

Research Question(s)		
	Clinical	Methodological
Primary Objectives	<p>To identify the outcomes and attributes of gene therapy and prophylaxis that are important to PWH, and that will influence their choice</p> <p>To define the relative importance and the value for PWH of therapy characteristics (e.g. differences in the frequency and modality of therapy).</p>	To investigate differences in preferences with varying levels of disease severity (11d)
Secondary Objectives	<p>To examine how PWH trade-off between treatment attributes.</p> <p>To identify predictors that may explain differential preferences for treatment attributes and/or levels.</p>	<p>To investigate how to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/tailored to HTA/payer decision making (15b) – as discussed in the PREFER strategy document (Chapter 4 “Further PREFER strategy and tactics”), PREFER would also like to investigate how patient preferences can be used in decision making</p> <p>To understand how patient preference studies can be conducted in rare diseases – a question specifically raised in the PREFER strategy document (“Chapter 4 Further PREFER strategy and tactics”)</p>
Method/design		
Methods	<p>Qualitative Methods</p> <p>First, a targeted literature review will examine previous relevant studies to generate a list of top-down attributes and levels. Following this, a group of clinical experts (n=8) (including haematologists, nurse specialists, a haemophilia psychology specialist and physiotherapists) and patient advocates (n=10) will be invited to participate in semi-structured interviews to inform to attribute and level development. The interview guide developed during the PAVING study will be used (with minor adaptations to fit the UK context) in interviews with patients to first educate interviewees on gene therapy and to then explore their opinions in-depth. Semi-structured interviews with these stakeholders will result in the identification of attributes and levels bottom-up. In addition, interviewees will be asked to rank top-down as well as bottom-up identified attributes. The interviews will be completed by the majority of the stakeholders first, with the remaining being used to validate</p>	

	<p>the results. The interviews will be transcribed and using framework method a systematic and flexible approach will be used to analyse the qualitative data and provide refined results. Following this the suggested attributes and levels will be validated with the remaining group of stakeholders.</p> <p>Quantitative Methods</p> <p>A discrete choice experiment (DCE) will be conducted alongside a patient survey on demographic and clinical outcomes. DCE scenarios will be created and an orthogonal design will be chosen to define the number of scenarios to include in the study. The sample size requirements will be adjusted dependent on the number of attributes and levels selected. A pilot study will be conducted and the DCE design will be amended to meet any changes required. The DCE will be translated to an electronic format that will then be administered to PWH online. Prior to participation in the DCE survey, respondents will be required to read a participant information sheet and provide informed consent form (online).</p>
Accompanying psychological instruments, educational tools (where applicable)	Psychological instruments: health literacy (Chew et al. 2008). ¹⁶
Background and Rationale	
<p>PREFER Question(s) Addressed (from prioritized list)</p>	<p>PREFER research questions</p> <p>The different PREFER research questions that will be investigated in this study and the way in which they will be addressed are presented below.</p> <p>Examining how similar the results are of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (2d1)</p> <p>Results of this study (DCE) will be compared with the PAVING study (threshold technique)</p> <p>Examines how generalizable preferences are from one disease to related diseases (9b)</p> <p>Responses between haemophilia A and B will be compared</p> <p>Responses between the Belgian population in the PAVING study and the UK population in the current study will be compared</p> <p>Examines to what degree preferences vary with stakeholder perspective: patient vs caregiver (11b)</p> <p>Although not directly exploring the above research question, in the qualitative research, the responses for choice of attributes will be compared between PWH and clinical experts.</p> <p>Examines to what degree preferences vary with disease experience or severity (11d)</p> <p>In subgroup analysis of the quantitative phase, preferences will be compared by disease experience or severity</p>

	<p>Patients recruited through different channels (11k) In the PAVING study, participants are recruited in the clinical setting and through patient organisations. In the HAEM study, participants will be recruited via a patient organisation. The studies may be compared to explore participant recruitment approaches and participation.</p>																								
<p>How the case study supports or inform medical product decision making</p>	<p>PREFER recommendations This study will be of added value to the PREFER recommendations as it 1) meets the PREFER strategy in investigating how qualitative and quantitative patient preference studies can be conducted in the context of rare diseases and how these studies can inform HTA and reimbursement decisions and 2) can provide insights on how patient preference studies should be designed to inform future decision making for very innovative (advanced) therapies. Table 1 demonstrates the added value of the HAEM study compared to the PAVING for PREFER.</p> <p>This study can together with the other WP3 case studies contribute to the following topics of the recommendations (topics cited from ‘Scope of Recommendations’):</p> <p>Rationale for conducting/using patient preference studies: This study will contribute to showing what the value of patient preferences can be in patient preference sensitive situations.</p> <p>Considerations for when and how to design patient preference studies: This study will investigate how to design patient preference studies in rare diseases aiming to inform HTA bodies or payers. The question of how to conduct patient preference studies in rare diseases was specifically raised in the PREFER strategy document (“Chapter 4 Further PREFER strategy and tactics”)</p> <p>Involvement of patients in patient preference studies: This study could be a great example of how patients can contribute to patient preference studies as we will collaborate throughout the design, conduct and interpretation with multiple stakeholders and patient organizations including the UK Haemophilia Society via regular expert reference group meetings.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="376 1579 1367 2085"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2" data-bbox="376 1579 1098 1659">Study features</th> <th data-bbox="1104 1579 1251 1659">PAVING study</th> <th data-bbox="1257 1579 1367 1659">HAEM study</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="376 1668 459 1809" rowspan="2">PREFER strategy</td> <td data-bbox="466 1668 1098 1727">Examines a rare disease</td> <td data-bbox="1104 1668 1251 1727">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1257 1668 1367 1727">✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="466 1736 1098 1809">Is primarily conducted to inform HTA/reimbursement</td> <td data-bbox="1104 1736 1251 1809">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1257 1736 1367 1809">✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="376 1818 459 1951">Future decisions</td> <td data-bbox="466 1818 1098 1951">Examines preferences regarding an advanced therapy</td> <td data-bbox="1104 1818 1251 1951">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1257 1818 1367 1951">✓</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="376 1960 459 2085" rowspan="2">Methods</td> <td data-bbox="466 1960 1098 2018">Country</td> <td data-bbox="1104 1960 1251 2018">Belgium</td> <td data-bbox="1257 1960 1367 2018">UK</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="466 2027 1098 2085">Qualitative method: semi-structured interviews with patients, using the PAVING interview guide</td> <td data-bbox="1104 2027 1251 2085">✓</td> <td data-bbox="1257 2027 1367 2085">✓</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Study features		PAVING study	HAEM study	PREFER strategy	Examines a rare disease	✓	✓	Is primarily conducted to inform HTA/reimbursement	✓	✓	Future decisions	Examines preferences regarding an advanced therapy	✓	✓	Methods	Country	Belgium	UK	Qualitative method: semi-structured interviews with patients, using the PAVING interview guide	✓	✓
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	Qualitative method: semi-structured interviews with patients, using the PAVING interview guide	✓	✓																						

	Quantitative preference elicitation method	Threshold technique	DCE
	Educational tool: tool developed in the PAVING study	✓	✓
PREFER research questions	How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods (2d1)	X	✓
	Examines which presentation formats respondents prefer (4a2)	✓	X
	Examines how generalizable preferences are from one disease to related diseases (9b)	✓	✓*
	Examines to what degree preferences vary with stakeholder perspective: patient vs caregiver (11b)	X	X
	Examines to what degree preferences vary with disease experience or severity (11d)	✓	✓
	Patients recruited through different channels (11k)	✓	✓
	Examines how to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/tailored to decision making (15b)	✓	X
✓: feature of the study X: not a feature of the study * PAVING and HAEM: Responses between haemophilia A and B will be compared Only HAEM: Responses from the qualitative phase (interviews) between the Belgian population in the PAVING study and the UK population in the current study will be compared			
Study Population			
Key inclusion criteria	Participants must meet all of the following inclusion criteria to be eligible for inclusion in the study: Aged 18 years or older; Must be able to read written English; You must live in the United Kingdom; Must be diagnosed with moderate or severe haemophilia; Voluntarily accept to participate in the study; Provide informed consent to participate in the study.		
Key exclusion criteria	Participants meeting any of the following criteria will not be included in the study: Aged younger than 18 years; Unable to read written English; You do not live in the United Kingdom;		

	<p>Not diagnosed with moderate or severe haemophilia; You do not voluntarily accept to participate in the study; You cannot provide informed consent to participate in the study.</p>
Setting	<p>Country: United Kingdom Qualitative approach: Interviews (online interview with clinical experts and patient advocates) Quantitative: Online survey</p>
Sample Size requirement (total and by country)	<p>Qualitative Phase: We want to conduct interviews with a mixed group of stakeholders to ensure we capture all perspectives when deciding upon the relevant attributes and levels. This group will include 8 clinical experts and a total of 10 people with haemophilia.</p> <p>Quantitative Phase: A minimum of 120 people with moderate or severe haemophilia (A or B) in the UK will participate in the online DCE. Recruitment will be managed and coordinated by the haemophilia society.</p> <p>Following the completion of the qualitative phase for the development of possible attributes and levels, a further exploration of minimum sample size requirements will be explored. Based on number of attributes and levels, the estimates for possible parameter (coefficient) values will be made to address any additional parameter requirements.</p>
Describe how patients will be included in the design and conduct of the preference study	<p>Patient involvement To ensure the study is patient relevant, the protocol will be setup with, and reviewed by patient representatives from the UK Haemophilia Society and HAEMNET.</p>
Outcome measurement (which endpoints need to be reported)	
Endpoints to be reported	<p>Endpoints / attributes and potential levels: The stages in which we will decide on the selection of attributes and levels that are appropriate for this study design are as follow. Targeted literature review: To identify any potential attributes already identified in the literature (clinical trials, previous patient preference studies and reimbursement criteria). DCE attribute and level development: Potential attributes and levels will be summarised for use in semi-structured interviews based on the findings of the targeted literature review. Semi-structured interviews with majority of key stakeholders: The proposed attributes and levels will be discussed further with feedback from different stakeholders (clinical experts and patient advocates) with the stakeholders</p>

ranking the proposed attributes. This will be completed with the majority of the identified stakeholders leaving a few for validation purposes.

DCE attribute and level refinement: Once a number of the semi-structured interviews have been completed the original list of attributes and levels will be refined based off the feedback.

Semi-structured validation interviews with remaining key stakeholders: The remaining semi-structured interviews will be used to validate the refined list of attributes and levels and any further feedback will be used to create the final attributes and levels before piloting.

DCE pilot testing in general population sample (for data quality check): The DCE will first be piloted with general population to ensure the attributes and levels are easily understood, with any required changes being implemented before being piloted with PWH.

Figure 1. Overview of attribute development and selection process

*Additional information provided in next slide

Patient characteristics:

Before completion of the DCE each participant will be asked to complete a survey to provide basic demographic information and clinical information about their condition. These will include questions on the following:

Baseline demographic questions include:

- Age
- Gender
- Ethnicity
- Marital status
- Employment status
- Education status
- Household income
- Region in UK
- Urban or rural location
- Acute and chronic comorbidities

Clinical information questions:

- Confirmation of moderate or severe haemophilia
- Type of haemophilia
- Current treatment regimen
- History of inhibitors
- Bleeding episodes in the past month

	<p>Muscle, joint or other bleeds in past 6 month Joint damage (problem joints) Location of joint damage Major procedure on a joint (fusion or replacement) in past 12 months Impact of haemophilia on daily life Time off work due to haemophilia Distance from health treatment centre Mode of transport Health insurance status</p> <p>Knowledge, comprehension and satisfaction questions: Knowledge about gene therapies for haemophilia A comprehension task to explore participant understanding Discussion with physician about decision to receive gene therapy Satisfaction with current treatment</p> <p>Potential results: The potential results that can be generated following the completed of the DCE are as follows: Magnitude and direction of attribute level coefficients Relative importance of each level within each attribute Trade-off between attributes (Marginal rate of substitution)</p>
Planning	
Deliverables related to this case study	Study protocol, statistical analysis plan, study report.
Estimated start	February 2020
Estimated completion	October 2020
Contributions	Antony P. Martin from HCD Economics will lead this study with his team. Eline van Overbeeke, Sissel Michelsen and Isabelle Huys from PREFER KU Leuven will collaborate with HCD Economics with the study design, through the qualitative phase (including interview guide, semi-structured interviews and framework method) and the quantitative phase.
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